

THE SOCIAL PRACTICE OF LEARNING

A case study exploring pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences from multiple perspectives.

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Abstract

An exploration of pre-registration nursing student practice learning experiences.

Practice learning experiences are a central component of pre-registration nurse education where student nurses spend 50% of their programme within the practice learning environment. The diversity of learning experiences offers student nurses the opportunity to develop the knowledge and skills to deliver safe and effective care. The literature reviewed confirmed that the student-mentor relationship is a fundamental aspect of effective practice learning experiences. In particular, the relationships formed, and the support students received from their mentor was crucial. However, it is clear the practice learning environment is complex, where supporting students' learning is multifactorial, yet research exploring the practice learning environment from multiple perspectives appears to be lacking.

This professional doctorate research used a case study design guided by Yin's (2018) approach to case study research. The participants included student nurses, mentors, liaison lecturers, practice education facilitators and a ward manager. Data was collected through focus groups and interviews over a seven-month period from June 2019 until January 2020. Following the analysis, the findings were compared to the literature to offer an understanding of how they supported, refuted, or added to the existing knowledge.

The findings identified two distinct yet interrelated themes. Theme one, *teamwork makes the dream work*, demonstrates how practice learning experiences are shaped by a wide range of relationships and social interactions centred around aspects of mutual support, collaboration and encouragement. Optimal practice learning environments were recognised as being inclusive and supportive. Whilst the student-mentor relationship was recognised as being crucial to a positive learning experience, students considered the support of their fellow peers as being invaluable. Theme two, *the emotional rollercoaster*, provided further insight into the complexities of the practice learning environment, which was regarded as being intensely emotional, where emotional ambivalence was often experienced.

Recognising this complexity, this research recommends that preparation and routine debriefing sessions are integrated within programmes of study where student nurses are adequately prepared and encouraged to critically reflect on their learning experiences. Furthermore, acknowledging the emotional demands on those supporting learning, peer support networks and facilitated reflective sessions should be encouraged for practice supervisors and practice assessors. Finally, this study recognised the value peers added to the

student journey; therefore, alternative collaborative models of learning that embrace peer learning and support should be considered.

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Glossary of Terms

Student	The term student denotes a student on a pre-registration nursing programme.
Mentor	Supports pre-registration nursing students teaching learning and assessment on placement. Defined by the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) as 'a registrant who following successful completion of an NMC approved mentor preparation programme has achieved the knowledge, skills and competence required to meet the defined outcomes.' (NMC, 2008)
Sign-off mentor	Sign-off mentors are registered mentors who have met additional criteria, who at the end of a programme of study make judgements whether the student has achieved the required standards for entry onto the register (NMC, 2008).
Practice Education Facilitator (PEF)	A registrant who provides guidance, advice and support to staff supporting learners (mentors) to enhance the quality of the practice learning environment.
Liaison Lecturer	Lecturer employed by the university with a remit to: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• provide pastoral support to students within the practice learning environment.• Quality assurance of the practice learning environments in partnership with the placement provider.

Chapter 1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to this Thesis.

Practice learning experiences are located at the core of pre-registration nurse education. These experiences aim to provide student nurses with diverse clinical learning opportunities in order to develop the knowledge and skills to deliver safe and effective care as a registered practitioner (Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC), 2018 a). The importance of learning within this clinical context has been widely acknowledged as it not only helps students practice skills in a real-world context but helps them develop their professional identity (Browne *et al.*, 2018). The supervisory relationship between the student and mentor has been highlighted as one of the most influential components of practice learning experiences (O'Mara, 2014). However, these experiences are multifaceted and whilst this relationship is integral, the literature suggests these experiences are shaped by multiple factors, including team interactions (Henderson *et al.*, 2010; Melincavage, 2011), pedagogical atmosphere, leadership and collaborative working (Warne *et al.*, 2010; Bisholt *et al.*, 2014). Indeed, Baraz, Memarian and Vanaki (2015., pp 52) describe the practice learning environment as an 'interactive network of forces that influences student learning', emphasising the complexity of learning within this real-world environment.

There appears to be an implicit understanding that a greater amount of time spent in the clinical learning environment positively influences nursing students' learning and ability to provide safe nursing care (Warne *et al.*, 2010). However, for many pre-registration nursing students, the practice learning environment can cause anxiety (Gibbons *et al.*, 2011), leading to high attrition rates, especially in those early placement experiences (Aston & Hallam, 2011). Therefore, understanding how these experiences are perceived could potentially enhance future pre-registration nursing programme design and practice learning experiences.

1.2 Personal Motivation for this Study.

The motivation for undertaking this research study is driven from a passion for the practice learning environment. Having been a registered nurse for almost 30 years, I have spent the last 15 years in various mentoring and education roles. As a mentor, I have had first-hand experience of the fulfilment supporting student nurses learning and development on placement. Furthermore, these mentoring experiences have also made me acutely aware of the daily challenges that are presented in balancing students' learning needs with care delivery in a busy clinical environment.

I have also witnessed many changes within pre-registration nurse education throughout my career. As the healthcare needs of the population change, so too has the role of the nurse as they strive to provide more complex care and fulfil advanced practice roles. The requirement for nurses to be highly trained, well-educated, critical thinkers is essential to enable them to make complex clinical decisions (Van Colln-Appling and Guiliano, 2017). This further emphasises the critical role practice learning experiences play in shaping the future nursing workforce. However, the challenges facing the practice learning environment have been widely debated (Panda *et al.*, 2021). Staff shortages and increased clinical caseloads all exert growing demands on the nursing role; more specifically, increasing demands on nurses' time have resulted in student learning needs not consistently being recognised as a priority (Thomson *et al.*, 2017; Veeremah, 2012).

Within my current role as an adult nurse lecturer, concerns have been raised anecdotally by students regarding their experiences. Lack of support, lack of engagement, lack of supervision and attitudes of the wider team towards student learners were often disclosed by the students when reflecting on their experiences. Similar findings have also been cited in the literature (Henderson *et al.*, 2012; Teatheredge, 2010; Gray and Smith, 2000).

The motivation for this study was also driven by the publication of several Government and professional body reviews, namely Raising the Bar Report – The Shape of Caring (Health Education England (HEE), 2015) and the Royal College of Nursing (RCN) mentorship project (RCN, 2015). Raising the Bar, commissioned by Health Education England in partnership with the Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC), questioned the quality and consistency of practice learning environments, suggesting that in relation to mentorship and effective practice-based education, significant variations existed (HEE, 2015). Moreover, the report described how a supportive learning culture within the practice environment influenced student attainment of learning outcomes and their motivation to remain on the programme. As such, they made several recommendations to ensure pre-registration nurse education practice learning experiences were of a high quality.

Simultaneously, in response to concerns raised regarding the facilitation of undergraduate nurse education in practice, the RCN commissioned a review of mentorship provision within the United Kingdom (RCN, 2015). They identified how positive mentoring relationships shaped learning experiences. The review findings emphasised the centrality of effective mentorship to support students' practice learning experiences.

However, several challenges were also illuminated; these included the complexity and the overly prescriptive nature of the NMC (2008) Standards to support learning and assessment in practice, a shortage of sign-off mentors, and a lack of protected time for mentors to undertake the role effectively. As a result, they recommended a review of the current mentorship provision where alternative models of mentorship should be considered in order to enhance practice-based learning in contemporary learning environments.

Both reports resonated with my own personal experiences, where the value of mentorship and challenges associated with supporting students learning was acknowledged in equal measure.

As mentioned above, although there is evidence to suggest the role of the mentor is crucial to the success of the student's learning experience (Teatheredge, 2010), a scoping search identified there is an apparent dearth of academic research into the complexities of this relationship. Furthermore, although the clinical learning environment has been of interest to nurse educators for many years, the research into this field has at times, been disparate with what would appear to be an imbalanced methodological focus on quantitative research tools and inventories.

1.3 Overview of this Study

Lave and Wenger's theory of situated learning (1991) and communities of practice (Wenger, 1998) served as the theoretical frameworks that guided this research. Here communities of practice and situated learning challenge the notion that learning is an individual activity; alternatively, they position learning as a social process that focusses on interaction (Lave and Wenger, 1991; Wenger *et al.*, 2002).

Acknowledging the complex multidimensional nature of practice learning experiences, a multidimensional approach to this research was required. Utilising a case study methodology, this research reviewed contemporary literature, collated placement information and retrieved data from focus groups and semi-structured interviews. To get an in-depth understanding of practice learning experiences, a range of participants were invited to take part; these included pre-registration nursing students, mentors, managers, practice education facilitators and liaison lecturers, thus providing a rich source of data exploring this complex social learning environment.

As a nurse lecturer with strong links to practice, I can appreciate the changing, challenging landscape of health care and the daily struggle nurses face to deliver high-quality care. This

research, therefore, should in no way be viewed as a criticism of current practice learning experiences. Instead, as recommended by the Royal College of Nursing (2015) and HEE (2015), it is an opportune time to explore practice learning experiences further in order to get a better, more in-depth understanding of this complex phenomenon. By involving key stakeholders, this research will attempt to explore and understand how their experiences are shaped.

At the outset of this study, the Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008) guided pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences; however, there was an awareness that these standards were under review. Although the research team understood the role of the mentor might change, there was an acknowledgement that regardless of the terms used to define the roles, practice learning within undergraduate nursing and midwifery programmes would continue. As such, on placement, students would still require support. Therefore, after discussions with the supervisory team, it was decided the study would still proceed. As the data collection commenced prior to the introduction of the Standards of proficiency for registered nurses (NMC, 2018a), the term mentor is used throughout most of this thesis. However, the new standards do feature; a brief overview is provided within the historical context of practice learning in the literature review and within the discussion where the findings are also explored in the context of these new standards.

1.4 Theoretical Framework.

As Grant and Osanloo (2014), explains the theoretical framework of any thesis is the foundation from which all knowledge is constructed, serving as a structure and support for the rationale, purpose and significance of the proposed research. Therefore, this section aims to

provide some discussion around the theoretical underpinning relating to teaching and learning within clinical practice.

There is a plethora of learning theories offering a complementary perspective of learning that have been used to explore pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences. A brief summary of the main theories (behavioural, cognitive, social and humanistic) is presented below (table 1).

Table 1 Summary of learning theories.

Learning theory	Assumptions
Behavioural learning theory	Emphasis is on observable behaviours that are recordable and measurable (Aliakbari <i>et al.</i> , 2015). If behaviour is rewarded or reinforced, a response is more likely to occur (Melincavage, 2008). Behaviourist theories purport that reward and reinforcement are instrumental to learning. Focussed on behavioural goals as the primary evidence of competence (Landers <i>et al.</i> , 2020). Educational practices including competency-based education linked to behaviourism.
Cognitive learning theory	Cognitive theories contend that internal mental processes, not exterior behavioural patterns, are what really matter when it comes to learning (Melincavage, 2008). Learning is more meaningful when connected to prior knowledge that the learner can relate to. Here the learner controls the learning process instead of the environment controlling the learning.
Social constructivist/Social learning theory	Strong emphasis on observational learning and highlights the importance of cognitive processes that occur during this (Landers <i>et al.</i> , 2020). Central to the concept of social constructivism is that learners form knowledge and make sense of the world within social contexts. This theory purports a reciprocal relationship between the learner and the environment (Melincavage, 2008).
Humanistic Learning Theory	Humanistic learning theories are underpinned by the assumption that adult learners are self-motivated controlling their own learning (Melincavage, 2008). Encourages individual student development and is student centred promoting individual growth (Landers <i>et al.</i> , 2020). Students are self-directed.

As can be seen from table 1, a range of diverse theories support the theoretical underpinning of learning; however, the frameworks used in this study are rooted within social learning theory (Melincavage, 2008). Both situated learning (Lave and Wenger, 1991) and communities of practice (Wenger, 1998) provide some explanation of the foundation of teaching and learning within the clinical learning environment and are critically explored in more depth in Chapter 3. These theories suggest that the sociocultural approach to learning occurs from lived

experiences within a specific context or culture, thus emphasising the importance of the environment where learning occurs and how this is linked to the learning process (Melincavage, 2008). For example, the practice learning environment is inextricably connected to how and what student nurses learn. It is through these experiences that they learn both the 'hands-on' physical skills of caring for patients and the social characteristics of the nursing profession (Melincavage, 2008). Moreover, as Jørgensen and Hadders (2015) suggest, legitimate peripheral participation and communities of practice are a useful lens to explore pre-registration nurse education as they have a strong emphasis on learning in practice and therefore provide the foundation for this research.

1.5 Structure of this Thesis.

This thesis follows a traditional structure that takes the reader through the research journey. Chapter one has set the context for this research; it provided the introduction and the personal motivation driving the topic of interest. This chapter concluded with a brief overview of the study including a summary of the theoretical frameworks that guided this research.

Chapter two is divided into two sections; section one considers the historical context of pre-registration nurse education. It presents the progression of practice learning within the United Kingdom and reflects on the policies and guidelines that have shaped this evolution. Section two of this chapter examines the contemporary literature related to pre-registration nursing practice learning experiences. Using a systemised approach to search and identify the literature, this section reports on the key themes that were identified.

Chapter three examines the different research philosophies and presents the chosen paradigm aligning with the research aim and objectives. A variety of different research methods are then considered before presenting case study as the most appropriate methodology. The remainder

of this chapter critically explores case study as a research design and how it will be applied to this study.

Chapter four explores the research design of this study, offering a rationale for the trajectory of the decisions made throughout this research process. This chapter focuses on the methods used, it considers the most appropriate tools for collecting the data and describes the boundaries of the case. It explores the ethical considerations and describes how the participants were recruited. Finally, this chapter concludes with a summary of the data analysis procedures used.

Chapter five presents the findings of this research; this includes the placement information and the narrative recollections of the participants' perceptions of practice learning experiences. This chapter is framed using direct quotes to illustrate and underpin the themes that emerged.

Chapter six presents a critical discussion; here, each of the themes are interrogated in relation to the relevant literature. Chapter seven concludes this thesis; firstly, a summary of how the research answered the aim and objectives are presented. Following this, there is a reflection on the research process that includes an acknowledgement of the strengths and weaknesses of this study. Finally, recommendations for practice and suggested areas for future study are presented.

To conclude, this chapter presented an overview of this thesis that explored the personal motivation and theoretical underpinnings that guided this research study.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

2.1 Introduction to Chapter

This chapter will briefly outline the historical background and critical discourse surrounding pre-registration nurse education and practice learning. This will be followed by a systemised review of contemporary literature that identified six themes, thus providing the context for this study. The literature review followed an iterative process that was reviewed as the focus of the study was refined and further developed; the literature was also revisited throughout the research process to ensure that any newly published material was included.

2.2 Historical Context

As previously mentioned, the practice learning environment is a central component within pre-registration nurse education as it allows students to apply theoretical knowledge within a real-life context (O'Mara *et al.*, 2014). Whilst it provides a platform where students can develop knowledge, skills and clinical competence, the practice learning environment also facilitates the development of their professional identity (O'Mara *et al.*, 2014). As such, it is often described as a complex social entity that can be challenging, exciting, unpredictable, and stressful (Baraz, Merriarian and Vanaki, 2015). Although learning and teaching within the workplace is by no means a new concept, balancing the complexities of clinical practice and social interactions combined with the pressures faced by student nurses explains why the practice learning environment is unique in terms of pre-registration nurse education (Henderson *et al.*, 2010).

Historically nurse education has been synonymous with an apprentice-style model of training (Attenborough *et al.*, 2019). This vocational model focused on 'on the job' learning, where the majority of nursing students were employed by the National Health Service (NHS) (Longley *et*

al., 2007). This traditional route was not completely without a theoretical basis. Although there was an element of classroom-based learning, education was centred on the practical component, where nursing students observed and practised skills within the clinical environments (Glen, 2009). At the point of registration, nursing students had already achieved a significant amount of experience and were considered to be 'work ready' (Greenwood, 2000); however, this model also faced criticism. Although they were perceived as invaluable members of the team, helping to deliver a service, limited attention was given to the student's personal development and individual learning needs (Andrews and Wallis, 1999). Specifically, very little time was dedicated to their learning as students were often exploited and used as a cheap source of labour (Greenwood, 2000). Moreover, this training model also represented a form of rote learning that prevented students from developing critical thinking skills. Alternatively, during the extended periods in clinical practice, students were socialised into nursing's authoritarian 'doing' culture (Stacey, 2014; Greenwood, 2000).

In 1985 the Royal College of Nursing commissioned the Judge report (RCN, 1985); the impetus of this report was centred around high attrition rates of nursing students, concerns regarding the increasing student numbers and the implications of this on clinical practice (Ousey, 2011). Their recommendations included strengthening the curriculum to include subjects such as sociology and psychology and awarding full student status to those studying a nursing qualification (Ousey, 2011). As such, the Judge report initiated the move of nurse education into higher education.

This move into higher education for all nurses and midwives signalled an educational reform of pre-registration nurse education. It was introduced throughout the United Kingdom in 1992 with the project 2000 initiative. At the time, this marked change was considered revolutionary as this programme saw pre-registration nurse education becoming integrated within higher

education, where nurses were awarded a diploma of higher education (Andrews and Wallis, 1999). As students were no longer employees, they were awarded supernumerary status. Here rather than being rostered as part of the workforce, they were able to observe and participate in care appropriate to their stage of the programme. However, for some students, this move created a sense of separation from the clinical environment (Hyde and Brady, 2002). In 2009 the NMC announced that by 2013, nursing would become an all-graduate profession (Ousey, 2011); for some, this was perceived as the final step of the passage towards professional recognition.

As pre-registration nurse education evolved, so too did the role of the mentor as the assessment and accountability of students within clinical practice became the responsibility of nursing and midwifery staff (Callaghan and McLafferty, 1997). Whilst the concept and philosophy of mentorship has been inherent within nurse education on an informal basis, this change prompted the formalisation of the role. In the context of pre-registration nurse education, the NMC, define a mentor as:

'a registrant who following successful completion of an NMC approved mentor preparation programme has achieved the knowledge, skills and competence required to meet the defined outcomes' (NMC, 2008, p 23.).

However, formalising the mentor role further prompted debates within the literature; despite the consensus that the role of the mentor was crucial to the development and support of nursing students in practice, concerns were quickly identified (Andrews and Wallace, 1999; Fulton, 2015). For example, across the United Kingdom, differing interpretations of the mentors' role and responsibilities were evident; this was primarily attributed to the ambiguity of the terminology, where the phrase mentor was used interchangeably with terms that included assessor, supervisor, preceptor and facilitator (Andrews and Wallis, 1999). Moreover,

tensions regarding role conflict were apparent where mentors were expected to support and guide but also formally assess the students (Fulton, 2015). Unsurprisingly, this led to a lack of continuity resulting in an inconsistent approach to the implementation of the mentor role within the practice learning environment (Fulton, 2015).

Recognising the need for consistency in relation to mentoring and development of those staff that support pre-registration nursing and midwifery students, the Nursing and Midwifery Council developed the Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2006), which were later updated in 2008. Although up to this point, mentorship was advocated, it was not until the introduction and implementation of these standards that mentorship became a mandatory requirement for all pre-registration student nurses and midwives whilst on placement. This framework defines eight domains that outline the knowledge and skills that a mentor requires to appropriately support and assess undergraduate students within clinical practice (see Appendix 1). These standards bound together academia and clinical practice by clearly defining the assessment roles in university by academic staff and in practice by clinical staff.

Whilst these standards were perceived as valuable as they recognised the importance of practice learning, some challenges were identified. As a requirement, the standards stated that all nursing students must be supported and assessed by a mentor (NMC, 2008) utilising a dyadic model of supervision. However, this model of supervision suggests that power relationships will inevitably exist, as it relies heavily on the mentor as they are solely responsible for passing or failing the student in practice (Fulton, 2015). In addition, the two key responsibilities of the mentorship role (support and assessment) are not mutually exclusive and could be perceived as contradictory (Fulton, 2015). As such, making judgements and assessing a student's performance in practice (particularly if a student is failing) conflicts with

the humanistic rhetoric described by the NMC (2008), where the mentor is also responsible for providing the student with nurturing support and guidance.

Concerns were also raised in practice due to the inflexible nature of the standards, as student nurses were required to spend a minimum of 40% of their time with their mentor (NMC, 2008). Compared to other practice-based education models within the Health and Care Professionals Council (HCPC), these standards appear overly prescriptive and potentially inhibit opportunities for inter-professional learning (RCN, 2015).

To summarise, the Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008) were introduced to ensure consistent, high-quality assessment and support of pre-registration nursing students and midwives within the practice learning environment. There were many positive aspects of these standards, particularly the introduction of a quality assurance framework where previously none had existed. However, they were developed in a very different economic climate through a consultation process (Turnbull, 2014). For example, as Andrews *et al.* (2010) explain, the number of pre-registration nursing students had increased significantly in the preceding ten years. In addition, more stringent financial constraints, staff shortages and increased student numbers imposed upon the practice learning environment suggest that this dyadic model is no longer financially viable (Turnbull *et al.*, 2014).

In response to Duffy's (2003) seminal research, which explored mentors' experiences of supporting failing students, NHS Education for Scotland (NES), in collaboration with NHS partners and Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), implemented a new role to enhance the practice learning experience for nursing students in Scotland. Practice Education Facilitators (PEFs) were employed in all NHS boards to contribute to the practice learning environment by providing advice, guidance and support to mentors. An evaluation of this new role indicated

that it added value to the practice learning environment, despite challenges related to PEF visibility in practice (Carlisle, Calman and Ibbotson, 2009). However, as mentors are often reluctant to fail students (Duffy 2003), there is the danger by introducing supporting roles such as the PEFs, mentors may devolve responsibility when making difficult decisions. This was alluded to by Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy (2017), who suggested that mentors still seek authorisation when failing students and do not always have confidence in their own decision-making. However, Hunt *et al.* (2016) argues seeking support from others provides guidance and reassurance to mentors when making difficult decisions. Despite the concerns explored above, the introduction of these supportive roles would appear to strengthen the practice education infrastructure and provide additional guidance to those supporting student nurses in practice (Carlisle, 2009; Devlin and Duggan, 2020).

Whilst the discourse around practice learning and mentorship has been widely debated, findings from a rapid review of mentorship purport that effective mentorship of pre-registration nursing students is required in order to bridge the gap between theory and practice (RCN, 2015). Good role modelling was identified as an essential component of mentorship, where mentors should demonstrate strong professional values and beliefs. This ethos was also threaded through the national preparation for mentorship (NES, 2013), which reinforced the influence of effective role modelling on student learning experiences. However, chronic staff shortages, continual service redesign and unrelenting clinical pressures, ultimately have an impact on mentors' ability to be effective role models (Vinales, 2015). Concerns related to current mentorship provision were also highlighted by Willis (2015), reporting that inconsistencies within practice learning were still evident throughout England. Their appraisal of pre-registration nurse education agreed that safe, effective practice learning experiences underpin the development of competent registered nurses; however, they

suggest that existing models of mentorship are not sustainable in the current healthcare climate. Moving forward, they recommended that the NMC review the practice of one-to-one mentorship. Both Willis (2015) and RCN (2015) endorsed approaches where the facilitation of students learning became everyone's responsibility rather than solely the mentors'. This could be achieved through piloted models of coaching, facilitation and mentoring where greater student numbers in the area could also maximize the capacity of the practice learning environment. However, the infrastructure to support some of these models is challenging; as such, trying to implement a consistent approach and equity of practice learning experiences for all students may be problematic (Rylance *et al.*, 2017).

2.2.1 Future Nurse: Standards of Proficiency for Registered Nurses.

Consequently, as a result of the concerns highlighted above, in 2016, the NMC began the process of consultation, working alongside key stakeholder groups to review the standards of education for nursing (Leigh and Roberts, 2018). The Future Nurse: Standards of proficiency for registered nurses were launched in 2018 (NMC, 2018a), with implementation within academic education institutions commencing roll out in 2019. These standards aimed to define the knowledge and skills the future generation of nurses and midwives would require to provide safe, effective care (NMC, 2018b).

Part two of the standards focuses on student supervision and assessment in practice, where three new roles were introduced: practice supervisor, practice assessor and academic assessor. Within the previous standards (NMC, 2008), only a registered mentor was able to support students' learning and assessment; in contrast, the practice supervisor role recognises that all registered nurses are able to support students learning (Duffy and Gillies, 2018). Through the introduction of the practice assessor role, a clear distinction between the role of assessor and supervisor has been created where those supporting students' learning cannot

simultaneously assess their practice (Leigh and Roberts, 2018). However, whilst the decoupling of the roles of support and assessment could lead to a more objective, robust student assessment, McGuinness *et al.* (2019) argue that this also introduces additional risks where the assessment process could become fragmented. The third new role introduced, the academic assessor, is required to work in partnership with the practice assessor to assess and make judgments on the student's progression (NMC, 2018a). These standards for student supervision and assessment introduced across the United Kingdom offers educational institutions and practice partners the opportunity to work collaboratively and strengthen partnerships (Duffy and Gillies, 2018).

To conclude, this section of the literature review has explored the history of pre-registration nurse education, focusing on practice learning. It describes how education has evolved over the years, moving from an apprentice-style model where nursing students were employees to becoming fully embedded within higher education institutions and being supernumerary within the practice learning environment. This section also considered the policies and guidance that have shaped practice education within the United Kingdom.

2.3 Review of Literature

2.3.1 Aim of the Review

The primary aim of this research study was to explore pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences; having provided a historical overview of practice learning, this next section of the literature review explores the contemporary literature relating to practice learning to offer the context for this research and identify any gaps within the current evidence. Phase one of the search strategy involved a systemised approach to identify the key

literature exploring pre-registration nursing practice learning experiences. However, as the review progressed and the researcher’s knowledge of the social complexity of learning in practice evolved, the search was further expanded to explore the areas associated with communities of practice, situated learning and the social context of learning (table 2).

2.3.2 Search Strategy

Three electronic databases were searched (Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature CINAHL, Medline and Journals@Ovid). These databases were chosen as it was anticipated they would yield the most relevant articles related to the research topic. When reviewing the literature, it was apparent that the terminology pertaining to practice learning was diverse, with terms such as practice learning, clinical learning, clinical placement and practice placement being used synonymously. Therefore, a wide-ranging combination of all keywords and terms was used to retrieve the most relevant evidence (see table 2).

Table 2 - Search Strategy

Key Terminology: Search 1	Key Terminology: Search 2
student nurs* AND practice learning OR clinical learning OR practice placement OR Clinical education	Student nurs* AND Communit* of practice
Student nurs*AND practice learning environment OR Clinical learning environment OR Clinical education environment	Student nurs* AND situated learning
Student nurs*AND mentor*OR preceptor*	Student nurs* AND social context of learning
Nurse education AND Student nurs* AND mentor*	

As mentioned previously, the literature review followed an iterative process. To ensure the literature search was both exhaustive and reflective of the contemporary nature of practice learning, the search was carried out from 2008 to the 11th of June 2019. The search was then re-run in May 2022 to ensure any recent literature was included.

The initial search retrieved a large number of articles; therefore, to keep the literature succinct, only research studies exploring pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences were included, those studies focusing solely on other healthcare professionals were excluded. As well as those located within the United Kingdom, studies from different geographical locations were included. The initial scoping search identified a breadth of relevant literature from an international perspective; furthermore, many of these countries have similar nurse education models, including an emphasis on practice learning, and as such, were considered relevant. The inclusion and exclusion criteria that were applied are presented in table 3. After searching the electronic databases, a hand search was carried out, reviewing all full-text articles; this was to ensure that no relevant research had been overlooked.

Table 3 Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Full-text articles written in English.	Other healthcare professionals
All geographical areas	Opinion pieces
All methodologies	Conference papers

The search strategy initially retrieved 319 articles; following the screening of all abstracts, this number was reduced to 56. Full texts were then retrieved and reviewed based on the inclusion/exclusion criteria and relevance. In total, for the review, 38 articles remained.

2.3.3 Quality Appraisal

The focus of this literature review was not to assess the quality of the evidence retrieved and disregard studies; rather, it was to identify the current knowledge and evidence base around pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences. However, critical appraisal allows the researcher to evaluate the evidence base in a structured way (Buccheri and Sharifi, 2017). For this review, to assess the rigour, trustworthiness, relevance and results the papers were critically evaluated using the McMaster University critical appraisal review tools (Lletts *et al.*, 2007). Whilst there are several critical appraisal tools available, the McMaster University review tools were chosen for the following reasons. Firstly, they offered a range of different tools depending on the nature of the research (quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods). Secondly, all tools were supported with comprehensive guidance to aid the process. Thirdly, having used them previously, the researcher was familiar with the critical appraisal tools. A summary of each of the articles reviewed, along with their methodology, geographical location, findings and limitations, is presented in table 4.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
Bennett and McGowan (2014) England	To explore mentors' experience of assessing pre-registration nursing students in clinical practice.	Qualitative. Realist Focus groups A total of 5 focus groups (n=35) mentors participated.	Changing roles and responsibilities – Participants described the confusion they experienced between the supportive elements of their role and the perceived negative aspects, notably that of being an assessor, Relatively few mentors have had experience dealing with a fail scenario. Lack of time to work with the student identified as a significant challenge impacting on student assessment.	Population – only mentors who had experience assessing students in the past year were purposively invited to participate – may well be a large population of mentors with issues that were not explored. No discussion of the relationship between the researcher to the participants. Only adult field mentors were included in the study. Unclear if the focus group formed part of their annual mentor update.
Bisholt <i>et al.</i> (2014) Sweden	Student assessment of the learning environment in different clinical settings.	Mixed methods. Three universities. Validated tool (CLES). Student participants were n=185. The settings explored were: Hospital, community, primary health care and mental health.	Overall satisfaction did not differ between placement areas. Hospital placement students agreed more strongly that sufficient meaningful learning occurred and that learning within these areas was multidimensional. Overall, the learning experiences reviewed were positive. Atmosphere of the PLE contributed to overall learning experience.	Hard to compare subgroups, e.g., MH only nine students. Only 3 rd year students – different anxieties and learning needs during their final placement. Unclear if MH placement was for MH students (different education systems limited the generalisability out with Sweden)

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
			Independence at times inhibited.	
Broadbent <i>et al.</i> (2014) Australia	Preceptor perspective supporting student nurses	Mixed methods Survey with Likert scale and qualitative comments, constructivist approach to this analysis. Preceptors n=34 (28% response rate.)	Being a preceptor was a positive part of the nurses' role. Role confusion and lack of time were highlighted as being problematic, lack of communication between service providers and the university regarding placement experiences. Beneficial having students provides the opportunity to discuss professional issues. Preceptors would like more training.	Poor response rate. Small scale One hospital trust. Self-rated questionnaires
Brown <i>et al.</i> (2012) Scotland	To explore mentorship practices supporting pre-registration nursing students.	Non-experimental postal survey design. Participants registered mentors across 6 NHS boards. (n=1760). 41% response rate	18% of mentors passed a failing student. 8% of these felt that the university would overturn their decision. Lack of confidence attributed to failing to fail. PEFs and LL are not visible in the areas; therefore, hard to build good relationships.	Not generalisable. Findings could have been more robust and explored further and cross-tabulated, e.g., those that said they had passed a failing student were they newly qualified as a mentor?
Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy (2017) United Kingdom	To develop a theoretical framework to explain how mentors make	Grounded theory, 1:1 interviews (n=20) and focus groups (n=38) All disciplines.	Reluctance to fail persists. When students were borderline, the study revealed that there was substantial conflict to derail mentors' decision-making.	Significant service reconfiguration and policy change simultaneously happened in line with the study and could have influenced mentors' responses.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
	sense of their experience		Effective management of borderline situations was achieved through collaboration. Conflict managing hopefulness.	No discussion or researcher relationship with participants. Local not specified, just UK.
Connor (2019) UK	Student perceptions of knowledge development and consolidation in a clinical community of practice	Qualitative descriptive Eight nursing students. Recruited from 3 fields of nursing (adult, child, and mental health).	The CoP provides an opportunity for students to gain tacit and explicit knowledge along with their professional identity. However, limited innovation or growth of the CoP was identified.	No disclosure of the different fields of nursing and how this may have influenced the results. Small sample size.
Courtney-Pratt <i>et al.</i> (2018) Australia	Nursing students' experience of being bullied in the clinical and academic settings.	Mixed methods sequential design. This paper presented feedback from qualitative feedback. A qualitative descriptive approach was used. Semi-structured interviews. 29 students (1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd year)	Students identified that bullying occurred in clinical. Bullying had a profound impact, including anxiety, depression, and confidence being undermined. No episodes were formally reported. Peer support helps build resilience.	Purposive sampling, although cited as a limitation appropriate for qualitative research. No account of experiences explored from different stages of the program.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
D'Souza, <i>et al.</i> (2015) Omani	Perception of and satisfaction with the clinical learning environment among nursing students	Clinical Learning Environment Supervision Teacher Evaluation 310 pre-registration nursing students.	Students valued supervision, leadership, and participation. Both nurse and patient relationships meaningful in supporting learning in the CLE.	100% response rate (? Perceived coercion). Only sampled students. Unclear what field of nursing participants were recruited. The clinical nurse educator role formed part of the assessment not applicable within all models of nurse education.
Foster, Ooms, Marks-Maran (2015) UK (London).	To gain an understanding of students' expectations and experiences of mentorship.	Mixed methods, exploratory sequential design. Student nurses. Focus group (n=12). Questionnaire - 53 students participated (45% response rate).	Overall, the experiences were positive. Students rated teaching support and supervision, and encouragement as the most valuable aspects of mentorship.	Likert scale used (pre-determined responses). Only one male student, which was not representative. Focus groups were carried out by the researcher that was known to the participants. One-sided perspective no mentors were involved in the study.
Gidman <i>et al.</i> (2011) England	Students' perceptions of support on placement.	Undergraduate nursing students were recruited from the first and final years. Mixed methods. Questionnaire and focus groups.	Students face external pressures. Primary sources of support were required for clinical skills, placement, documentation and personal issues. Valued support from peers Mentor main source of support	Only students' perceptions were reported. Students at the opposite end of the education spectrum, no input from second years.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
		Questionnaire starter students (N=174) Completion students (n=98) 4 x focus groups total student numbers n= 35		
Harrison-White and Owens (2018). UK (South England).	Nurse link lecturers' perceptions of the challenges facing student nurses in clinical learning environments.	Qualitative, grounded theory. Liaison/Link lecturers Focus groups (n= 10 participants) Follow-up 1:1 interviews (N=5).	Recognised mentors were the primary source of support for students. Students either 'fit in' and get access to learning or 'fall out' and learn to get through it.	Researcher known to participants in a senior position, may have influenced the views shared.
Hunt <i>et al.</i> (2016) UK (England)	Understanding what supports mentors' decisions to fail students.	Grounded theory. 31 nurses' experiences of failing student nurses on placement. Mentors (n=15) PEF (n=8) Liaison lecturer (n=8) All fields.	Support is essential for mentors during this time. Blurring of roles between assessment and support. Mentors frequently experienced anxiety related to their decisions.	Did not explore the validity and reliability of the mentors' judgements (the author did acknowledge this). All fields not equally represented. Blurred roles regarding recruitment, i.e., PEFs or LLs who were previous mentors, so drew upon those experiences.
Jack <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Reporting of decisions students	Descriptive narrative Mixed methods.	In general, placements were perceived positively.	Unclear what the sample size was; only the response rate given.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
UK (North England)	made in relation to staying or leaving the nursing programme. This paper reports on the perceived unfairness students experienced.	Students who had discontinued their programme were invited to complete the survey. (n=1425) Interviews (n=22)	Lack of time for teaching and learning identified. Supportive mentors were crucial in guiding the students' study. Supernumerary status was not supported.	Fields of nursing not explained.
James and Chapman (2014) Australia	Nursing students' experience of their first clinical placement.	Qualitative. Phenomenology 6 first year first placement students	Students described feeling overwhelmed seeing how patients dealt with and lived with illness. Preceptors and mentors influenced their overall experience. Felt a burden, not welcomed, intimidated receiving feedback.	Unequal relationship between students and researcher, researcher known well to participants.
Joklainenen <i>et al.</i> (2013) Finland and England	Finnish and British mentors' conceptions of facilitating nursing students' placement learning and professional development.	Focus groups phenomenographic approach. Mentors N = 39	Teaching and learning should be student focused. PLE should be fit for purpose. Ongoing assessment of students' achievements viewed as significant.	More than one facilitator in focus groups potentially inhibited participant responses. The author recognised the conversational nature of the focus groups could have encouraged group effect.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
Koontz <i>et al.</i> (2010) USA	Staff nurses and students, the good, the bad and the ugly.	Descriptive, qualitative, exploratory. Sample 10 senior nursing students.	Being with a mentor helped them feel part of the team. Factors of good mentoring identified. Learning is also identified from poor mentors. Increased responsibility increased their confidence.	Only 3 rd year students, not representative of the student population. Only students involved.
Levett-Jones and Lathlean (2008) Australia	Belongingness a prerequisite for nursing students' clinical learning.	Qualitative interviews. 18 participants.	Students reported feeling safe, comfortable, supported and self-motivated when in an area that facilitated their belongingness. The registered staff with whom the students worked with daily were the most critical factor in enabling belongingness.	Not apparent what factors enhance/engender belongingness. Only selected findings are presented in this paper.
Liljedahl <i>et al.</i> (2016) Sweden	Nursing students' interactions in the practice learning environment.	An ethnography-inspired qualitative study. Observations, interviews. Three hospital sites in Sweden. Six days observations. Follow-up interviews with 2 students, 3 supervisors, and 2 managers.	Students aspired to fulfil their role; however, they frequently became overwhelmed with the responsibility of caring for patients. When values did align, students did not compromise. The workplace readily invited students in.	The sample population is unclear (presume adult nursing field). Three different sites were used, limiting the researcher's ability to engage with the environment deeply. Observer effect possible in field observations.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
Manninen <i>et al.</i> (2013) Sweden	Exploring first year nursing students' experience in practice.	19 first year student nurses participated from a sample of 28. Individual and group interviews were used.	Belongingness and mutual respect are necessary.	Small scale, specific and unique learning unit explored as such findings may not be transferrable.
McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith (2014) UK	Mentors	Descriptive Mixed methods. Mentors. Questionnaire n=61 (46.9% response rate). Two focus groups with mentors (N=13)	Student support acquiring skills ranked as the most important. Recognised the importance of student peers. Students should have a willingness to learn.	No discussion of the relationship to researchers. Two trusts (one community and acute) no exploration of the different patients/caring needs and if this impacted on mentor provision.
Mead, Hopkins and Wilson (2011) UK (Wales).	Nurse mentors' views on their role.	A mixed methods survey (using interactive technology) is reported here. 94 participants. Mentors (n=69) Sign off mentors (n=6) practice educators (n=19).	Mentors would not feel pressured to pass a failing student. Mentors were unconcerned about being branded as bad mentors if they failed a student. Mentors felt they had sufficient training.	Participants were recruited from a mentor study day, therefore potentially an already motivated population group. Furthermore, information was within the welcome pack, and all attendees participated, suggesting possible coercion as thought it was part of the conference. Interactive technology was used, therefore limited exploration of the reasons for responses.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
Melincavage, (2011) USA	Student nurses' experiences of anxiety in the clinical setting	Phenomenology 7 students participated via unstructured interviews.	Students who experienced anxiety were demeaned, felt abandoned felt exposed due to their inexperience.	A small sample of only 7 students.
Minton and Birks (2019) New Zealand	Nursing students' experiences regarding the nature and extent of bullying on placement.	Cross-sectional survey. This study presented a thematic analysis of the qualitative texts. 296 surveys returned	Students were subject to and witnessed bullying and harassment behaviours. Covert behaviours displayed. Preceptors/mentors are the most common perpetrator. Caused physical and psychological effects, even caused some students to leave the programme,	All students were invited to participate, no record of how many this was. Also, no account provided from the sample the percentage that were witness to/experienced bullying behaviours. Also, the study title attracted those who had only witnessed poor practices, no good practices explored.
Molesworth, (2017). (UK) Scotland	Nursing Students' First Placement: Peripherality and Marginality Within the Community of Practice	Qualitative, deductive content analysis. Interviews and focus groups with first year student nurses (17)	Peripherality supports learning however being marginalised can be disempowering. Mentors and Liaison lecturers played a central role in supporting participation with the CoP.	Analyst-driven deductive analysis. Relatively small sample size from one University in Scotland.
O'Driscoll Allan and Smith (2010). England	Exploration of leadership and students' practice	Mixed methods Ethnographic led case study.	A range of leadership roles were identified, e.g., ward managers, link lecturers etc. however, mentors lead student learning in practice.	Limited information is given with regard to fieldwork observations. A poor response rate of online survey (20%).

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
	learning experiences.	<p>Case study and Fieldwork in 4 NHS sites.</p> <p>Pre-registration nursing students: Online survey (<i>n</i>=937). individual interview (<i>n</i>=8) Focus group (<i>n</i>=3)</p> <p>Focus groups and interviews were carried out with. Lead nurses (<i>n</i>=10) Ward managers (Mentors (<i>n</i>=6) Link lecturers (<i>n</i>=8) PD nurses (<i>n</i>=11) Placement coordinator (<i>n</i>=1) Practice educator (<i>n</i>=5)</p>	<p>HCSW also influenced learning.</p> <p>Supernumerary status was not standardised across all sites.</p> <p>Managers identified that supernumerary status inhibited learning, especially in busy areas.</p> <p>Mentors did not believe that being supernumerary prepared students for practice—the apparent tension between being supernumerary and part of the workforce.</p>	<p>Not all participant groups across all sites were equally balanced – some areas had no participants.</p>
O'Lunaigh (2015) Ireland	Exploring the influence of nurses on nursing students. Case study	Case study focus groups (registered nurses) interviews students (<i>n</i> =5)	Interaction with others influences learning.	Mentor sample not clear number in the focus groups not recorded.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
O'Mara <i>et al.</i> (2014) Canada	Challenging clinical learning environments	Qualitative. Focus groups. 54 undergraduate nursing students.	Students identified that a challenging clinical environment resulted in decreased learning. Less likely to ask questions if felt uncomfortable. Students became self-reliant.	Unable to link study findings to programme sites (participants were recruited from 2 different programmes). Participations could be considered as those students accessing somewhere to vent.
Papastavrou <i>et al.</i> (2016) Cyprus	Nursing students' satisfaction with the clinical learning environment.	Quantitative Descriptive. Tool CLES+T. N=463 undergraduate students, three universities. 70.3% response rate.	Year 1 students had higher levels of satisfaction. Having a named mentor equated to higher satisfaction levels. Mentorship relationships are the most critical factor in the CLE.	Students had only experienced short placements, unable to assess the CLE adequately. Quantitative study limited understanding of the views and perceptions explored.
Papathanasiou, Tsaras and Sarafis (2014) Greece	To assess nursing student views and perceptions of the clinical environment in Greece.	Quantitative, descriptive survey CLEI. N=196 students (65.3%)	A noticeable gap between students' actual and preferred experiences. Greater acceptance and belongingness are linked to higher student satisfaction. Task orientation is also an indicator.	Self-reported questionnaire (answers can be socially desirable). One university.
Roxburgh (2014) Scotland	Evaluation of a hubs and spokes model of practice compared with	Qualitative (although part of mixed methods study). Focus groups	Although preferred hubs and spokes model recognised the value or rotational. Reflecting on the previous H&S model, belongingness is evident. Longer placement, students were able to build a	A small study evaluating a specific model, hard to say if the student would have felt the same had they not been part of the pilot study, as there was no comparison.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
	traditional rotational.	Second year nursing students who had been part of the initial trial. 35 students.	relationship, trust and respect between themselves and their mentor. Resilience from their year one experience allowed them to stay on the programme. Continuity of mentorship enhanced learning.	
Rylance <i>et al.</i> (2017) England	An evaluative study of student nurse mentoring.	169 mentors from all fields	Mentors were satisfied with their role as a mentor, on the whole, enjoyed having students. Frustrations with the role included a lack of time and supporting students who lacked interest.	Not all fields of study are equally represented, e.g., 74% mental health and 15% adult nursing. The overall sample size is unclear. Recruitment detail not specified. Possible coercion data collected as part of mandatory mentor update. Ethics not disclosed.
Smedley and Morey (2009). Australia	Improving learning in the clinical nursing environment: perceptions of senior Australian Bachelor of Nursing Students.	Quantitative. CLEI 65 participants Response: actual n= 55 (84.6%). Preferred (n = 38, 58.4%).	The preferred experience was rated statistically significantly higher than their actual experiences. Recognised that all clinical experience evaluated well, recognised room for improvement. Students are realistic about what PLE can offer.	No attempt to code responses; therefore, unable match actual and preferred responses; as such, the inconsistent response rate means comparisons between the two tools are limited.
Teatherddge, (2010) UK	Interviewing students and qualified nurses to	Students (8) interviews. Mentors' questionnaire	A positive attitude towards learning and mentoring is essential. Lack of time to mentor.	Limited information regarding ethics, although stated as part of a more extensive study.

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
	find out what makes an effective mentor.	Sample of 270 (23% response rate)	More support is required for mentors.	No information regarding the analysis.
Thomas, Jinks and Jack (2015) UK	Finessing Incivility.	Grounded theory, data retrieved from student diaries. 30 students participated only 14 returned their diaries.	Students often experience incivility and developed mechanisms to cope with this.	Diaries reliant on accurate and honest recollection of the situation, no other participant groups involved.
Thomson, Docherty and Duffy (2017). UK (Scotland)	Nursing students' experiences of mentorship in their final placement.	Qualitative phenomenology. Unstructured interviews, 7 final placement students participated.	Several themes were identified, including belongings, anxiety, support, feedback and being more independent.	A very small study, at times, the study was presented in an overly descriptive text. For example, although it identifies belongingness as a theme, it does not discuss why this was important to students' final placement experience.
Turnbull <i>et al.</i> (2014) UK	Report on commissioned study. An investigation of mentorship and mentorship preparation.	Appreciative enquiry. Focus groups. Mentors and student mentors across 4 NHS trusts. 15 student mentors. Survey with current mentors n=16 (8% response rate)	Support mentors received varied. Reason for undertaking mentoring included CPD, managers request. The mentorship course helped develop new mentors.	Poor initial response rate. One of the aims was to ascertain reasons for not completing the mentor preparation course; however, the research team were unable to recruit participants from this group. The student mentors had not yet passed the module assessment;

Study and location	Aim	Research design (methodology/data collection/participants).	Findings	Limitations
				therefore, their responses may well have been influenced by this.
Veeremah (2012) UK	Barriers to effective mentoring	Mentors sample n=346, 58% response rate.	Mentors identified a lack of time to adequately mentor. Practice assessment documentation is an area of concern. Managerial support helped fulfil the role. The integrity of the mentor role maintained.	Checklist was used for data collection with pre-determined questions limiting responses.
Warne <i>et al.</i> (2010). Multiple European countries.	An exploration of the clinical learning experience of nursing students in nine European countries	Quantitative. Used previously validated tool (CLES+T). 17 schools across 9 countries. Student participants (n=1903)	Longer placement statistically linked to improved satisfaction. The supervisory relationship is also highlighted as key to a successful placement experience.	Not able to generalise findings due to size and cross-sample. Quantitative study did not allow for the exploration of context or provide any in-depth detail, i.e., conceptualising what satisfaction means. Self-reported questionnaire.

Table 4 Summary of articles reviewed.

2.3.4 Identifying the Themes.

The selected papers were analysed through a process of reading and re-reading to identify the key concepts and findings as recommended by Holm, Berland and Severinsson (2016). These were then tabulated; the visual representation was useful in identifying the connection between the studies and the emerging themes. Some of the themes appeared to be inextricably linked, where there was some noticeable overlap. For example, belongingness was often associated with the student-mentor relationship and/or student support within the practice learning environment. However, merging these themes would not have allowed the nuances and understanding of each to be explored in depth. In total, six themes emerged from the review of the literature; belongingness, the student mentor-relationship, student support, mentoring, the practice learning environment, and challenges (see diagram 1).

Diagram 1.

This next section presents a discussion of each of the themes that emerged.

2.4 Literature Review Themes

2.4.1 Theme: Belongingness

The necessity for pre-registration nursing students to achieve a sense of belonging and the impact this had on their practice learning experiences was a consistent theme seen throughout the literature. Belongingness within the practice learning environment has been written about extensively and is defined as the intrinsic human need to feel secure, accepted, included, and valued within a group (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008). Moreover, having a sense of belonging has been identified as a prerequisite for student success within the practice learning environment (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016).

Within the literature, the concept of belongingness was articulated by student nurses in several ways; however, it appeared to be rooted within supportive learning environments that promote inclusivity where student nurses feel accepted and valued as part of the team (Smedley and Morey, 2010; Melincavage, 2011). In particular, supportive learning environments were identified as having a positive effect on student learning as they cultivated a sense of belonging (Smedley and Morey, 2010). In contrast, if learning environments were perceived as being unsupportive, students learning was often thwarted as they were less likely or willing to ask questions as they did not feel comfortable and feared making mistakes (O'Mara *et al.*, 2014; Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016), thus leading the students to become disconnected from the practice learning environment (James and Chapman, 2010).

For students, the acceptance from the clinical staff was perceived as essential, specifically their mentor and the registered staff they worked with on a daily basis, where this acceptance helped them feel they were a part of the team (Koontz 2010; Levett-Jones and Lathlean 2008; Manninen, 2013). Indeed, students commonly reported how feeling part of the team led to a

higher level of satisfaction with their placement experience (Thomson *et al.*, 2017; Melincavage, 2011; James and Chapman, 2010; Smedley and Morey, 2010). These findings resonate with Maslow's hierarchy of needs, where if an individual's belonging needs are met, they can progress towards self-actualisation (Hopper, 2020). Within the literature, it was clear when students experienced this acceptance and belongingness, they were able to concentrate on the available learning opportunities rather than focusing on trying to fit in (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, these positive relationships between clinical staff and students enabled the students to participate within the community of practice rather than feeling left in the periphery (Smedley and Morey, 2010). This notion of participation and the links to belongingness resonate with the work of Thomson, Docherty and Duffy (2017); here, they identified how being entrusted to deliver patient care gave students an invitation into the learning environment. In addition, this helped promote a sense of achievement which in turn made them feel accepted (Minton and Birks, 2019; O'Lunaigh, 2015). This not only emphasises the importance of participation and inclusivity but describes how belongingness and trusting relationships are intertwined. Wegner identified that there may be a number of barriers present that inhibit participation (Wenger, 1998). However, they argue that the negotiation of meaning within a community of practice involves both participation and reification, where the interplay between these complementary processes plays a significant role in shaping learning.

Having a sense of belongingness and the intrinsic need to be accepted appears to be anchored within the development of effective interpersonal relationships between the student and the rest of the team. The motivation to feel part of the team and contribute to patient care can be seen as an example of legitimate peripheral participation where students value participation as a means for gaining access to the community of practice (Connor, 2019).

In contrast, there was evidence to suggest when a sense of belonging did not exist, this had a damaging effect on students' learning experiences, emotional health and well-being (Melincavage, 2011). There were examples referenced in the literature where a lack of belongingness led to stress and anxiety, where students were left feeling demoralised (Melincavage, 2011; O'Luanaigh, 2015). Additionally, students' self-esteem was negatively affected when they were demeaned or ignored by qualified staff (Melincavage, 2011). Consequently, these negative feelings not only inhibited students' learning but generated a sense of uncertainty (Manninen *et al.*, 2013). For some students, a reduced sense of belonging created feelings where they did not feel respected or valued. This was exemplified when there was a failure to address the student by their name; this simple behaviour was described by the students as demoralising (O'Luanaigh, 2015). Likewise, there was evidence to suggest if inclusivity was lacking, this caused feelings of abandonment that resulted in a loss of trust in the relationship (Melincavage, 2011). Again, this links to the importance of developing effective interpersonal relationships and suggests that if feelings of mistrust emerge and belongingness is not engendered, the relationship cannot flourish.

Arguably forging effective relationships and developing a sense of belonging does not happen instantaneously and takes time; however, the design of the pre-registration nursing curriculum and the organisation of practice learning experiences do not always afford students this luxury (Roxborough, 2014). The current rotation model based on a series of several short placements can be challenging for some students as they are required to start over and reinvent themselves in each practice learning area.

The desired motivation to be accepted and belong within the practice learning environment offered an interesting insight into students' behaviour. In order to 'fit in' students often forfeited their rights to supernumerary status (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008; O'Mara *et al.*,

2014), as such learning opportunities were often compromised as students appeared more concerned with being accepted rather than focusing on their learning needs. For some students, although they were welcomed and included within the teams, this membership was conditional, where students were expected to conform to routines and working practices (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016). In particular, they described how students often conform to workplace norms and practice in an effort to gain acceptance; as a result, it would appear from their research that belonging to the group may be more important than following one's own principles.

According to Wenger, learners experience three modes of belonging while creating an identity within a community of practice: engagement, alignment and imagination (Wenger, 1998). Engagement is achieved through direct experience, active involvement, and working together; imagination is the personal and collective images of the world that locate individuals in a range of contexts where alternative possibilities are generated. Finally, alignment occurs when individuals direct their energies aligning with standards towards a shared goal, connecting their practice to the broader context (Smith, Hayes and Shea, 2017; Grealish and Ranse, 2009). In relation to student nurse's experiences on placement, both Morley (2016) and Grealish and Ranse (2009) describe how barriers to challenging situations and engagement can be overcome through the use of imagination and alignment, where students consider alternative possibilities and link their own practice to the wider professional context.

There were some examples of this within the literature; when students experienced alienation, there was evidence to suggest positive experiences were still achievable in spite of the difficulties encountered (O'Mara *et al.*, 2014; Koontz *et al.*, 2010). Here students sought other forms of support from their peers and other members of staff, becoming responsible for their own learning and seeking out alternative learning opportunities. In addition, students used

'imagination' to envisage alternative possibilities reflecting on how this could influence their future practice (O'Mara *et al.* 2010). These findings demonstrate that although the need to feel included is a natural instinct, when this was contested, the students relied on their personal resilience.

However, it is worth noting this was not always the case; for some students, the alienation and incivility they experienced caused them to reassess their career choices and leave the programme of study (Minton and Birks, 2019).

Many of the experiences described in the literature potentially relate to the inherent cultures present within the practice learning environment, where each area provides a different social context with their own norms, routines and practices. The literature reviewed goes some way to uncover the social constructs that exist within the communities of practice and demonstrate how being ignored and not feeling welcomed can consequently affect student morale (Melincavage, 2011).

The literature emphasises that the intrinsic human need to be accepted within a social group is just as applicable to the practice learning environment; in particular, students value welcoming behaviours that promote inclusiveness (Smedley and Morey, 2010; Melincavage, 2011). In terms of enabling students to feel part of the team, it appears that mentors are ideally placed to ensure that students are accepted within these communities through personal endorsement. However, acceptance and membership within a community of practice is established through mutual engagement (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016); therefore, the interaction between both parties is interdependent. Having said that, most of the evidence related to belongingness and how this is experienced is reported from students' perceptions. It potentially lacks insight into their engagement and how practice learning environments invite students into their agency. While there is an implicit assumption that belongingness and

acceptance lead to a more favourable practice learning experience, it is not clear from the literature how belongingness is engendered.

In addition, although belongingness has been widely explored within the context of practice learning, how this was experienced varied considerably across the evidence reviewed. This suggests within practice learning environments; there appears to be a lack of understanding of the concept of belongingness and the impact it can have upon learning experiences.

2.4.2 Theme: The Student-Mentor Relationship

Another emergent theme from the evidence reviewed was the importance of the relationship between the student and mentor, where a positive relationship was described as the foundation of a successful practice learning experience (Helminen, Tossavainen and Turunen 2014; Warne *et al.*, 2010). This relationship was often contextualised by the qualities of an effective mentor, where a range of factors were identified that support the foundation of an effective student-mentor relationship (Gibbons, 2011). From the student's perspective, a good mentor provides guidance and reassurance, particularly in the initial exposure to a new practice learning environment, as students could often feel anxious and apprehensive (James and Chapman, 2010; Teatheredge, 2010). Moreover, students identified that having a positive attitude towards mentoring and being compassionate and motivated to support student learning were essential mentor qualities (Koontz *et al.*, 2010). Personal attributes such as being friendly, approachable, understanding and patient were also seen as being essential (Gidman *et al.*, 2011). These interpersonal skills appeared to underpin an effective student-mentor relationship.

It is also clear from the literature that the relationship developed between the student and mentor had a profound effect on the student's overall learning experience, where having a trusting relationship with their mentor allowed the students to observe, practice and learn within this secure relationship (Teatheredge, 2010). Likewise, Molesworth (2017) suggests that the opportunity for students to participate is often dependent on their mentor; therefore, students focused on building a good rapport. This further emphasises the significance of the student-mentor relationship as it is through an effective interpersonal relationship that students are afforded the opportunity to gain access to the available learning opportunities and practices within the community. This notion of mentors being the gatekeepers draws parallels with the concept of legitimate peripheral participation. Through sponsorship from a more experienced other, newcomers gain access to the knowledge, cultures and activities of the community, whereby they develop a shared identity (White, 2010). Moreover, where this sponsorship is lacking, students can feel alienated as they have an insecure identity within the community of practice (White, 2010).

However, it is proposed for the student-mentor relationship to flourish; the responsibility lies with both parties. O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith (2010) argue that the development of an effective relationship is based on partnership and is the mutual responsibility of both parties in shaping practice learning experiences. Students should arrive prepared for practice with a readiness to learn (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014; Joklainenen *et al.*, 2013; McIntosh, Smith and Gidmen, 2014; O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith, 2010). Moreover, students' preparation for practice and willingness to learn demonstrates their desire to engage within the community of practice (Connor, 2019). This indicates that both the mentor and student need to be invested in this relationship for it to be successful.

However, this also highlights how the opportunities to learn are centred around the student's position in relation to the power dynamics. Ultimately as gatekeepers, mentors are in a position of dominance as they are responsible for organising learning and making judgements on the student's performance (Harrison-White and Owens 2018). As such, the student's position of vulnerability may have a detrimental impact on their practice learning experiences if their learning opportunities are limited.

The existing evidence is very clear that the degree of support received within practice learning greatly influences how students perceive their experiences. Students frequently identified that support from their mentor was often lacking, which left them feeling exasperated with low self-esteem, thus impacting on their satisfaction with the practice learning experience (Thomson *et al.*, 2017; Foster *et al.*, 2015). Specifically, within their final practice learning experience, students described how more support from their mentor was essential, where the lack of support effected their levels of confidence on placement (Thomson *et al.*, 2017). Yet, this expressed need for more support from their mentor is contrary to the seminal work carried out by Bondy (1983), who suggests by this stage in the programme, students should be using their own initiative and relying less on their mentor. Therefore, the desired need for more support poses a challenge for mentors as they try to balance the support needs of the student whilst encouraging them to work towards becoming an independent practitioner.

In contrast, too much support was recognised by some students as having a negative impact on their practice learning experience. There were instances where students wanted to become more autonomous and were left feeling frustrated if this was not supported by their mentor (Bisholt *et al.*, 2014). Despite the contrasting findings reported, it is noteworthy that too much or too little support can cause frustration and distress. This suggests that there is a potential

dichotomy occurring between what students and mentors feel is an appropriate level of support. It also raises the importance of not only identifying individual student learning needs but communicating these effectively to ensure the support provided in practice meets both the mentor and student expectations.

When exploring the concept of support within the practice learning environment, there was a general consensus that one-to-one supervision was linked to higher student satisfaction (Warne *et al.*, 2010; Papastavrou *et al.*, 2010). Here students who were allocated a named mentor rather than a group supervision model evaluated their placement more favourably. One possible explanation for this is that a one-to-one model allows for a more individualised experience, where mentors can cater for the student's individual learning needs; moreover, having an identified named person to support the student helps build personal relationships (Warne *et al.*, 2010).

However, it has been argued that traditional one-to-one models of mentor support are not sustainable in the current healthcare climate (Rylance *et al.*, 2017). As mentioned previously, continual service redesign, staff shortages and an ageing workforce have all been cited as contributing to mentor shortages within the United Kingdom (RCN, 2015). As discussed earlier in this chapter, to address the workforce challenges, recommendations have been made that move away from the traditional one-to-one models of supervision (RCN, 2015; Wills, 2015). Interestingly, this move to alternative models of supervision appears to contradict the evidence, as one-to-one mentoring relationships have been identified as an important factor impacting on practice learning experiences (Warne *et al.* 2010; Papastavrou *et al.* 2010).

2.4.3 Theme: Support from Others

Although the relationship students had with their mentor was considered crucial to their overall practice learning experiences throughout their placement, students inevitably sought support from other invaluable sources. Fellow peers were acknowledged as a valuable resource (Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018; Thomas, Jinks and Jack 2014). In particular, students discussed how other students and newly qualified nurses were enthusiastic and motivated in their attitude towards providing support (Gidman *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, their peers were able to provide reassurance which appeared particularly beneficial to early career students.

The significance of peer support appeared to be invaluable when students experienced incivility or episodes of bullying within their practice learning experience (Thomas, Jinks and Jack 2014; Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018). More specifically, students described how having fellow students on placement to discuss and debrief with, helped enhance their resilience (Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018). This demonstrates that although mentors are generally considered the main line of support for students, peer support can also be a valuable contribution. However, there is a lack of contemporary evidence available to understand how peer support is consistently utilised within practice learning experiences.

In relation to support from other staff within the practice learning environment, it is clear that learning does not happen within a vacuum as other healthcare workers inevitably impact upon these experiences. Collaborative working within the multidisciplinary team was identified as important by some students (Manninen, 2013). In particular, working with other healthcare professionals appeared to enable students to not only understand their role, but also help shape their professional development as it provided an insight into how the role of the nurse

related to other professionals (Manninen, 2013). Several studies also made reference to the influence of healthcare support workers (HCSW) on students' practice learning experiences (Thomas, Jinks and Jack, 2015; McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith, 2014; O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith, 2010; Jack *et al.*, 2018). In the absence of their mentor, HCSWs played a central role in supporting students, allowing them access to learning opportunities and sharing their knowledge (Thomas, Jinks and Jack, 2015).

Similarly, McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith (2014) recognised the valuable contribution healthcare support workers could add to the student's development and engagement. However, the influence of HCSW on students' practice learning experiences was not always viewed positively. Some students perceived working alongside the HCSW was detrimental to their learning as they were often used as a 'free pair of hands' (Jack *et al.*, 2018, pp 932). Yet O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith (2010) argue, as registered nurses are often required to focus on the technical aspects of care, the majority of bedside care is delivered by HCSW. Therefore, by working alongside HCSW, student nurses are exposed to invaluable learning opportunities.

Finally, in relation to support, some students highlighted that there was a lack of support from faculty staff throughout their practice learning experience. There was an indication from students that support was often lacking where access to a link or liaison lecturer from their programme of study was not always forthcoming (Foster, Omms and Mark-Maran, 2015).

2.4.4 Theme: Mentoring

The majority of evidence reviewed analysed practice learning experiences from the students' perspective; however, there were some insights provided into how this relationship could also be beneficial to mentors' own personal development (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014; Rylance *et al.*, 2017). There was a distinct acknowledgement that mentors were committed to their role in supporting students learning and development; terms such as rewarding, inspiring and satisfying were referred to when acknowledging the positive aspects of mentoring (Turnbull *et al.*, 2014).

Mentors also identified that having a student encouraged them to keep up to date with current evidenced-based practices, as students often brought a fresh perspective (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014; Rylance *et al.*, 2017). In particular, they recognised how working with a student encouraged them to reflect on their own practice. Moreover, spending time with students offered mentors an opportunity to debate contemporary issues in nursing (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014) and learn from each other.

When exploring the theoretical underpinning of communities of practice, White (2010) explains how communities continually evolve and learn through a process of shared learning. This collaborative learning can enrich communities when newcomers challenge accepted cultural practices that result in change (Morley, 2016). Within the context of the practice learning environment, it is clear that students can add value to the community, demonstrating the reciprocal learning that can occur. Moreover, this reveals how supporting students within the practice learning environment can also be a significant gain for mentors. However, this acceptance to engage with, and learn from students, was not consistent across the literature.

Indeed, Connor (2019) argues practice learning environments are often focused on the status quo, where practice is maintained and reproduced therefore, they have limited scope for innovation and creativity.

Throughout this review, mentors frequently highlighted the value they placed on the support they received while undertaking the mentoring role. Collaborative, supportive relationships with all stakeholders (peers, managers, and lecturing staff) were viewed positively, as this support helped provide reassurance and guidance to mentors (Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy, 2017). However, the support received was not consistent across the evidence. To adequately fulfil their role, some mentors identified that more support was required (Bennet and McGowan, 2014; Jokelainen *et al.*, 2013; Mead, Hopkins and Wilson, 2011). Specifically, mentors claimed they would benefit from opportunities to discuss and debate the validity of assessment decisions with their peers when faced with challenging situations. This highlights how collegial support can mitigate mentors' anxiety when faced with problematic situations and provides some insight into the emotional complexity mentors may experience when making judgments on student assessments.

The emotional turmoil mentors could experience was recognised consistently (Hunt *et al.*, 2016; Bennet and McGowan, 2014; Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy, 2017). Indeed, some mentors appeared to struggle with the dual facets of their mentorship role. At times, there was an incongruence between the pastoral aspects of supporting and nurturing the students learning and development and simultaneously assessing their practice (Bennett and McGowan, 2014). This appeared to be perpetuated when students were not performing at the expected standard, as such mentors' emotional resilience was often challenged, particularly when there was a question over a student's competence. However, Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy (2017)

argue that pastoral and nurturing needs can be provided simultaneously without compromising the mentor's position of accountability.

The concept of mentor resilience was explored in depth by Hunt *et al.*, (2016). Whilst there was a general agreement that supporting an underperforming student could be emotionally taxing, it was clear mentors often internalised a failed student experience as a reflection on themselves and the mentorship support, they had provided (Hunt *et al.*, 2016). Contrastingly, Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy (2017) suggest this self-deprecating behaviour is merely a coping strategy mentors use to deal with such an emotionally challenging situation.

Consistently the mentors who had failed or supported a failing student found the experience traumatic (Brown *et al.*, 2012; Hunt *et al.*, 2016). Disappointment, confusion, discouragement, guilt and frustration were just some of the negative emotions mentors described (Hunt *et al.*, 2016). It is clear from the literature that supporting students who are failing is not an easy task, where mentors often experienced anxiety.

To assist them in their role, mentors identified that more support from Higher Education Institutions (HEI) was required, as this was not consistently present (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014). In addition, a lack of communication between the two parties was cited as a barrier to effective practice learning experiences, where changes to the assessment and curriculum were not always conveyed, thus causing confusion to those supporting learning (O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith, 2010). Broadbent *et al.*, (2014) established that there was a certain amount of ambiguity regarding how HEIs engage with the practice learning environment. They suggested that a close collaborative relationship between the educational institutions and practice areas is required to provide ongoing support to underpin students' practice learning experiences.

Although this study was undertaken within an Australian context where the models of supervision differ slightly, the findings resonate with research carried out in the United Kingdom (Bennett and McGowan, 2014).

Nursing students also recognised support for mentors appeared to be lacking (Foster, Omms and Mark-Maran, 2015). They highlighted that more guidance and feedback from liaison lecturers would be beneficial to mentors, in relation to student assessment and documentation. These findings suggest that partnership links between Higher Education Institutions and placement providers could be strengthened to ensure consistency and continuity.

Although support from faculty was described above as lacking, mentors reported that other sources of support were often available. In particular, mentors valued the role of the practice education facilitator (PEF). This support was particularly beneficial when dealing with challenging situations (Hunt, 2016; McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith, 2014). There appeared to be an implicit understanding from the PEF regarding the difficult nature of supporting a student who was underperforming; as such, they were able to provide guidance and reassurance throughout this challenging time (Hunt *et al.*, 2016). However, it is important to note that although the role of the PEF has been adopted nationally across Scotland (NES, 2020), it is not consistent throughout the United Kingdom; furthermore, the PEF role is not formally recognised by the NMC (Hunt *et al.*, 2016). This is somewhat disappointing, considering the role has been highlighted as an essential element of support for mentors (Hunt, 2016; McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith, 2014). Moreover, within the literature, there was some evidence to suggest that mentors, at times, lacked confidence when presented with a student who was failing (Brown *et al.*, 2012; Hunt *et al.*, 2016). It is also interesting to note that despite the

introduction of the Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008), it appears mentors still lack a degree of confidence when undertaking student assessments. It was clear accessing support from their peers, and the PEF helped give mentors affirmation when making these difficult decisions.

2.4.5 Theme: The Practice Learning Environment.

There was a strong focus within the current literature that examined the context of the practice learning environment. It has been well documented that the learning environment itself is an essential aspect of pre-reg nursing education (Papastavrou *et al.*, 2010). As discussed previously, the practice learning environment provides student nurses with a platform where they can bridge the theory practice gap, enabling them to translate the theoretical knowledge and apply it within the context of nursing praxis (O’Luanaigh, 2010).

There is evidence to suggest that effective practice learning experiences are inextricably linked to the quality of the practice learning environment (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014). Several inventories were identified that explored the psychosocial elements of the practice learning environment (Papastavrou *et al.*, 2014, Warne *et al.*, 2010; Papathanasiou, Tsaras and Sarafis 2014; Smedley and Morey 2009; Bisholt *et al.*, 2014; D’Sousa *et al.*, 2015). It is evident that the use of inventories not only served as a robust quality assurance tool for the HEIs but also attempted to explore the importance that students attach to their practice learning experience and the factors that influenced their satisfaction. Indeed, most practice learning experiences were regarded in a positive light as they provided students with an opportunity to enhance and develop skills (Papastavrou *et al.*, 2014; Warne *et al.*, 2010). However, students consistently identified that they preferred a more positive, supportive environment than that which they

had experienced as their ideal experiences were not met (Papathanasiou, Tsaras and Sarafis 2014; Smedley and Morey 2009). For example, students indicated that being valued within the practice learning environment was an area that could be enhanced further (Smedley and Morey, 2009). In addition, students perceived that innovative and creative teaching experiences were lacking (Papathanasiou, Tsaras and Sarafis 2014). These findings suggest that although students rated their experiences positively, there was still room for improvement.

However, what is clear from the evidence reviewed is that the positive experiences students described within the practice learning environment are not down to luck. Effective leadership and ward management were highlighted as critical elements of a supportive clinical learning environment. (D'Souza *et al.*, 2015). Ward managers who retained overall responsibility for student learning and mentorship helped shape positive learning experiences (O'Driscoll, Allan and Smith, 2010). Well-organised environments where staff worked together as a team also contributed to a more positive learning environment (Papastavrou *et al.*, 2016). This demonstrates the positive influence that good leadership has on practice learning experiences, more specifically, how the leadership style within the learning environment plays a crucial role in fostering positive learning experiences.

2.4.6 Theme: Challenges

Although practice learning experiences were generally viewed positively, not all experiences were nurturing. As mentioned previously, when exploring the theme of belongingness, students often felt ignored, belittled or even, in extreme cases, bullied (Melincavage, 2011; Minton and Birks, 2019; Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018). For many, this bullying was often covert and subtle; nevertheless, it resulted in students not feeling welcomed within the practice area

(Minton and Birks, 2019). Bullying behaviours are considered to be reflective of the culture and atmosphere of the placement area and are often attributed to poor leadership (Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018; Minton and Birks, 2019). However, there is a reluctance by students to formally raise any concerns as this may result in punitive consequences; therefore, students are left feeling powerless. These findings are perhaps not surprising and again highlight the power relationships that exist within the practice learning environment.

Students also appeared to be aware of the workload pressures mentors faced and how this could contribute to their behaviour and attitude. For example, Thomas, Jinks and Jack (2015) established that students were very cognisant of their mentor's workload, where their mentor's stress levels often resulted in rude behaviours. However, there was an acceptance of this as they recognised this was unintentional and a reflection of their mentor's workload.

Another challenge frequently identified as impacting on practice learning experiences was the lack of time to adequately support students teaching and learning (Veeremah, 2012; Teatheredge, 2010; Joklainenen *et al.*, 2013; McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith, 2014; Harrison-White and Owens, 2018). The increased complexity of healthcare delivery and the resulting increased workload was cited as a barrier to effective mentoring (McIntosh, Gidman and Smith, 2014). Mentors specifically described how competing expectations prevented them from spending adequate time with students to support their learning and development needs on placement (Veeremah, 2012; Teatheredge, 2010). Although time constraints appeared to have been a long-standing issue, what is not clear from the evidence is how this can be managed and resolved. Furthermore, these findings suggest that mentors perceive teaching and learning as an additional activity, a separate task from patient care, rather than part of their

everyday role. Undoubtedly, there are resource implications within the practice learning environment as the demand on mentors' time can have an impact on students' practice learning experience. However, the actual impact of this has been underexplored within the literature.

2.5 Discussion and Rationale for this Study.

It is evident from the literature that the discourse and interest around practice learning remains high on the agenda for pre-registration nurse education. The literature reviewed presents some clear evidence regarding pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences. However, several gaps were identified that provide a rationale for this study.

As discussed in chapter 1, the sociocultural theories of situated learning (Lave and Wenger, 1991) and communities of practice (Wenger, 1998) have been used as a lens to explore this topic, offering an insight into how student nurses learn in practice. Here the emphasis is placed on the inherently social nature of learning that is contextually situated (Morley, 2016). Legitimate peripheral participation draws attention to the importance of sponsorship from an experienced other in developing newcomers' knowledge, skills and professional identity (White, 2010). Moreover, without this sponsorship, newcomers can feel alienated, subsequently inhibiting their learning. Likewise, the literature confirms that the student-mentor relationship is a fundamental aspect of effective practice learning experiences where mentors can offer this sponsorship. The relationships formed and the support student nurses received from their mentor was deemed crucial (Helminen, Tossavainen and Turunen 2014; Warne *et al.*, 2010). However, it is clear that mentorship is a complex, multidimensional process that values individualised learning.

Similarly, Wenger's communities of practice theory is centred around collaborative learning. As discussed previously, Wenger defines communities of practice as groups of people who share a common interest or domain of knowledge and engage in collective learning through ongoing interactions (Wenger, 1998). There are three requisites identified by Wenger for a cohesive community of practice to exist, mutual engagement, joint enterprise and a shared repertoire (Morley, 2016). The evidence suggests that successfully functioning communities of practice are environments that prioritise embedding newcomers through support, acceptance and engagement, it is through this process that students feel empowered and motivated to learn (Terry *et al.*, 2020). It was clear from the literature that when students felt they had a sense of purpose within the community, their learning increased (Connor, 2019; O'Lunaigh, 2015).

The literature review also highlighted how interpersonal connections and social interactions were central to learning within the practice learning environment (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016); it was through the interactions that students learned from more experienced others on placement, gaining new insights and expanding their knowledge. In addition, Wenger's theory describes how novices can make a substantial contribution to the development of new knowledge through collaborative working practices (Wenger, 1998). In particular, the socialisation and interaction between old-timers and newcomers within a community can enhance and develop current practices empowering communities to evolve (Morley, 2016). This reciprocity and collaboration aligned with within a cohesive community of practice was also recognised within the literature review. There were some examples where mentors' professional development was enhanced through their participation in supporting students learning (Broadbent *et al.*, 2014; Rylance *et al.*, 2017).

This review also confirms that the student-mentor relationship is a fundamental aspect of an effective practice learning experience. The relationships formed, and the support student received from their mentor was deemed crucial. However, it is clear that mentorship is a complex, multidimensional process, that values individualised learning. However, the mentors' perspective is underrepresented within the evidence reviewed. As can be seen from table 4, the majority of studies (n= 24) explored practice learning from the student's perspective with less emphasis on mentors' experiences (n=11). Moreover, only three articles explored practice learning from the student's and mentor's perspectives. This study will redress this imbalance by including both mentors and students to provide a holistic understanding. In addition, acknowledging the multidimensional nature of practice learning, additional participants (PEFS and liaison lecturers and clinical managers) will be invited to participate.

One of the most important factors identified by students as impacting on their learning experience was belongingness (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008; Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016). Here the social context of the learning environment influenced how students learned on placement. Although there are numerous definitions of belongingness, they are all centred around a personal sense of acceptance and connectedness between an individual and the environment that is created through interaction with others (Vivekananda-Schmidt and Sandars, 2018). This suggests that regardless of the model of support used, students need to feel valued as part of the team, yet the means by which these feelings are engendered is lacking, something that this research aims to explore.

The evidence reviewed also offers insight into how support is perceived within the practice learning environment by both students and mentors and the presenting challenges that can be resolved by a more collaborative approach. It is clear the practice learning environment is

complex, where supporting students' learning is multifactorial, yet research exploring the practice learning environment from multiple perspectives appears to be lacking.

The literature also described some of the challenges students and mentors faced within practice learning, this included the incivility experienced (Courtney-Pratt *et al.*, 2018) and the lack of time to devote to teaching and learning was frequently cited (Veeremah, 2012; Teatheredge, 2010; Joklainenen *et al.* 2013; McIntosh, Gidmen and Smith, 2014). However, staff shortages, service redesign and unyielding clinical pressures are realities of modern clinical practice (Willis, 2015). Therefore, these experiences need to be explored in greater depth in order to understand the impact of the resource demands. This research will look to address this by exploring and interpreting the contextual factors that impact on practice learning experiences.

Much of the available literature investigating mentorship within the practice learning environment has focused on quantitative measurement tools. Whilst this method is valuable in terms of standardised data collection and generalisability of findings, these tools did not offer a deeper understanding of the meanings of these experiences and address nuances within the student-mentor relationship. Although the quantitative studies within this literature review attempted to assess students' satisfaction with their practice learning experience, they were unable to conceptualise the meaning of satisfaction or provide any additional narrative or context when exploring the student's responses.

In addition, there is a consensus that the current mentorship provision is no longer sustainable within the United Kingdom (Willis 2015; RCN 2015). Yet, as practice learning enters unprecedented times in relation to the changes in educational standards for pre-registration

nurse education, it is important to develop a better understanding of these practice learning experiences. This will ensure any good practice or important factors identified by students and those supporting their learning are not lost in the desired need for change.

Furthermore, much of the research exploring practice learning experiences has been undertaken out with the United Kingdom; this study aims to address this gap by exploring the relationships, culture, and learning located within a hospital in Scotland aligned to a Scottish university.

Finally, with the implementation of the NMC Standards for student supervision and assessment (NMC, 2018a), this study presents a timely contribution to the research into pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences. To address the current gap in the evidence, this research aims to explore the practice learning environment by providing a greater understanding of practice learning and the factors that impact upon these experiences. Providing a unique contribution to knowledge and practice, this research will aim to use an inclusive approach involving mentors, students and other participant groups (PEFs, liaison lecturers and ward managers) involved within practice learning.

2.6 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter sought to provide an overview of the historical context of practice learning, setting the scene for current practice. Using a systematised approach, the contemporary literature was reviewed exploring practice learning experiences and a critical discussion of the six key themes (belongingness, support from others, challenges, student-mentor relationship, mentoring and the practice learning environment). Following this, the justification for this research study was also presented.

Chapter 3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction to Chapter.

This chapter presents the decision trajectory of the methodological choices for this research study. Firstly, the research aim and objectives are presented. Following on, the philosophy of research is introduced where the position of this study is explored. Thereafter, a critical discussion of the theoretical frameworks guiding this study is offered. This chapter then introduces case study, as an appropriate methodology to address the research aim and objectives. The different approaches to case study design are then critically examined. Finally, this chapter concludes with a discussion on the quality and rigour of a case study design and how it will be applied to this research.

3.2 Research Aim and Objectives

The literature review undertaken in chapter two helped to identify the key themes and gaps within contemporary practice learning literature and, as such, facilitated the formation of the following research aim:

The aim of this study is to explore pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences from multiple perspectives using a case study approach. This will be achieved through the exploration of these learning experiences and the examination of the context of the learning environment. As such, the following objectives will guide this study.

Objectives:

- to develop an understanding of what influences pre-registration student nurses' practice learning experiences.
- To explore the perspectives of mentors, managers, practice education facilitators and liaison lecturers about practice learning experiences.
- To interpret the contextual factors related to pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences.

3.3 Philosophy of Research

The choice of appropriate methodology has long been recognised as a critical component of any research design; as such, the discourse surrounding how best to explore the social world has been widely debated (Stacey, 2014; Gerrish and Lacey, 2010). Although the research aim and objectives will ultimately shape the methodological choice, it is crucial that researchers understand the philosophical assumptions that underpin their research, as this understanding can inform and influence how the research is carried out (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Huff, 2009). Therefore, researchers need to be cognisant of the different research traditions to make an informed decision and provide justification and rationale for their choices (Yilmaz, 2013).

The terms paradigm, ontology, epistemology, and methodology are now briefly explained. A research paradigm is described as a belief system or theory that guides the research process; subsequently, each paradigm is characterised by their different perspectives related to ontology, epistemology and methodology (Borbasi and Jackson, 2016). It is essential that researchers recognise these differences, understanding that contrasting ontological and epistemological perspectives can lead to different research results of the same phenomenon

(Grix, 2010). Ontology is the study of being (Crotty 1998); consequently, the researchers' ontological assumptions reflect how they view the world and perceive reality (Scotland 2012). Epistemology is concerned with the nature or study of knowledge; epistemological assumptions are drawn from how this knowledge is created and understood (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011; Scotland, 2012). Finally, methodology is the research design or framework that is used to acquire knowledge. The research paradigm creates a holistic view of how knowledge is regarded, how the researcher perceives themselves in relation to this knowledge and what approaches can be used to discover the knowledge.

3.4 Position of this Research

It is clear from the literature review that learning and supporting learning in practice is complex; moreover, how these practice learning experiences were perceived varied considerably. As introduced in Chapter 1, the theoretical frameworks used in this study, situated learning and communities of practice, are underpinned by social constructivism.

From an ontological perspective, social constructivism is based on the assumption that reality is not pre-existing or independent of human perception; alternatively, social constructivism emphasises the role of social interaction and collaboration, where learning occurs through dialogue, negotiation, and joint problem-solving with others (Akpan *et al.*, 2020). Here, individuals create their own understanding and interpretations of reality through their interactions with others and the environment (Creswell and Poth, 2018).

From an epistemological perspective, social constructivism asserts that knowledge creation is a product of social interaction that is influenced by the historical, cultural, and social contexts in which it is located (Galbin, 2014). The focus is on learning as a process of meaning-making, where learners actively engage with new information and integrate it with their prior

knowledge and experiences (Bada, 2015). Therefore, knowledge is not passively transmitted but actively created by learners as they make sense of their experiences. (Moss, Grealish and Lake, 2010). Moreover, this perspective emphasises the subjective contextual nature of knowledge and challenges the notion of a single, objective truth.

3.5 Theoretical Frameworks Guiding this Study.

This next section provides an overview of the theoretical frameworks that have informed this study and their applicability to this research.

3.5.1 Situated Learning, Legitimate Peripheral Participation.

Lave and Wenger's social constructivist theory of situated learning departed from the traditional theories of cognition that positioned learning as an individual activity (Patel, 2017); alternatively, they propose that learning is a collective social process (Lave and Wenger, 1991). Moreover, they assert that communities of practice provide a meaningful context for learning. Lave and Wenger's original concept purports that all learning is situational and context-driven. Here, they argue that learning is embedded within the opportunities newcomers are afforded to participate within the community of practice, through a term they coined legitimate peripheral participation (Lave and Wenger, 1991). The trajectory of the learner through legitimate peripheral participation suggests learners initially participate on the periphery, undertaking tasks that meet the community's needs (Patel, 2017). As learners become embedded within the community, they move into a more central role and full participation. Within the context of student nurse education, exposure to learning opportunities or affordances that will allow them to participate in the nursing profession, is an essential component of the legitimate peripheral participation process (Nagle, 2021).

This approach to learning creates a deeper meaning than simply 'learning by doing' as individuals constantly shape their identity by participating in the practices of their community

(White, 2010). As such, the desire to become a more pivotal member of the community can be an effective motivator for learning.

3.5.2 Communities of Practice

Although the theory of communities of practice was initially introduced within the theory of situated learning, Wenger expanded upon this extensively within his later works. Here the concept of a community of practice (CoP) was based upon a social participative way of learning constructed from a shared interest to enhance and develop new knowledge within a situated learning environment (Wenger *et al.*, 2002). Ultimately the community of practice acts as a vehicle for the transfer of tacit knowledge through legitimate peripheral participation (Andrews *et al.*, 2008) and can be both intentional and incidental (White, 2010). However, the mastery of knowledge and skills require newcomers to participate fully within the practices of the community (McSharry and Lathlean, 2017). It is through this participation that learners begin to develop a sense of belonging and form relationships. Moreover, it is through the development of these relationships that individuals who seek to share and generate knowledge can gain experiences and learn from one another (Terry *et al.*, 2019).

As introduced in chapter two, Wegner (1998) asserts that cohesive communities of practice are bound by three interconnected dimensions: mutual engagement, joint enterprise and shared repertoire. Mutual engagement refers to the interaction and active participation of the members leading to a shared meaning (Li *et al.*, 2009). Joint enterprise relates to the common purpose, shared interest or collective goals that bring members together. Finally, shared repertoire encompasses the tools or resources created to negotiate meaning and facilitate learning (Li *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, by interacting, working collectively and sharing knowledge, communities of practice can thrive.

As half of the pre-registration nursing programme is situated within the practice field, it is reasonable to suggest that a large proportion of student learning will be within these communities of practice (Molesworth, 2017). Therefore, the quality of students' practice learning experiences will be shaped by the communities and cultures experienced within the practice learning environment (Woods *et al.*, 2016). As White (2010) explains, the practice learning environment offers student nurses the opportunity to locate their theoretical classroom learning in an authentic context, enhancing its meaning, where students can learn from existing members of the community.

Lave and Wenger (1991) argue this 'on the job' learning is centred around acceptance within the community of practice and is a process of acculturation rather than simply practising skills independently of the social context in which they are located (White, 2010). Expanding upon this, Andrew *et al.* (2008) describe how belongingness, collaboration and participation are central to the functioning and sustainability of a community of practice. Consequently, D'Souza *et al.* (2015) found that nursing students who were included as part of the team and were able to contribute to the delivery of care by fully participating within the community reported feeling more empowered and satisfied by their learning experience. However, Morley (2016) warns that those within a community of practice are not solely responsible for students' learning. Although the relationship between nursing students and their community of practice is crucial to their personal development, they suggest that both the student's ability and motivation to pursue learning opportunities are equally as important within the learning process as the community's ability to support learning.

Nevertheless, not all communities are effective learning environments. For example, the bond between group members can become intense, inhibiting the integration of newcomers as they are often excluded (Li *et al.*, 2009). Moreover, group thinking can often oppress creativity

within the community as individual ideas are not considered, which in turn restricts the growth and development of the community (Li *et al.*, 2009). However, as mentioned previously, Wenger describes several tactics that can be adopted in order to address challenges related to engagement within a community of practice (Morley, 2016). Through the use of imagination and alignment, students may be able to consider alternative possibilities and link their own practice to the wider professional context (Morley, 2016; Grealish and Ranse, 2009).

To summarise, the theoretical frameworks guiding this study resonate with the practice learning environment. Essentially, these frameworks identify with practitioners working within social and collaborative learning capacities. With a strong emphasis on learning in practice, legitimate peripheral participation and communities of practice are a useful lens, in order to explore practice learning experiences.

Therefore, the theoretical underpinning of this study is based upon the constructivist social learning theories of situated learning and communities of practice that support teaching and learning within the practice learning environment. These frameworks also support the methodology used within this study.

3.6 Methodology

As mentioned at the outset of this chapter, when choosing a methodology, researchers need to consider not only the research aims and objectives but the ontological and epistemological assumptions and the nature of the phenomenon being studied. This research did not aim to test a hypothesis or present an objective viewpoint. Alternatively, in line with a social constructivist perspective, the aim was to explore and interpret practice learning experiences to provide a deeper understanding of the complexities of this learning environment. Central to this was the acknowledgement that there would be multiple meanings and interpretations.

Within social constructivist research, the researcher seeks to uncover how social interactions and cultural contexts shape individual understandings and experiences (Cresswell and Poth, 2017). Moreover, this study was also strongly influenced by the context where these experiences were located in order to understand the historical and cultural influences that may impact practice learning experiences. Reflecting on this, it is clear the aim, objectives and philosophical viewpoint aligns with a qualitative methodology.

3.6.1 Qualitative research.

Through detailed exploration and rigorous data analysis, qualitative researchers aim to generate new knowledge and an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon from the participants' perspective (Yilmaz, 2013). Here the research methods offer rich accounts to convey an in-depth understanding of the context (Than and Than, 2015). Unlike positivist research, the aim of qualitative research is not to make generalisations; rather, the focus is on transferability. Transferability is concerned with small-scale intensive studies that provide rich, thorough, thick descriptions to fully understand the research participants and the study context (Polit and Beck, 2010). This allows the readers to extrapolate and make judgements as to how the findings can be applied or transferred to other areas of similarity (Bryman, 2012). There are several different qualitative research methodologies that could have been undertaken. Appendix 2 provides a brief summary of the methods that were considered and subsequently rejected. After much deliberation, it was decided that the most appropriate methodology for this research was case study.

3.6.2 Case Study

Although several definitions of case study exist, all agree in principle that the focus of case study research is the exploration of a complex issue in-depth in its real-life context (Yin, 2018; Yazan, 2015; Merriam, 1998; Stake, 1995). Case study is an empirical enquiry that involves an

intense, detailed analysis of a social unit (the case). The case is studied in its totality using multiple evidence sources to provide a rich, in-depth account of a complex issue (Morgan *et al.*, 2016; Priya, 2014). The use of multiple data sources (qualitative, quantitative or both) allows for the phenomenon to be explored through a variety of lenses enabling multiple aspects of the issue or problem to be understood (Baxter and Jack 2008).

Yin (2018, pp. 15) further defines case study research as a method of enquiry that;

‘investigates a contemporary phenomenon (the case) in and within its real-world context especially when the boundaries between the phenomenon and context may not be clearly evident’.

This suggests that case study research is applicable where the researcher aims to explore a real-time case that assumes the contextual setting will inform the understanding of the phenomenon (Yin, 2018). This definition was relevant to the current research study as it emphasised the ‘real life context’ and recognition that the topic under investigation (practice learning experiences) is closely linked and related to the context it is experienced in. Indeed, Yin’s definition not only highlights the importance of the context within the phenomenon but suggests that researching one without the other would provide an incomplete account.

In the broadest sense, context is defined as ‘the interrelated conditions in which something exists or occurs’ (*Merriam-Webster*, 2022). More specifically, the context of the practice learning environment has been described as multidimensional, where experiences are shaped by a range of factors, including the environment, curriculum, relationships and the culture experienced (O’Mara *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, within this research, understanding the context

of the practice learning environment means understanding both the internal and external influences on practice learning experiences.

This research will not only consider the voice of key participants within the practice learning environment, but by including multiple sources of data it will illuminate the context in which these experiences are located. There are several examples where case study research methodology has been successfully used to illuminate practice learning experiences by providing rich, in-depth accounts of the case (Cronin, 2014; Newton *et al.*, 2009; Roxborough, Conlon and Banks, 2012). Here using a case study approach, the authors were able to draw upon the complexities of the practice learning environment, further confirming case study as an appropriate methodology in which to examine this complex social phenomenon.

3.6.3 Case Study Approaches

As highlighted, case study was deemed to be the most appropriate methodology for this study. Historically case study research has been rooted within the study of social sciences and has been widely used within sociology, anthropology, psychology and education disciplines (Taylor and Thomas-Gregory 2015). Yet, despite the popularity of the methodology, its suitability within health and nursing has not always been embraced. Bryar (2000) explains that the use of case study as both a teaching strategy (using patient case studies as a learning tool) and methodological framework for undertaking research has created confusion and inhibited its use. As can be seen from the examples where case study has been successfully used (Cronin, 2014; Powell, 2013 Roxborough, Conlon and Banks, 2012; Newton *et al.*, 2009), this methodology can be a valuable tool when the aim is to explore complex situations in context. Indeed, the intensive, systematic investigation adopted within case study research enables the holistic nature of phenomena to be explored and illuminated.

There are, however, many different approaches to case study research. This next section presents the different methods used by two seminal authors, Yin (2018) and Stake (1995), that were considered for use within this study.

Yin (2018) and Stake (1995) utilise distinct yet different approaches to case study research. Both authors place emphasis on the deep exploration of an identified phenomenon and stress the importance of using multiple data sources (Baxter & Jack, 2008; Creswell and Poth, 2018). However, where these approaches differ is in the methods employed and the level of flexibility permitted throughout the research process (Hyett, Kenny, & Dickson-Swift, 2014; Yazan, 2015; Whitmore *et al.*, 2018).

Yin (2018) defines case study methodology as an empirical, stand-alone approach that employs the use of rigour in the study design. Embedded within Yin's approach to case study is a sequential, logical, systematic design (Yin, 2018, Yazan 2015, Harrison *et al.*, 2017). Researchers are encouraged to review the literature and existing theories to develop propositions that will guide the study (Whitmore *et al.*, 2018). The data collection, (that can be quantitative, qualitative or both) and subsequent strategy of data analysis can then be used to support or contest the claims made (Harrison *et al.*, 2017). Consequently, building theory and propositions into the research design not only enables the development of the research problem but helps ensure the validity of the research as the propositions help focus the researcher on the link between the data collection and research questions.

In contrast to the structured design and preparation of Yin, Stake (1995) adopts a more abstract flexible stance that uses only qualitative data. This approach allows the research design to unfold throughout the research process. Stake suggests two or three issues which help to form a conceptual structure that guides the data collection; however, as the research evolves, a more substantive focus may become apparent. Indeed, Stake (2005) purports that

the course of enquiry cannot be chartered in advance. This flexibility of approach and lesser focus on design preparation is often appealing to researchers; however, the lack of guidance could potentially lead to ambiguity and uncertainty, especially for novice researchers (Yazan, 2015).

Both authors agree that defining the case is a crucial element of case study design. According to Stake (1995), there are three forms of case study classification: intrinsic, instrumental, and collective. However, Stake (1995) suggests that these classifications often overlap, and the case study may not exclusively sit within one category or the other.

Whereas Yin (2018) defines case studies as being used to explain, describe, or explore a phenomenon within its real-life context. He further describes case studies as being single, multiple and either holistic or embedded, indicating that the type of case study selected will ultimately be determined by the overall aim of the research. A brief summary of the case study typologies is tabulated below.

Table 5 Case Study Typologies

Study Type	Brief Description
Intrinsic (Stake, 1995)	Focuses on understanding what is particular about a case. Driven by genuine interest.
Instrumental (Stake, 1995)	Helps provide insight into a particular problem or issue. Can help refine theory.
Collective (Stake, 1995)	The study of several cases to explore an area of interest across multiple contexts and settings
Explanatory (Yin, 2018)	Can be used to test theories, explain casual theories relevant when answering the 'how' and 'why' questions.
Exploratory (Yin, 2018)	Used to explore those situations in which the intervention being evaluated has no clear, single set of outcomes. Often used as a pilot study.

Descriptive (Yin, 2018)	This type of case study is used to describe an intervention or phenomenon and the real-life context in which it occurred.
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(Stake, 1995; Baxter and Jack, 2008; Yin, 2018).

A hallmark of any case study research is the use of multiple data collection methods; this not only allows the researcher to develop a holistic, comprehensive understanding of the case (Stake, 1995; Yazan, 2015) but also enhances rigour by encouraging method triangulation of the data (Carter *et al.*, 2014; Yin, 2018). As such, triangulation can produce new understandings and offer alternative perspectives through the convergence and comparisons of the research findings.

3.6.4 Selecting an Approach

As an early career researcher, the more logical nature of Yin’s approach was initially appealing.

Through examination of the research question as well as the available literature, it was decided that the use of propositions would help guide the study. The propositions would enable gaps in the literature to be addressed and offer a focus for the data collection by placing boundaries on the scope of the study (Whitemore *et al.*, 2018; Baxter and Jack, 2008). Utilising Yin’s (2018) case study design would also allow the opportunity for embedded units, therefore enabling the analysis of the different nursing designations (students, mentors, managers, PEFS and LL) within the same unit of analysis and context (practice learning experiences).

Yin’s description of case study was further confirmed as the most appropriate methodology for this research as it aligned with the three specific conditions that Yin (2018) describes. A case study is an apposite choice when the research aims to explore:

- ‘How’ or ‘Why’ questions asked about.
 - A contemporary set of events

- Over which the researcher has no control. (Yin 2018, pp. 13).

These considerations were met within this study when the research aim and objectives were developed. Firstly, the focus of this research is to understand “how” or “why”. Here the research objectives focus on using “how” as a means to interpret and explore practice learning experiences; however, it was also anticipated that this research may illuminate why differences in experiences occur. Secondly, as identified within the evidence reviewed, the context directly influences practice learning experiences. Practice learning takes place within a social setting that is inevitably influenced by many different factors. Indeed, the practice learning environment has been described as being exciting, challenging, volatile, dynamic and unpredictable (O’Mara *et al.*, 2014; Cronin 2014), where there are multiple variables functioning within any given experience. As such, the nature of practice learning experiences cannot be fully understood without consideration of the contextual factors that impact upon these experiences. Therefore, using case study methodology would provide a vehicle in which to understand this contemporary complex phenomenon in depth. Thirdly, the practice learning experiences examined within this research would not be manipulated, within this research, no interventions were proposed related to the phenomenon. Alternatively, this research is interested in understanding the phenomenon as it occurs naturally within the identified practice learning context in which the researcher will have no control.

Finally, as discussed previously, although there are alternative ways in which a case study methodology could be employed, Yin (2018) supports the use of multiple data sources; therefore, Yin’s (2018) case study approach was adopted, in order to capture the complexity of the phenomenon being studied, through the collection and analysis of qualitative data and placement information. Using this approach, it is proposed this research will build a rich holistic picture of practice learning experiences that will address the aim and objectives of the study.

While the rationale for choosing Yin has been discussed above, the tensions using this methodology also need to be acknowledged. For example, several authors have positioned Yin as taking a post-positivist position (Yazan, 2015; Harrison *et al*, 2017); yet Baxter and Jack (2008) argue Yin's case study design is firmly rooted within a constructivist perspective as it has a strong emphasis on the social construction of reality. Within his writings, Yin does not declare any philosophical position (Yazan, 2015). More specifically, Yin (2018) purports that case study research offers method fluidity as it can be used within quantitative, qualitative or mixed methods research. This pragmatic freedom and methodological openness are also supported by Luck, Jackson and Usher (2006), who suggest this methodology can be used across any paradigm as long as the researcher demonstrates methodological congruence between their philosophical positioning and research design.

Within this study, Yin's case study methodology will provide an approach to conducting an in-depth investigation of pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences. This methodology places emphasis on the holistic understanding of this complex social phenomenon through the exploration of multiple perspectives and the examination of the context in which these experiences occur. These principles align with the core tenets of social constructivism, which embrace the socially constructed nature of reality and the influence and importance of social interactions, context and subjective interpretations.

3.6.5 Ethical Considerations for this Study

Ethical awareness is a central component of any research design, regardless of the methodology. Within every study, there is a moral dilemma which aims to find a compromise between the search for truth and the protection of human rights and values of the study participants (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). Within the study of social sciences,

researchers often place less importance on the value of ethical approval (Silverman, 2011), yet Parahoo (2014) argues that regardless of the research methods protecting those involved should be a founding principle to ensure there is no exploitation of participants by the researcher.

The potential ethical problems that could have arisen from this study mainly relate to the role of the researcher as a lecturer at the University attended by the participants (pre-registration student nurses); as such, there was a risk that participants may have felt obliged to participate in the study. To overcome this, only pre-registration nursing students within year three of the program were invited to participate; as a lecturer in the nursing programme, the researcher had no contact with part 3 students in terms of teaching, learning and assessment. It was also emphasised to all participants within the consenting process that any participation was voluntary and would have no bearing (positive or negative) on any future assessments.

In addition, the literature highlighted that many students found their practice learning experiences to be stressful and emotional (Gibbons *et al.*, 2011); therefore, there was the potential for discussions and reflections on their experiences to become emotive. As such, information regarding support services (including student counselling and NHS staff care) was offered to ensure participants were supported if required.

3.6.7 Ensuring Quality and Rigour

Historically case study has been described as lacking precision and often viewed as flawed (Simmons, 2009; Cronin, 2014). However, Yin (2018) purports that four tests or tactics can be employed within case study research (or indeed any empirical social research), in order to establish the quality. These are construct validity, internal validity, external validity and reliability. Table 6 illustrates how each of the tactics can be achieved within case study research.

Whilst these tactics lean towards a positivist tradition, they provide a structure and plan for the research process that demonstrates dependability, transferability and credibility (Yin, 2018). The aim here was to strike a balance that respected the unique characteristics of the chosen case study methodology while upholding the quality and rigour of the research process. Central to this was the data collection, Yin (2018) suggests that validity and reliability can be strengthened by

- the use of multiple evidence sources,
- the creation of a case study database
- maintaining a clear chain of evidence.

As discussed earlier, the use of multiple evidence sources can corroborate the findings across different data sources or methods strengthening the trustworthiness of the research (Carter *et al.*, 2014). The development of a case study database, provides an efficient and organised way to manage, analyse, and synthesise the data (Yin, 2018; Kaman and Othman, 2016). Finally, by maintaining a clear chain of evidence where there is a clear decision-making trajectory and transparency throughout, helps maintain the focus of the research and enhances the rigour of the research process (Yazan, 2015; Cronin, 2014).

Table 6 Rigour and Case Study Research

Test	Case study tactic
Construct validity Correct operation measure for concepts being studied.	Using multiple sources of evidence Have key informants review draft CS report.
Internal Validity Seeking to establish whereby certain conditions lead to others.	Do pattern matching. Do explanation building. Address rival explanations Use logic models.
External validity Whether/how findings can be generalised.	Use theory in single cases.
Reliability Procedures can be repeated with same results.	Use case study protocol. Develop a case study database. Maintain a chain of evidence.

(Yin 2018, pp. 43, 2018).

3.6.8 Study Propositions

As discussed earlier in this chapter, in conjunction with the aims and objectives of this research, there were several propositions that guided this study. In case studies, propositions help the researcher place limits on the boundaries and scope of the study, therefore, increasing the viability of the research project (Whitemore *et al.*, 2018; Baxter and Jack, 2008). Moreover, propositions help guide the study by informing the analysis process and ensuring the topic under study is thoroughly investigated (Whitemore *et al.*, 2018).

Existing theories, personal and professional experience, and literature can all be drawn upon in the development of propositions (Yin, 2018). Following the literature review and reflecting on previous experience, four propositions were developed to help guide this study.

- The practice learning environment is a complex social environment.
- The relationships formed and how these are perceived impact on practice learning experiences.
- The context of the practice learning environment influences pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences.
- How the practice learning experiences are perceived will be similar to those described within the literature.

3.7 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter presented an analysis and critique of case study as the chosen methodology for this research. Firstly, the position of this study was explored. Following on the theoretical frameworks guiding this study were discussed and the congruence of these frameworks with the chosen methodology. The underpinning principles of case study were then presented including the different approaches to case study research that were considered. Yin's approach to case study was then offered as the chosen design, acknowledging both the strengths and limitations of this design and how quality and rigour can be applied. This next chapter draws upon the principles of case study research and introduces the design and methods used to undertake the research.

Chapter 4 Methods

4.1 Introduction to Chapter.

This chapter presents an overview of the methods used in this study. Firstly, it presents the design of the study, including the boundaries and setting for this study. The ethical considerations and the ethical approval process that was undertaken prior to collecting data are then presented. Next, the sampling strategy and data collection methods are discussed; this section also includes a brief summary of the participants. A description of the analysis process as described by Yin (2016) is presented, concluding with the reflexive strategy that underpinned the research.

4.2 Design of this Study.

This study was an exploratory, embedded case study design. As discussed in the previous chapter, case study is commonly used when it is difficult to control all the variables that are of interest within the research (Yin, 2018). It was considered the most appropriate method to explore the practice learning experiences as it would enable an in-depth investigation of the phenomenon and context. As such, a range of interpretive data collection methods, including semi-structured interviews and focus groups, were utilised to understand the social processes in detail and the contextual factors that impact upon practice learning experiences, providing an invaluable and deep understanding.

However, it was also decided that placement information would be collated. This information, although purely descriptive, could further help describe the context of the case. It was anticipated that this information would help build a richer picture of the case and describe the setting for this study.

4.2.1. Exploratory Design.

This case would be described by Yin (2018) as an exploratory case study due to the lack of prior research as identified within the literature review (RCN, 2015). An exploratory case study is particularly relevant when the aim is to gain a deeper understanding of a phenomenon or complex issue (Scholz and Tietje, 2002). Moreover, this research is seeking to explore practice learning experiences from multiple key stakeholder perspectives as opposed to comparing existing theory (explanatory case study) or elaborating on current theory through description (descriptive case study).

4.2.2 Embedded Units

Yinian design allows for the possibility of exploring embedded units within a single case (Yin, 2018; Whitmore *et al.*, 2017; Yazan, 2015). Rather than a single unit of analysis, an embedded case study design focuses on the multiplicity of evidence to explore salient aspects of the case (Scholz and Tietje, 2002). In the context of this research, it allows the synthesis of collective accounts of the same case; these sub-units provide an opportunity to analyse different nursing designations such as student nurses, mentors, ward managers, practice education facilitators (PEFs) and, liaison lecturers, experiences of practice learning.

4.2.3 Boundaries of the Case

Perhaps one of the most crucial elements of case study is identifying the case and its boundaries; the identification of specific parameters is essential to establish what does, and does not constitute the case, thus ensuring the research remains focused and does not become too broad (Baxter and Jack 2008; Harrison *et al.*, 2017; Yin, 2018). Several suggestions exist as to how the case can be bound, for example, time and place, time and activity and by definition and context (Stake 1995; Miles and Huberman 1994; Yin 2018). The case within this

study is described as pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences; it can be bound further by study setting and time as described below.

4.2.4 Study Setting

The setting for this study is a local district general hospital in the west of Scotland. The hospital comprises of a variety of in-patient and out-patient settings that facilitate practice placement experiences for the University of the West of Scotland pre-registration nursing programme. This setting provides a physical location for the context of this case. The case study is also described as a single case. A single case study is an appropriate choice when the case can be viewed as a common or typical case; as such, the objective is to capture the conditions of an everyday situation (Yin, 2018). The commonality was particularly relevant to this case as all pre-registration nursing programmes within the United Kingdom offer practice placement experiences hence the typicality of the case and the setting selected.

4.2.5 Time Boundaries

The time boundaries placed within this study were any practice placement experiences during the three previous years of the nursing programme 2016 - 2019. The timeframe would allow for sufficient experiences to be explored yet ensure the events reflected on were contemporary.

4.3 Ethical Considerations for this Study

Ethical awareness is a central component of any research design, regardless of the methodology. Within every study, there is a moral dilemma which aims to find a compromise between the search for truth and the protection of human rights and values of the study participants (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). Within the study of social sciences,

researchers often place less importance on the value of ethical approval (Silverman, 2011), yet Parahoo (2014) argues that regardless of the research methods protecting those involved should be a founding principle to ensure there is no exploitation of participants by the researcher.

The potential ethical problems that could have arisen from this study mainly relate to the role of the researcher as a lecturer at the University attended by the participants (pre-registration student nurses); as such, there was a risk that participants may have felt obliged to participate in the study. To overcome this, only pre-registration nursing students within year three of the program were invited to participate; as a lecturer in the nursing programme, I had no contact with part 3 students in terms of teaching, learning and assessment. It was also emphasised to all participants within the consenting process that any participation was voluntary and would have no bearing (positive or negative) on any future assessments.

The review of the literature highlighted that many students found their practice learning experiences to be stressful and emotional (Gibbons *et al.*, 2011); therefore, there was the potential for discussions and reflections on their experiences to become emotive. As such, information regarding support services (including student counselling and NHS staff care) was offered to ensure participants were supported if required.

4.3.1 Ethical Approval

For this research, ethical approval was obtained by the UWS ethics committee through the completion of an ethics application (Appendix 3). As the study did not involve patients, ethical application through the NHS board was not required. However, as local NHS board employees were involved in the study, contact was made with the NHS research department where the study was undertaken to gain formal approval. In an effort to ensure transparency, practice

education leads were also informed of the study. Finally, the programme leader and Head of the Division were also made aware of the study.

4.3.2 Consent

Informed consent is the foundation of ethical practice and allows subjects to have control over their decision to participate or not (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). To ensure participants were able to make an informed decision regarding consent, an information leaflet was developed to provide an overview of the study (Appendix 4). This information was given to the participants at least one week before the data was collected to ensure they had enough time to digest the information and raise any further questions. For the student and mentor participants, invitation to participate was initiated through a third party to minimise any bias. Prior to the data collection, consent forms were completed and retained, and a copy was also given to the participants.

4.3.3 Confidentiality and Anonymity

Reassurance was given to all participants that confidentiality would be maintained throughout the study and anonymity protected for all written and published materials.

When presenting detailed, rich accounts within qualitative research, maintaining confidentiality can present unique challenges; although personal identifiable information can be removed, contextual information may still lead to participants being identifiable via deductive disclosure (Kaiser, 2009; Tsai *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, within this study, participants were assured that careful consideration would be given to the verbatim quotes that were used, where any identifiable contextual data would be redacted. Here the aim was to balance the rich accounts provided by the participants whilst simultaneously protecting their identity.

Pseudonyms were used to identify the participants within the thesis, and all ward areas were anonymised. However, participants were also reminded that all information disclosed should be in accordance with the relevant codes of professional conduct; they were made aware that

if any information was disclosed to the researcher that related to malpractice, the researcher would have a moral and ethical obligation to act upon this in line with the UWS code of ethics.

4.4 Purposive Sample Strategy

The aim of purposive sampling is to include data sources that are information-rich (Yin, 2016). As discussed in the previous chapter, this study aimed to explore a diverse range of perspectives; therefore, students, mentors, managers, PEFs and liaison lecturers were invited to participate. The eligibility criteria within this study were driven primarily by the boundaries of the case and the ethical considerations of the study. For example, as the case was exploring practice learning experiences within a local district general hospital, only students who had previous placement experiences within this area were invited to participate. Moreover, the mentors, manager and PEFs and liaison lecturers were all affiliated with this area. As mentioned above, only third-year students were included, the primary reason being the researcher did not teach or mark in part three of the programme, therefore, minimising any possible risks of bias or perceived coercion. A breakdown of the participant numbers and data collection can be found in table 7.

Participants	Number included	Data collection method
Third-year pre-registration nursing students.	15	Focus groups
Mentors	9	Semi-structured interview
Liaison lecturer	3	Semi-structured interview
Practice education facilitator	2	Semi-structured interview
Ward Manager	1	Semi-structured interview

(Table 7 Participant numbers and data collection methods)

4.5 Recruitment

All participants were invited to attend via email, where information regarding the study was shared (Appendix 6). A follow-up email was sent to all participants who had expressed an interest in participating with dates and times of the planned interview and focus group sessions (Appendix 7 and 8). This email also included the participant information sheet and consent forms.

4.5.1 Students

Year three lecturers initially introduced the study to the students; this was to minimise any perceived coercion by the researcher. The lecturers were given a brief overview of the study and asked to use the participant information sheet as a guide for the information shared. At this point, as detailed within the participant information sheet, students were assured that any participation was voluntary. A follow-up email was then sent to all students who had expressed an interest via their student email account (Appendix 8). This contained the participant information sheet and consent forms. In addition, as the students were attending campus for their theory component, face to face information sessions were organised by the researcher where students could come and ask questions and find out more about the study.

4.5.2 Mentors and Managers

An email containing information about the study was sent to all eligible mentors and managers via the local practice education team, as they had access to the mentor database and individual email information. Participants were asked to forward their note of interest to the researcher.

4.5.3 Practice Education Facilitators and Liaison Lectures

As mentioned above, all eligible participants were formally invited via email. Email details were easily accessible via the practice education networks. Due to the relatively small number of eligible practice education facilitators and liaison lecturers, the researcher contacted them directly; however, all were assured that any participation was voluntary.

4.6 Data Collection Methods Used.

The following section provides a brief summary of each of the methods (focus groups, semi-structured interviews and demographic data) and how they were used within this study.

4.6.1 Overview Semi-structured Interviews

Yin (2018) describes case study interviews as one of the most crucial sources of evidence as they enable participants to describe, explain and reflect on experiences; moreover, this reflection provides rich data and insights into a particular situation (McNiff and Whitehead 2011). Semi-structured interviews allow for open-ended questions enabling the participants to express their personal, in-depth responses (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013; Braun and Clark, 2013). Furthermore, this technique allows for a degree of flexibility, where the researcher can probe for further information, depending on non-verbal clues or if interesting lines of discussion emerge. However, as Kelly (2010) explains, there is a fine line between probing for clarification and guiding the interview and subsequently introducing bias. One of the main benefits of semi-structured interviews, however, is the interaction between the interviewer and interviewee (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013).

4.6.2 The Interview

(Participants - mentors, manager, practice education facilitators and liaison lecturers)

Semi-structured interviews were selected for these participant groups for practical reasons, acknowledging the logistic difficulty of trying to get all participants available at a suitable time. However, the interviews proved to be a rich source of data. An interview schedule was developed to guide the process, where open-ended questions guided the discussions. Interview one was considered the pilot for this study to ascertain if the interview guide was effective in gathering enough data on the topic of study. This was the shortest interview at just

25 minutes; on reflection, this appeared to be related to researcher's nerves rather than a lack of data. Appendix 10 is an excerpt from the reflective journal that captures the anxiety experienced undertaking this first interview. As no changes were made to the interview schedule, the data from this interview was used in the analysis.

The location for the interviews was chosen after consultation with the participants; this varied depending on the participants' work location, for example, the liaison lecturer interviews were carried out on campus, whereas the mentor, PEF and manager interviews were carried out at the hospital site, this ensured that they did not incur any additional travel time.

4.6.3 Overview of Focus Groups

Focus groups were the data collection source for the student participants. Focus groups are a method of collecting data from multiple participants simultaneously, described as a form of group interview, that empowers participants to interact and explore a specific topic, thus generating a collective rather than individual perspective (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2011). The use of focus groups offers numerous advantages for data collection as they can elicit a form of inquiry and communication that mimics group discussions and encourages social interaction with each other allowing the perspective of the participants to emerge (Savin-Baden and Major, 2012).

The structure of any focus group is key to its success; pertinent to this is the role of facilitator (Braun and Clarke, 2013). It is the responsibility of those facilitating the focus group not to make judgements, rather, they should empower the participants to contribute and should encourage commentary, whether positive or negative in nature (Kruger 2014). Often the facilitator's role is organic, interjecting when required to clarify or follow up on any points (Braun and Clarke, 2013).

Being mindful that not all students may feel comfortable sharing their experiences within a group, during the recruitment process, students were offered the choice of attending a focus group or one-to-one interview. However, all interested participants opted to attend a focus group. The focus groups were carried out on different sites (one arranged at the hospital and one at the university campus). As travel expenses were not being reimbursed, this offered a degree of flexibility for the students.

4.7.4 Management of Data

Both the focus groups and interviews were digitally recorded. As Braun and Clark (2013) explain, qualitative researchers are interested in the specifics of participants' responses when discussing their individual experiences; therefore, an accurate record is required. However, supplementary field notes were also taken to ensure any interesting points for follow-up were captured at the time.

A large amount of data was retrieved from the two focus groups (161 minutes) and fifteen interviews (572 minutes). The shortest interview was 25 minutes with the longest interview being 58 minutes. To become more familiar with the data and capture the essence of the conversations, audio recordings were transcribed verbatim. This provided a detailed account that included repetitions, pauses etc. Whilst the transcription was very time-consuming, it allowed a deep level of immersion. This level of immersion is perceived as essential, not only helping the researcher become familiar with the data but also aiding the development of meaningful insights (Patton 2014).

4.7.5 Placement Information

Multiple data sources are a key characteristic of case study research, where data from each of the sources are converged, providing a holistic understanding of the case (Baxter and Jack, 2008; Whitmore *et al.*, 2018). Aligning with an interpretivist/constructivist perspective, semi-

structured interviews and focus groups were selected as the primary source of data. However, unlike other qualitative approaches, case study research offers the flexibility of integrating additional information, in order to holistically understand the phenomena (Baxter and Jack, 2008).

In this study, placement information from pre-existing data in each practice learning area was also collated to provide the setting for this study and offer a rich understanding of practice learning experiences. At the time this research study was undertaken, all areas supporting pre-registration nursing students learning were required to maintain a mentor database (NMC, 2008). Therefore, information regarding the number of mentors and number of students each area could support was collated for analysis. It was anticipated that this information would not only help build a more holistic picture of the practice learning environment but may substantiate or further contextualise the findings from the qualitative data.

4.8 Analysis

Based on the principle of data convergence, the data analysis and interpretation occurred simultaneously. Yin's (2016) framework of qualitative analysis was used to guide the analysis process. Here the analysis is an iterative process and does not follow a linear trajectory (see diagram 2). Alternatively, it focuses on the inductive, emerging, and interpretive inquiry of the research and, as such is aligned to the underpinning principles of constructivist enquiry. How each of the five phases within this framework were applied within this study is described below and summarised in diagram 2. In addition, a worked example of the data analysis can be found in Appendix 11.

4.8.1 Compiling

In preparation for analysis, Yin (2016; 2018) suggests creating a database as an effective way of collating and organising the data. For this study NVivo™ version 12 (QRS, 2020) was where

transcripts of all interviews and focus groups were uploaded along with any notes and memos. Throughout the analytical process, this served as a repository to support the organisation, management and manipulation of the data. Furthermore, as Houghton *et al.* (2017) suggest, the use of software programmes such as NVivo™ can provide transparency and enhance the rigour and trustworthiness of the research process through the provision of an audit trail.

4.8.2 Disassembling

This second phase of analysis calls for the researcher to break down the data into fragmented sections; this process is commonly repeated several times (Yin, 2016). Within this study, data coding was carried out systematically, analysing each transcript fully. The aim was to fragment the data; at this stage, the codes appeared very descriptive. This line-by-line analysis produced an abundance of initial codes, however on review, many of them were similar or shared similar meanings and were grouped together. These initial ideas and concepts were coded using NVivo™ to identify themes. The table below provides an example of the initial coding.

Table 8 Initial coding.

Initial Codes	Excerpt
Increased confidence Supportive Confidence Individual needs Empowering Enthusiasm Nurturing	I had the other mentor and I am not kidding she was brilliant, she taught me the things I didn't feel confident in, cause I was going onto my management placement – having a good mentor is paramount, if you have a good mentor that's willing to support you, she could see that I wasn't confident with drips and things and she was like 'right come on' and these are the things you learn from, she took me under her wing, and we got on great, it was a fab placement.

Support Guidance Learning opportunities Frustration Hindered Regressing Lack of autonomy	See I found that my last placement, my mentor watched me do everything and she taught me an awful lot.....she did teach me a lot, whereas now I'm not allowed to do what she showed me and I just don't get it. So kinda I do feel like I've went backwards instead of forwards as my mentor won't let me do anything.
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4.8.3 Reassembling

This stage requires the researcher to search for patterns across the data through a process of 'playing with the data' (Yin, 2016, pp. 204). Initial codes were categorised and tabulated, as this study involved embedded units, patterns were searched across the entire data set. Again, NVivo™ was used to generate visual charts and images (see Appendix 12). This was particularly useful when looking for similarities and differences within the data set. The initial codes were then aligned with more focused codes. It was at this point that tentative categories began to emerge.

This stage of the data analysis process involved triangulation, where the research aim and objectives were interrogated from multiple perspectives. In the context of research, triangulation can strengthen the credibility of the findings as it determines if data from multiple sources converge (Smith, 2018; Yin, 2016). Moreover, as Smith (2018) reiterates, data triangulation is a key component of case study design.

4.8.4 Interpretation

Interpretation involves giving meaning to the emergent themes where the researcher critically interprets the findings bringing the analysis together (Yin, 2016). The aim at this stage was to look for relationships between the categories and emerging themes. In this study, each of the themes were questioned and critically discussed in relation to the literature looking for connections. Interpretation drew upon the theoretical frameworks that underpinned the

study and explored rival explanations to create insightful interrelations, this is presented in chapter 6 of this thesis.

4.8.5 Concluding

Finally, the concluding phase brings together conclusions from the study's findings and interpretations and captures the significance of the research (Yin, 2016). This includes answering the research questions and making recommendations for future practice. In this study, the conclusions and recommendations are presented in chapter 7.

Diagram 2 Data analysis process (adapted from Yin, 2016 and Roberts, 2018).

4.9 Rigour of the research process

As discussed in chapter three, case study historically has been described as flawed due to the lack of rigour (Simmons, 2009; Cronin, 2014). Consequently, Yin suggests four tests that researchers should employ to ensure the quality and rigour of their research. How each of the four tactics were used within this research is detailed in table 9 below.

Table 9 Quality and Rigour in This Study

Test	How it is addressed within this study.
Construct validity	Multiple sources of evidence used – Interviews and focus groups with various students and staff groups. Placement information setting the scene (mentor/student numbers etc). Use member checking to review transcripts.
Internal Validity	Data analysis – findings explored within the context of existing literature. Rival explanations explored within the discussion.
External validity	Research design Constructivist/interpretivist - applicable theoretic frameworks - Lave and Wenger (1991), Wegner (1998). Common case - findings may be transferable.
Reliability	Protocol developed to guide the research study. Reflective journal used to record decision trajectory (trajectory presented in the thesis). Database developed with all evidence. Analysis reported verbatim from transcripts.

(Yin 2018, pp. 43, 2018).

Moreover, Yin suggests validity and reliability can be strengthened by the use of multiple evidence sources, the creation of a case study database and maintaining a clear chain of evidence (Yin, 2018). In this study, as described above, multiple data sources were used to provide a rich, thick understanding of practice learning experiences. A case study database was creating using NVivo™ version 12 (QRS, 2020). This served as a repository for all information

and was used to store, organise and analyse all data. Finally, this thesis presents the chain of evidence, decision-making trajectory and transparency of the research process.

4.10 Presentation of the Data

The placement information collected provides the setting for this study and will be initially presented in a table format to illustrate the differences and similarities across the practice learning environments explored. Any links to the themes will then be explored within the analysis and discussion chapters.

In contrast, the themes identified will be presented using direct quotes. Although using quotations within qualitative research is now standard practice, as Yin (2016) purports, the use of quotations allows the researcher to bring the context to life and underpins the interpretation and explanations provided. However, the quotes used need to be carefully selected; Lingardd (2019) describes how they should be illustrative, succinct and representative of the data. In recognition of this, the quotes used within this thesis follow these three principles and are taken verbatim from the participants' narratives to ensure authenticity.

4.11 Reflexivity

The researcher's positionality, which must be acknowledged, is a critical component of any research study. Positionality and reflexivity are inextricably linked; however, reflexivity is the process by which the researcher ensures their positionality is not detrimental to the research study (Savin- Badin Major, 2012). As such, reflexivity enables the researcher to consider their position and related influence, by supporting them to understand how they have constructed, or imposed meanings, throughout the research process (Bolton and Delderfield, 2018). Moreover, reflexivity focuses on understanding the complexity of their role as the researcher in relation to others through the questioning of attitudes, values and assumptions. It is

important that the researcher recognises they are part of the social world being explored, and therefore critical self-examination is required. Although several definitions of reflexivity exist, Olmos-Vega *et al.* (2022) define it as follows;

'A set of continuous, collaborative, and multifaceted practices through which researchers self-consciously critique, appraise and evaluate how their subjectivity and context influence the research processes' (pp. 4)

This definition emphasises the continual nature of reflexivity. Likewise, within this study, the process of reflexivity was ongoing and extended across the entire research process. There were several tactics employed to help support the reflexive process. Firstly, a reflective research journal(s) was maintained throughout. This allowed ideas, perspectives and assumptions to be considered. In particular, this was critical during the analysis. Recognising that I had extensive practice learning experience, the use of the reflective journal helped me explore my own preconceptions and position as the researcher. These notes were continually revisited throughout the analysis to ensure that it was the participants' narratives that formed the basis of this new knowledge. Secondly, there was a clear trajectory of the decisions made throughout the study. This thesis presents the decision train, providing the justification and rationale, to maintain transparency and enhance the validity of the research process. Thirdly, regular supervision meetings with the supervisory team facilitated discussions that supported the reflexive process; here, ideas and concepts were challenged and explored.

Walsh (2003) suggests there are four types of reflexivity that should be employed within any study. Table 10 describes these stages and provides examples of how they were applied to this research study.

Table 10 Application of reflexivity

Type of reflexivity	How it was applied.
Personal Reflexivity	<p>This research was conducted as part of my professional doctorate and was an area of interest that I had a great deal of knowledge of and experience working within. Being insider research, many of my ideas came from my previous experiences. Whilst I acknowledge the importance of supporting students in practice, after undertaking the literature review, I was surprised at the unbalanced view of mentors as such decided to look at these experiences holistically from the student and mentor perspectives. However, through conversations with my supervisors, they encouraged me to look at the construction of a shared understanding as to how PLE were perceived from multiple perspectives. As such, this study was shaped to look beyond just the student and mentor relationship.</p> <p>My personal reflexivity involved reflecting on my assumptions around how I interacted within the PLE as a liaison lecturer and how I supported students in practice, as my beliefs, assumptions, epistemological stance, cultural and social background are variables that may well affect the research.</p>
Methodological reflexivity	<p>How are methodological decisions made, and what is the impact of these decisions?</p> <p>This study is located within an interpretivist/constructivist paradigm, informed by sociocultural learning theory that guided the use of case study methodology – however, this was not the only method that could have been used. Being methodological reflexive allowed other methods to be considered justifying the final choice (see Appendix 2). Reflexivity within Yin's case study methodology is integral in maintaining the rigour and validity. In this study, it was important to be continually reflexive when making decisions to ensure the data collection, analysis and interpretation were congruent with Yin's case study methodology. For example, I had to continually</p>

	<p>ensure I was following the process that guided Yin's methodology yet staying true to the constructivist nature of the research. By promoting self-awareness, transparency, and accountability, I was able to consider my own biases and subjectivity throughout. This thesis presents the trajectory of decisions made through the research process, offering justification and rationale for the decisions made and enhancing transparency.</p>
Interpersonal Reflexivity	<p>It was important that I considered the existing relationship I had with participants and any power relations that existed. As a lecturer and liaison lecturer, I was known to most of the participants and had to consider how the power differentials may affect the research process. I tried to mitigate some of the challenges through the sampling process. For example, as I did not teach or mark into any year three modules, therefore, only year three students were invited to participate. In relation to the other sample groups, rather than targeting individuals I knew well (who could have felt pressured to participate), an open email was sent asking them to express an interest.</p>
Contextual reflexivity	<p>Considering how the context influenced the research and those involved.</p> <p>Both my previous experience and the literature affirmed that the practice learning environment is a dynamic, socially complex, intense learning environment. Therefore, it was essential to reflect on how the interactions between students and others in the learning environment are shaped by the context in which they occur. This acknowledged how these interactions are unique and may not be the same as other learning environments.</p>

(Adapted from Olmos-Vega *et al.* 2022).

4.12 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter presented a description of the methods used within this research. Firstly, provided an overview of the study design. Following on it presented the ethical considerations and the ethical approval process that was undertaken prior to collecting data. The sampling strategy was then explored. This was followed by an exploration of the data collection methods used; semi-structured interviews, focus groups and the placement information that was collated, providing the setting for this study. Thereafter, an overview of Yin's (2016) data analysis process was presented. This chapter concluded with a brief discussion on reflexivity and the reflexive strategies that were employed throughout the research process. The next chapter will present the findings from this research.

Chapter 5 Findings.

5.1 Introduction to Chapter

This chapter commences with a brief outline detailing the participant information, number of interviews and focus groups that were undertaken. The placement information is then presented providing the setting for the study; each of the clinical areas are tabulated to identify the number of mentors and sign-off mentors within each area, along with the number of students each area supports. Finally, this chapter presents the two themes and seven subthemes that were identified following the data analysis. Verbatim quotes are used within this section to illustrate the findings.

5.2 Participant Information.

In total, 15 pre-registration nursing students participated in the study over two focus groups. One student was male the rest were female. To meet the eligibility criteria, all students had at least one placement within the hospital that served as the area of data collection. However, all of the students had multiple practice learning experiences within this environment, that they were able to reflect on.

A total of 15 semi-structured interviews were undertaken; this included nine mentors, three liaison lecturers, two practice education facilitators and one ward manager. From the mentors' perspective, the degree of experience mentoring varied considerably. This ranged from approximately 30 years to just under three years. Only one mentor (Ailsa) classed herself as a new mentor with less than three years of experience, however, during this time, she had supported and assessed numerous students within practice as a mentor. The remainder of the

mentors all had more than five years of experience as a mentor and had supported multiple students.

5.3 Setting for this Study (Placement Information)

The following table (table 11) provides an overview of the mentor and student numbers within the district general hospital that formed the boundaries of this case and the setting of the study.

Table 11 Placement Information

Placement area	Number of mentors	Number of sign-off mentors	Service level agreement	Year 1 students	Year 2 students	Year 3 students	Sign-off placement students
1	11	8	6	√	√	√	√
2	10	5	3	√	√	√	√
3	8	4	5	√	√	√	√
4	8	2	5	√	√	√	√
5	9	4	4	√	√	√	√
6/7	28	20	5	√	√	√	√
8	6	2	3	√	√	√	√
9	4	5	6	√	√	√	√
10	1	5	2	√	√	X	X
11	6	3	7	√	√	√	√
12	6	2	6	√	√	√	√
13	6	6	5	√	√	√	√

14	3	11	2	√	√	√	√
15	7	3	6	√	√	√	√
16	2	7	4	√	√	√	√
17	1	5	2	X	X	√	√
18	2	1	2	√	√	√	X
Specialist area 1	13	11	2	X	√	√	√
Specialist area 2	3	6	2	√	√	√	√
Specialist area 3	6	6	4	X	√	X	X
Specialist area 4	2	14	4	X	√	√	√

The above table details the number of mentors and sign-off mentors allocated within each area. Each of the placement areas have been anonymised to maintain confidentiality. Specialist areas were highlighted due to the different skill mix and patient demographic within these areas. Ward 6/7 is a combined unit hence the higher mentor/sign-off mentor numbers. The service level agreement represents the number of students each area agreed to support at any point in time. In addition, the table indicates what level of student the PLE can support in relation to first, second and third-year students and final 'sign off' placement students, as the final placement experience requires that students are supported by a mentor who has sign-off status (NMC, 2008).

What is clear from the table above is the lack of consistency across the mentor/sign-off mentor numbers and the number of students each area can support. For example, the maximum number of students supported at the time of this study was 6 (areas 1,9,12 and 15). Yet, within each of these areas, the number of mentors and/or sign-off mentors appears to differ dramatically, ranging from 8 to 19. Moreover, although area 6/7 is a combined unit and has a higher number of mentors and sign-off mentors, this does not appear to have positively impacted on the number of students they are able to support. Ultimately, the capacity of available learning experiences is influenced by the number of placement areas and the number of staff able to support and assess students. However, as can be seen from table 11, there is an inconsistent approach within individual areas regarding how many student nurses they are able to support in relation to the number of available mentors.

The information also describes the level of student (year one, two or three) supported within each area and again highlights a variation. At the time of data collection, not every area supports every level of student. In particular, there were several areas that did not offer placements to year one students or year three students. Historically, specialist placement areas have been reluctant to offer learning experiences for all nursing students as they were considered overwhelming and daunting (Conneely and Hunter, 2012). However, the evidence suggests these areas can offer innovative, unique learning experiences that have been shown to improve communication and decision-making within a high acuity learning environment (Williams and Palmer, 2014). In addition, this underutilisation of available placement areas for all students may negatively impact the student experience as it limits the scope for peer teaching, learning, and support.

5.4 Findings of Focus Groups and Interviews

After analysing the data, two themes and seven subthemes were identified. This next section describes and interprets each of these in detail using direct quotes to illuminate and emphasise the participants' perspectives.

5.4.1 Theme One - Teamwork Makes the Dream Work.

Whilst this phrase is commonly associated with successful sporting team analogies, it was clear from the data that the richest experiences were often attributed to the contributions made by the whole team. The focus of this theme is centred around aspects of mutual support, collaboration and encouragement, which all participants recognised as vitally important. This notion of teamwork by no means belittles the student-mentor relationship; indeed, this relationship was considered vital. In the context of this study, however, 'teamwork makes the dream work' suggests that practice learning experiences are shaped by a wide range of relationships and social interactions. Each of the four subthemes associated with teamwork will now be presented.

Diagram 3

5.4.2 Mentoring Relationships

In the context of practice learning experiences, without a doubt, the most significant theme that emerged from all participants was the relationships that formed between the student and mentor. The data supports the notion that an effective student-mentor relationship is multidimensional; factors such as personal characteristics, time spent together and how this relationship is perceived were explored by the participants.

Flourishing or Floundering

For all participants, there was an acknowledgement that this relationship influenced the practice learning experience. There were a number of examples where the development of this relationship, whether positive or negative, appeared to be indicative of how successful the placement experience was perceived. This is articulated in the abstracts below.

'you can a see difference in your learning, in your... Even your enthusiasm, everything is completely different if you don't... If your mentor's no interested... You need to build a good relationship with your mentor or your placement's just no the same'

(Gaynor, Student)

'I had the other mentor and I am not kidding she was brilliant, she taught me the things I didn't feel confident in, cause I was going onto my management placement – having a good mentor is paramount, if you have a good mentor that's willing to support you, she could see that I wasn't confident with drips and things and she was like 'right come on' and these are the things you learn from, she took me under her wing, and we got on great, it was a fab placement'

(Ella student)

There was also an acknowledgement of the impact that this relationship could have on the development of students' confidence.

'See when I go and visit a student on placement, and they are thriving you can tell it all comes back to the relationship they have with their mentor. See if their mentor is supportive and encouraging it's really obvious, they just have like...they just seem to have so much more confidence'.

(Scott, liaison lecturer)

'We are lucky here, the mentors are really good and really keen to support the student, this isn't an easy placement the patients are really sick and it can be daunting for students at first so they need a good mentor at their back that can really, you know really support them'

(Allison, ward manager)

Different aspects in the development of an effective relationship also emerged as some mentors appeared to take on a more protective role.

'but my mentor because she knew all this was going on the ward, she specifically made sure that I was only on shift when she was on duty, I went for lunch with her, I mean I was getting to do loads of stuff, but cause she didn't want me getting caught up in the ward politics, she made sure, that if I was left and she was away she made sure I was left with somebody she could trust'

(Emma, student)

The quotes above describe the mentoring relationship akin to a parental relationship that is protective in nature. Yet not all students valued this. In contrast, some students perceived this as being overbearing, somewhat limiting their autonomy which at times frustrated them. This

is articulated in the quote below by one student who felt restricted by her current mentor as to what she was allowed to be involved in; as a result, she perceived this was inhibiting her progress.

'See I found that my last placement, my mentor watched me do everything and she taught me an awful lot.....she did teach me a lot, whereas now I'm not allowed to do what she showed me and I just don't get it. So kinda I do feel like I've went backwards instead of forwards as my mentor won't let me do anything'

(Keira student).

'some mentors are just No! she's my student and they get very protective, and only want you to work with them, which is great and that but if there is other things going on , I mean I get it but I just feel you can sometimes miss out on stuff'

(Jenna, student)

From the student's perspective, it is clear at times, they felt their learning opportunities were limited if mentors were regarded as being overprotective; nevertheless, there was no acknowledgement from the student participants of the risk, responsibility and ultimate accountability that lies with the registered practitioner, and the challenges associated with this. It appeared there was a lack of understanding of the complexities of the mentoring role as they only considered their own needs were paramount.

Taking the Time to Mentor

The development of a positive relationship appeared to be greatly enhanced when students were able to spend an adequate amount of time with their mentor. Similarly, mentors

recognised the added value of spending time with their students and how this helped forge a more meaningful relationship. Indeed, the mentors' concern seemed to extend beyond their normal working day as they strived to ensure students were looked after in their absence:

'You know if I've got a student and I am on a day off I will make sure she knows who she is on with, or what she is going to do, if she is going to theatre you know have stuff in place for them for the days I am off and they are not with me'

(Karen, mentor)

Conversely, when students were not able to spend adequate time with their mentor, this appeared to have negative consequences.

'Cos I've seen, like, that happening and then, so for like a fortnight you're just kinda wandering about looking for somebody to take you under their wing'

(Jessica, student).

'It can be really hard trying to get time with their mentor, say they've got two weeks annual leave, then they go off sick and that student maybe only had 20% of their time with their mentor. That's having an impact on that student as well, because they're not getting the quality time that they should be having to spend time with their mentor, and again that impacts on their placement experience'

(Gillian, PEF).

'But I do encourage them to either be with me or the co-mentor as I think that's good they learn more that way otherwise they can be left kinda floundering about the ward or moved from pillar to post' (Karen, Mentor).

The above quote introduces the term floundering; this arose from discussions with participants who recognised the importance of having a named individual responsible for the student's learning experience. Without this relationship and personal sponsorship, it was clear that students could be left feeling helpless with very little direction. However, for some staff, having the time to spend with students could be difficult. This was particularly true of one mentor, who was also a deputy charge nurse. The mentor described how she often felt guilty not spending enough time with her student when her daily workload was often consumed by managerial tasks as she was often left in charge of the ward.

As well as having time to work with their mentor, investing the time and interest in getting to know the student and their learning needs were also considered to be important. In particular, time spent at the outset of the placement was viewed as critical as it appeared to set the tone for the rest of the experience.

'My mentor is the first mentor in the whole three years, she took my book and she said just give me half an hour and she sat in the office she read through emm my feedback and stuff like that and then she could then plan my management placement she kinda of could see, she felt as though there wasn't any gaps and I could go straight onto the

management role. But she was the first mentor that really really took the time to look back and about me, about how I felt what I felt I needed to develop’.

(Cerys, student)

‘I feel like I have been good on placements where you go in and your mentor....they go I am just going to take 15 minutes to go over....what does she feel competent in, what does she feel she needs – say for example if I didn’t have a lot of experience with catheters, they say like if that ever comes up you can get that experience, things like that’.

(Eva, student).

Whilst the experiences students recalled were variable, it is clear the investment at the outset of the placement helped cultivate a positive relationship and a positive learning experience.

Personal Characteristics

When exploring the student-mentor relationship, participants often described the behaviours and attitudes that were adopted and the personal characteristics that developed or hindered these relationships. Terms such as enthusiastic, caring, approachable and having patience were often used to articulate the positive characteristics of a good mentor:

‘I’ve been lucky though; all my mentors have been great. Great. I can’t fault any of my mentors, they’ve been fabulous. They explain everything. They went over everything. They had patience with me. Whenever I asked a question, it wasn’t a hassle for them to tell me the answer. They, they always supported me through everything, and they were

there, and it was..... they've been fabulous. Fabulous. I mean you hear all these horror stories but I honestly can't say a thing as my mentors have all been great'.

(Carly, student)

The above excerpt demonstrates how having a mentor that was patient, supportive and took the time to explain things helped the student flourish in that environment. Reflecting on this, mentors, too, recognised the importance of being approachable:

'I hope I am an approachable mentor and approachable team member, but I just like things done properly and I always explain to the students if there is anything you don't understand just ask'

(Ailsa, mentor)

In contrast, there were some aspects that were highlighted that were deemed not to be conducive to the development of a positive relationship. These aspects made it difficult for students to form meaningful relationships with their mentor, which ultimately impacted on their learning as they felt unable to ask questions. The quote below depicts a situation where there was limited personal connection between the student and mentor and how this influenced their learning experience.

'I've just worked so much better without, without my mentor being there. She was not here this week and I'm just feeling so much better about it. She teaches you a lot, but we just don't have a good rapport.

So, it's just awkward not very supportive, not for students, it's harder to approach if you have got a question and stuff like that'. (Cerys, student)

The students were also able to identify when there was a lack of willingness on the mentor's behalf to support students; this appeared to have a detrimental effect on their experience, with some students questioning why they had taken on this role as a mentor.

*'I've been nothing but, like, a nuisance to you. Why are you a mentor?
I think some of them are... You're kinda forced with a mentor, so I guess they just resent it. You should want to do it, you can just tell when they don't want to be a mentor, it's not nice'. (Jessica, student)*

As previously discussed, the relationships that developed were not the sole responsibility of the mentors. Mentors, PEFs and liaison lecturers spoke of the challenges when students appeared to be disinterested and the strain this had on developing effective learning relationships.

*'I mean see if you have a student who is struggling but they are keen and they want to learn that's fine, you can work with that, but if they come over uninterested, it's hard, sometimes there is not an awful lot you can do to ...I mean you can't make them do it'
(Kat, mentor)*

To summarise, all participants in this study highlighted the significance of an effective student-mentor relationship; although there were contrasting opinions and experiences, there was a

general agreement that fostering a meaningful relationship was crucial and without this, learning could be compromised.

5.4.3 Peers 'One of Us'

Participants in the study described the significance of their peers. In particular, students expressed how much they valued these relationships as they provided support, guidance and reassurance throughout their practice learning experience.

Their fellow student peers were regarded as 'one of them' in an attempt to describe how only their peers could fully appreciate how they were feeling as a student nurse in a placement area.

'I think having a student or two, it is quite nice cos you feel like there's someone that is in the same situation as you'. (Emma, student)

'There's definitely positives to being in placement with another student. Even if it's just for a wee bit of moral support' (Jenna, Student).

In terms of this moral support from other students, the liaison lecturers also recognised the value that student peers could add to practice learning experiences.

'The other students are their 'go-to' guys. Even the quiet ones, in my experience they would probably say first to another student if they were unhappy or struggling than go to a mentor or the University' (Scott, Liaison lecturer)

This was reinforced by the students who indicated they felt more comfortable asking another student for help if there was something they were unsure of, for fear of being ridiculed. They perceived their peers as being more approachable.

'I remember back when I was in first year and having a second or third year student there, they understood, they had no long been in my position, so if there was something that you felt silly asking your mentor or a nurse, you could ask another student'
(Abby student)

For some students, the cohesive relationships that were formed with their peers at times appeared to be invaluable. This was particularly relevant where challenging environments were encountered, as their peers were able to provide reassurance and had an appreciation of how they were feeling.

'It's good to have support from each other, so when I was like Uh..... I don't know if I want to do this anymore, like, I don't feel supported they'd be like oh no, you'll be fine. It'll get better and, like, they're the reason I stayed in the placement'
(Sophie, student).

One student, in particular, reflected on their experiences, recalling that without the support from the other student, they may have left the programme.

'Both Sarah and I were there and if it wasn't for Sarah, I don't know... I wouldn't have got through it, seriously I would not have made it past the four weeks, I would have turned around and quit it.....this was my first experience in care.'
(Jennifer student)

The above quote captures the strong bonds that can develop between fellow students and the profound impact these relationships can have. It also demonstrates how peers added value to the practice learning experiences by providing moral support, reassurance and encouragement that otherwise appeared to be lacking.

Whilst the benefit of having peer support was frequently discussed, not all students were allocated placements with their peers. The following quote reflects the isolation one student described on placement.

'I would have loved to have had somebody else that was just there to talk to, I mean I liked the ward, and they were all..... well nice but it's not the same when you are there yourself' (Nicole, student)

It was also clear from the data that student peers not only supported each other emotionally but also contributed to their learning and development of confidence. This was epitomised by one student's comments below.

'when I was in A&E I had, I had a first-year student and a second-year student and I got sent one of them to actually teach them stuff about A&E that they didn't know, rather than their mentors doing it. And I thought that was really good cos I was like, oh I don't really know anything and then, teaching it I was like, oh, actually, I do know. So that was a really good thing that I emm ..enjoyed'

(Nicole, student)

This highlights the mutually beneficial relationship with their peers through shared learning experiences. Here teaching a more junior student appeared to not only provide support but

also helped build their confidence as they were able to augment their own learning and development and share their knowledge. However, as table 11 demonstrates, not all placement areas support all levels of nursing students. This somewhat limits the opportunities for senior students to teach more junior students.

Despite the positive viewpoints discussed above, not all students described their peers in a supportive context. For some, they compared their learning experiences with their peers in a somewhat competitive manner when vying to get the 'best' learning experiences and opportunities.

'But, I think there can be too many students in a placement at one time as well, where you are kinda competing to go and do things and see things, emm, or you kinda feel it's a wee bit unfair because they're doing stuff that you're not allowed to do. You are competing sometimes'. (Emma, student).

*'But, on the other hand, you can have too many students *General Agreement* where you're no getting, like, for instance your mentor's off that day, and there's something that you could do or want to see but the other student's gonna get to do it, and she's done it three or four times, but because her mentor's there and your mentor isn't, you're just kinda left' (Jenna, student).*

This indicates that there is a fine balance between the collegial, supportive relationships and the competitive nature of learning with peers on placement. However, this finding could be indicative of the students' stage on the programme as all students participating in the study

were third-year students. This constant comparison with other students could be reflective of their own confidence as they prepare to finish the programme of study.

5.4.4 The Student's Role - You Get Out What You Put In.

As already discussed, the theme 'teamwork makes the dream work' is centred around the notion that everyone within the practice learning environment has a part to play in order to successfully facilitate pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences.

Whilst much of the available literature focuses on the invaluable contribution of mentors (Thompson, Docherty and Duffy, 2017), there appears to be very little consideration of the student's role, alluding to the notion that students are almost passive within their learning and professional development in practice. Yet within this research, there was a clear subtheme identified by all with regard to the student's roles and responsibilities and the impact this could have on practice learning experiences.

Preparation – The Key to Success.

From the Liaison lecturer, mentor, PEF and manager participants, there was a clear acknowledgement regarding the student's responsibility in the advanced preparation for their placement experience. Those students who were motivated to complete the learning activities and research prior to commencing were viewed favourably.

'some students are very well prepared for coming to placement, the last student, the work that she did before she came to this ward, oh it was outstanding, she had done so much.'

What the student wrote about her expectations was amazing it was outstanding preparation in her SOAR, and it let me know right away that I had a good student because she came prepared'

(Ailsa, mentor)

In the above excerpt, the mentor reflects on the pre-placement research the student had completed and recorded in her practice assessment handbook. What is evident is how the mentor clearly associated the student's preparedness with how well they would perform on placement, suggesting the good work ethic and effort made by the student prior to commencing would be indicative of the effort they made whilst on placement.

Ownership

The aspiration to do well and take responsibility for their own learning was also articulated by the students.

'I think as well you are responsible for your own learning opportunities, so you are literally getting out what you have put in, so if you don't get anything back that's your fault to... to some extent. I hate to be the one to say it, but it's true'

(Carly, student).

Here the student clearly recognised that they themselves had responsibility and ownership for their own learning. The narrative accounts from mentors also highlighted the concept of ownership, valuing those that were motivated and engaging, recognising them as adult learners.

'Because I am a big fan of ownership of things, I don't, I don't believe in spoon feeding people, I think no it's your placement, what are you hoping to get out of it? What are you looking to learn? What previous experience have you had... and then we can build on that together'

(Elaine, mentor)

'The students I think have got to be, I know they might find it hard, but they have to come out and say I am not sure I am allowed to do this..... or yes, I can do that, but I need you beside me. I mean some of these students have had really different types of placements, so I think to some extent we need to.....we have to be guided by them'

(Tricia, Mentor)

Expectations

The liaison lecturers, PEFs and more than half of the mentors within this study, explored the concept of student expectations, in particular, the realistic or unrealistic expectations that some students had in relation to their role as a student nurse.

'Sometimes I think what they expect from their placements and things is not realistic'

(Tricia, mentor)

'There was this one student who had quite firm expectations regarding what she wanted to achieve in her placement area, emm... and it was a bit slow to develop from her perspective, and I think it was unrealistic expectations from the student. She was a mature student who had done loads of other things previously and she, she almost had

a charter of expectations in her head, a student charter of what she expected to happen, and although ideally, I think we would love to be able to provide that, and I think we go some way to try and provide that, her charter and expectations were a wee bit more developed than ours. Her expectations weren't met initially'

(Christine Liaison lecturer)

'I don't know what their expectation of being a nurse is.....I mean I can see the expectation from the public just getting higher and higher.... The role of the nurse now has changed so much, I think for many of the students it comes as a shock what their role really is'

(Moirra, mentor)

The idea of unrealistic expectations or expectations not being met was not reflected in the student focus groups; however, the selection bias of the student sample group could potentially explain this. All students included in this study were final year placement students who, by this point, had had numerous placement learning experiences. As such, they would have gained, developed or altered their expectations over time due to their previous experiences. Nevertheless, what this sub-theme does draw attention to is how prepared students are for their early practice learning experiences, and tentatively questions if they are fully equipped to deal with the realities of clinical practice and hold realistic expectations of what to expect?

Positive Attitude.

The findings also explored the topic of students' general attitude towards placement. Those students that portrayed a positive attitude towards their learning experience were viewed upon more favourably. A positive student attitude was described in terms of the enthusiasm, motivation, willingness and the interest they showed towards their placement area.

'I know we think of them as our students, and we are quite protective of them and want the best for them and all that but the student has to be willing when they go to placement'

(Kate, Liaison lecturer)

'The majority of them are enthusiastic and keen and it is nice just to have somebody that's enthusiastic about nursing and is keen to learn'

(Moir, Mentor)

'I mean the ones that do get involved do really well. They don't realise, I mean maybe they think...they don't realise how important their attitude is, the way they come over, that's a huge part of it'.

(Allison, ward manager)

'it's just the initial impressions that they make with you can very much determine how the rest to of the placement is going to go. What they will do is phone up and we will say right here is your mentor you have such and such and, you'll say here are your shifts and they say well I can't do.... And they have not even put a foot in the door and it's just not a good impression'.

(Karen, Mentor)

Although the reasons affecting students' motivation are discussed elsewhere in this chapter, mentors appeared less willing to support those students who came across as having an apparent lack of interest.

However, there was recognition that, for many students coming into a new clinical area could be daunting, possibly influencing how they behaved.

'Another obvious thing that can impact on placement is the students, is their attitude towards their placement. I mean there is a whole range of things going on with a student when they first turn up on placement, there is the fear of going to a new area, every one of them no matter how confident they might appear, there is always that little of bit of fear turning up to a new area' (Scott Liaison lecturer).

The student nurse participants in this study also appeared to understand the significance of having a positive attitude. When describing her approach towards her placement one student reflected that;

'but see to be honest, I approach every experience the same, see if I can walk out that door and.... and know that I have helped someone, even the nurse.....my aim ...see for someone to say, gosh she was a good help today whether it was doing personal care, helping out anything...my aim is always to be I want folk to think she was a really good help today' (Jenna, Student).

To conclude, this subtheme explored the student's role within their practice learning experience. The development of an effective relationship appears essential within the context of practice learning. Previous discourse appears to position mentors at the centre of any relationship breakdown (Thomas, Jinks and Jack, 2015). Alternatively, the data from this study clearly emphasises that this is a two-way relationship. As such, students have a responsibility to come prepared to their placement, take ownership of their own learning and approach each experience with a positive professional attitude.

5.4.5 Everybody's Student (The Role of Others).

This subcategory emerged as the participants described how the wider staff group, in particular medical staff, health care support workers and other registered nurses, influenced practice learning experiences. Specifically, they discussed the relationships that evolved and the interprofessional sharing of knowledge that occurred.

Medical Staff

Medical staff were highlighted, by all participant groups, as being a valuable learning resource for the students. One mentor described the rich learning experiences doctors were able to provide to the student nurses and how this was perceived.

'I mean we have a few Doctors who are just amazing with the students and every single student that comes they say, I can't believe how helpful they were towards me as a student nurse'

(Moir, mentor)

Students also described the inclusive nature of interprofessional learning where medical staff actively sought out the student nurse involving them in learning opportunities:

'I find a lot in my ward with the Doctors, like, if they go to do something they'll come and they'll find me and they'll ask me if I want to see it as well, rather than just going and doing it and leaving me, y'know, out the loop'.

(Jennifer, student).

Similarly, another student explained how valued they felt when being included by senior medical staff.

'You always get the impression that a consultant doesn't want to talk to a student but in my last placement, they make you feel totally included in everything and I got sent down to theatre and he, he actually shouted over to me. He was showing me what exactly he was taking out and what was happening and stuff, and he did make me feel very included in what he was doing'.

(Keira, student)

As demonstrated from the quotes above, the students placed a great deal of importance on the relationship they formed with medical staff; despite this, not all interactions experienced were positive, with some students left feeling belittled. The quote below provides one student's experience that encapsulates this feeling:

'When they are nice.....and that does make a difference because some doctors, it's like you're no even there. And see when you're doing, like, the Doctors' rounds and stuff like that, and they don't take your word for it. Do you know what I mean? Like, it's, like it's almost kinda - You're just a student, get me somebody important'

(Cerys, student)

Although it was clear the students valued positive interactions and learning experiences when they occurred, the data also uncovered a potential hierarchy and power relationship between medical and nursing staff that would appear to still exist within modern-day healthcare. Rather than a collegial relationship, the students appeared to place medical staff in a superior position.

Healthcare Support Workers.

Healthcare support workers, or nursing auxiliaries as they were often referred to, were also frequently discussed throughout the data collection. Mixed views were expressed in relation to their role in supporting students' learning experiences. Although all participants recognised that a lot could be learned from the support staff, at times, there appeared to be a conflict of roles. Students reflected on their previous experiences working with healthcare support workers and described some of the challenges they had encountered.

'It doesn't matter that you're with your mentor and you're trying to do what your mentor's left you to do while they're on their break, if the auxiliary wants you to do something, they want you to do it there and then'.

(Jessica, student)

'I've found in a few wards when the students go in the auxiliaries think that the students are actually there to work for them'

(Sarah, student)

This finding considers the healthcare support workers' lack of understanding of the students' learning needs and their role on placement. So much of the available literature focuses on nursing students and the staff that primarily support their learning, the mentors; however, it is inevitable when looking at the current workforce skill mix that they will learn from an extended team of staff. Consequently, if healthcare support workers have a limited understanding of their role in nursing students' placement experiences, inevitable confusion will occur.

This was also articulated by one of the mentors who described a situation where she had to remind the senior student that as much as the health care support worker's role was important, the student was there to learn how to nurse and should be focused on more nursing skills.

'And I had to say to the student, what are you doing in this room? And they were like...she (the healthcare assistant) just asked for my help, I am like, no you are here with me today we are doing the ward round, yes what you are doing is important but I want you to come on the ward round'

(Tricia, mentor)

The above quote also highlights the conflict students can face between supporting the wider team and their learning. Furthermore, as with medical staff, this finding also raises the issue of hierarchy and where student nurses position themselves as they strive to develop their professional identity.

Despite the challenges highlighted above, there were several positive examples where healthcare support workers' involvement was regarded as crucially important, especially within the early placement experiences. They were viewed as an invaluable resource who

could show students the customary ways of working when first entering new practice learning environments.

'The auxiliaries on our ward are a great resource for students'

(Ailsa mentor)

'I always remember see my first placement, it was a great ward, see the auxiliaries were just great, for me I had never worked in care, I mean I had done other things, but I never worked in care before and they were great, great they were really good, you know, at showing me the ropes and helping me, pointing me in the right direction, I mean every ward is just so different'

(Jenna, student)

Whilst the concept of feeling welcomed and belonging within an area is discussed in more detail later in this chapter, what is clear from the student's narratives is the recognition that support staff could greatly influence practice learning experiences. The statement above draws parallels to the community of practice theory as outlined by Wenger (1998), where the old-timers within the community, in this case, the support staff, shared knowledge of the cultural norms with the newcomer (the student).

Other Registered Nurses.

A consistent pattern that also emerged was the influence that other registered nurses had on the overall learning experience. Many of the students described how they enjoyed working with other nurses on the ward. They spoke about the different ways of working and how this could add positively to their learning.

'I really do find that in every placement I've been in, every other nurse has been supportive. And, if they're doing something they will ask "Oh, do you want to come and see it?", so you can see it, or, if something is getting taken out, like a sutures or something, they'll say "Do you want to come and take it out" and things. They do really try and include you'.

(Eva, student)

Similarly, another student Cerys, discussed the different personalities she encountered, and how at times, she preferred working with other registered staff as opposed to her mentor, as they had a better rapport. This demonstrates the importance of developing good interpersonal relationships with the wider team. However, for some students, this appeared to be more profound than just developing good relationships. There were examples of good role modelling from other nursing staff, where having a positive attitude, patience, and a willingness to support learning helped make the student feel valued. The example below epitomises this where the mentor's willingness to share their knowledge and experience was appreciated and appeared to offer a sense of security to the student.

'There was this one nurse, she wasn't my mentor or anything, but she was so good, she just knew everything and nothing was a bother if I asked her stuff. I worked a lot of shifts with her, and she taught me so much, nothing was a bother'

(Sam, student)

The collaborative contribution of the wider team on the students' learning experience was also echoed in the quote below:

'every single person on that ward affects your learning, every single one, from the nursing assistants, domestics that can tell you how to clean up, clean up properly, you could learn from everything and everyone. If they're really team-minded then it's a great placement'.

(Emma, student).

This sub-theme, everybody's student, was epitomised by one student's description of the inclusive nature of students' practice learning experiences.

'that's when it worked best for me, see when the whole ward takes you on as a student. See when everyone takes you under their wing, the whole ward being aware of what student nurses can do, everyone from the domestics to the nursing assistants, everyone being on board with taking a student nurse'.

(Carly, student)

Whilst both quotes demonstrate the importance of inclusivity, they also draw attention to the value of role clarity. In these examples provided, having clear expectations of the student nurses' role helped develop their confidence on placement. Similarly, for the student, having an awareness and understanding of the contribution of other staff could enhance their learning experience.

Multidisciplinary working and interprofessional learning are a core element of effective team working that ensures patient safety and improves patient outcomes (Joynes, 2017). Moreover, the evidence emerging from this study indicates that this philosophy of a collaborative

approach to nursing students' learning can also positively impact on practice learning experiences.

5.5 Theme Two – The Emotional Rollercoaster.

Diagram 4

The use of this metaphor attempts to capture the range of emotions and the emotional journey that emerged when exploring the data. The focus of this theme is positioned around the polarising accounts of participant experiences. The study participants were exposed to a variety of challenges and experiences within the practice learning environment. As such, they experienced a range of positive and negative emotions. This theme attempts to describe and contextualise the array of emotions, in order to interpret and understand the effect on practice learning experiences.

5.5.1 Belongingness

(Diagram 5 Belongingness).

When exploring the context of the practice learning environment, a noteworthy finding was the premise of belongingness; the desire to belong prevailed within the student focus groups. Belongingness has been described within the literature as the emotions student nurses experience that makes them feel included, accepted, and secure within a specific environment (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008). Whilst the findings from this study depict students' experiences of belongingness, both positive and negative; they also highlight the awareness and the importance of belongingness from the other participant groups and the measures implemented in an effort to support this. Furthermore, this subtheme attempts to explore and

interpret factors that can engender or inhibit belongingness within students' practice learning experiences.

As mentioned above, without exception, all of the student participants in the focus groups expressed a desire to belong; however, this was not always what they experienced. Some students shared stories where they felt excluded. These feelings of exclusion appeared to have devastating consequences for student morale, to the extent that they were worried and anxious to attend placement. There were several examples provided where this led to the students feeling demoralised. For example, Gaynor (student) described one particular placement as being unsupportive and unwelcoming.

'You're dreading going into a placement like that, it's just an awful feeling and you're just trying to pretend everything will be ok'

(Gaynor, student)

'like you, I was dreading every shift, every time I got off that lift my heart sank that I was going in there.....they just didn't take time with students'

(Emma, student)

Similarly, one student described a negative placement experience where she did not have a sense of belonging. Instead, she felt a burden to the team, however, rather than feeling able to address her concerns with anyone, she withdrew into herself and, in her own words 'just put her head down' to get the placement finished.

'I mean I didn't even get 40% of time with my mentor, turned up for shifts that she had put in extra shifts and she didn't turn up, I was made to feel a burden, I had to just put my head down and get on with it'

(Sarah, student)

When trying to ascertain how this lack of belongingness transpired, the students described some passive aggressive behaviours such as being ignored, not being shown things, or not being invited for tea breaks; these behaviours made them feel resented for being there.

'Cos no every ward you go into are happy to see a student, some don't, they just cannie be bothered with you so it can make it difficult'.

(Jessica, student)

'you have folk that just walk past you, I mean I know they are not expected to be involved or anything but if they have a...if you are able to talk to them and stuff it would make you feel like a valued member'

(Nicole, student)

Regardless of whether these behaviours were intentional or not, for the students who experienced this, it was not pleasant. Some behaviours were more explicit; one example describes how a member of staff openly acknowledged to the student, that they loathed working with students.

'there was one person in particular, that told us to our face that she hates students'

(Ella, student)

The use of the word hate describes the strong reactions that students could be exposed to from others. Worryingly, these experiences of incivility and lack of inclusivity within the placement area seemed to affect their whole experience. Learning opportunities seemed to

be thwarted when students did not feel able to participate, and they appeared to disengage from the learning environment. What is apparent here is how, when feeling socially excluded, students were unable to thrive.

'it was horrible and it was such a good learning ward that we could have learned hundreds...but we didn't because they didn't take the time or want to share things with students, and if you're resented being there, you just feel like I don't want to be here'

(Emma, student)

First Impressions

The data indicates that the initial reaction from the staff team could often dictate how a placement experience was going to be perceived. There was a general agreement within the focus groups that areas where they were prepared for the student's arrival, were much more welcoming.

'that last ward...like, you got introduced to everybody, so see on the first day you go into Sister's office and meet her, it's her that sends the email, you can see that she's linked in emails to your mentor, introducing the student before, it's a good example, they know you are coming'

(Jenna, student)

In contrast, they were examples provided where the placement areas did not appear prepared for the student's arrival. They described how this lack of awareness could be disconcerting at the outset of the placement.

'I think it's always an off-putting thing when you go in and they go ahh right a student, emmm..... you could...emmm..... you could go with emmm... and I am like why, why? Why do they not know I am coming?'

(Sarah, student)

'my last placement they didn't even know they were having me as a student. The mentor wasn't aware that they had me as a student. I mean their attitude on the first day was right off, and I was like this is going to be great but I thought no, no it will be fine fine, fine, fine, you know how you just jolly yourself along'

(Cerys, student)

This quote not only describes how the practice learning environment's lack of preparedness impacted on how welcomed the student felt but also describes the internal negotiation and resilience from the student's perspective as they tried to convince themselves that things would improve.

Forming Relationships

Although a detailed discussion of the role of the mentor is described elsewhere, if there was not an opportunity to form meaningful, supportive learning relationships with their mentor, students' feelings of being socially isolated seemed to be increased. The excerpts included below detail how two different students did not have an allocated mentor for their first few weeks on placement and, as such, both felt isolated within the environment and lacked any direction.

'you were just kinda left by yourself up the top of the ward and then all of the other students were, kinda, taken away by their mentor to take part in other stuff'

(Ella, student)

'I went to, like, an area and my mentor was off, sick, and nobody took responsibility for me so for like, the first three weeks or something you're just going in and nobody wants you. Well, it got to the stage I was having lunch in my car because nobody included me, and that... you're dreading going into a placement like that, it's no enjoyable'

(Carly, student)

These quotes above affirm the crucial role mentors' sponsorship is in helping students settle within an area and form meaningful relationships; moreover, it highlights a reliance on this relationship, where without personal mentor support, students appeared to feel neglected and ignored.

Early Experiences

Interestingly, when probed further, the experiences students reflected on where they felt excluded were not necessarily recent experiences. For the majority of the students, these happened early on in their student nurse journey; however, how they had been treated still seemed to have a profound effect. This finding reinforces the social complexity of the practice learning environment and demonstrates how it can be difficult for newcomers to navigate. This appeared particularly relevant to early career student nurses as they learn how to interact and integrate into these communities of practice. The term 'knowing your place'

was used by one of the students as they described the social hierarchy within the area and their struggle to know where their role fit within this.

'you just don't know your place in a ward sometimes'

(Nicole, student).

There was also recognition by one of the students that every ward placement had its own organisational structure, making fitting in even more challenging due to the uniqueness of each area.

'But when we go in now as a third year, you watch how the ward runs, and I keep going back to first year and remembered folk saying 'every ward runs the same' and I am like that is wrong that is so so wrong cause every ward is completely different and it takes you a bit to get a feel for the area'

(Carly, student)

This was also recognised by two of the liaison lecturers, who also acknowledged the unique nature of every clinical placement area and the challenges this could present for student learning.

'You know every ward is different, and there are loads of things that can make it different for a student, you know whether it's the skills they get, or the type of patients they have, or how they get on with their mentor or even wee things like the shift pattern every area is different and it can be hard for the students not to compare one to the next'.

(Christine, Liaison lecturer)

Small Things, Big Difference.

Throughout the interviews with the ward manager and mentors, it became apparent that they recognised and were aware of the need for students to feel part of the team. They discussed the small things they tried to do to make the students feel included.

'We really try to be prepared for the student coming, every student that starts gets a welcome pack that gives more info about the ward and idea of the things we do. We allocated their mentor in advance and make sure everyone knows they are coming'

(Allison, ward manager)

'I think one of the most important things is you have to be welcoming to these people and you have to understand where they are coming from because you are very comfortable going into work, you know your responsibilities, and things you have to do and you are comfortable with your colleagues, so these students, boys and girls are coming and maybe they don't, they have no idea, they have never been in your department, so, you feel you are really quite responsible for making that experience a positive one'

(Carol, mentor)

'I think, see the very simple things like putting your student's name up on the whiteboard beside the nurse they are working with, it helps make them really feel part of the team. Also, introducing your student nurse to all the team, not just the staff but also the patients as well too, its important, so they know that she's not just a student. When you walk into the ward in the morning I always say, I am Ailsa I am the nurse you are working with today, and I introduce them to the patients too'.

(Ailsa, mentor).

Although this may seem like a small gesture, this is an example where the student's visibility and contributions were recognised and taken into consideration.

Whilst the importance of belonging within any area is crucial, some students appeared more resilient than others recognising that even challenging placement areas could be good learning experiences. There was also an awareness of the 'bigger picture' when comparing positive and negative learning experiences. Two students who had been to the same area discussed how staff shortages affected their learning experience as staff did not have the same available time to support them, and the area's attitude toward students learning had become the norm.

'I think it's severely understaffed they don't have the time cause they are so busy and because of that they don't have the inclination... ' (Jenna, student)

Speaking about the same ward another student commented.

'I think it's been like that for so long that they don't want to change it, that's the norm for in there, and it's such a shame as you could learn so much.'

(Sarah, student)

When it's Good, it's Great.

In contrast to the lack of belongingness discussed above, it became apparent that when students had a sense of belonging, their confidence grew, and they appeared to have increased self-esteem.

'That last placement was such a good learning ward, everybody took you under their wing and if anything was going on, you know anything new to see or that they would come and get me, which was great, you know, as in a couple of months we are going to have to put on a blue tunic'

(Cerys, student)

When describing how it felt when they had a positive experience, the students used words that included valued, appreciated, supported and confident. Even when mistakes were made, if the students felt safe and secure, they appeared to appreciate and value the feedback, as it was delivered in a constructive way.

'I hadn't realised that you weren't supposed to do that, but my mentor was great, he took me to the side and explained what I should have done, and I needed to hear that so the next time I could do it properly, you know you need that feedback'

(Eva, student)

There was also an example in one area where they took on board the student's feedback about a learning resource and made changes accordingly, this seemed to boost the student's self-esteem, and her respect for the area as her opinion had been valued.

When trying to explore the concept of belongingness in more depth, the students were asked what made a difference. Some students raised the length of time they spent on an individual placement; they expressed how they felt they were just becoming settled in a placement area when it was time to move on, and they had to start the whole process of trying to fit in again.

This was in comparison to their latter final placement, where they spent 12 weeks in the same practice learning environment.

Others highlighted the importance of feeling valued and appreciated, as this made them feel like they had contributed and made a difference.

'See if I walk out of that ward and if someone is saying thanks very much for your help that was great that makes you feel better, that's priceless'.

(Ella, student)

'One positive, one positive remark, that's all it takes, yip one positive a thank you anything like that, one you did well today, that's it just one'

(Abby, student)

To conclude, this subtheme explored the concept of belongingness and highlighted that there is a fundamental need for students to feel welcomed and supported within the practice learning environment. Those students who felt secure and were part of the team appeared to thrive in their placement area with an increased sense of self-esteem. Mentors and liaison lecturers appeared aware of the importance of belongingness and described measures taken to ensure the students were included. Students shared stories where they felt excluded and ignored, and although, at times, this appeared to lead them to disengage from the learning environment, there was also an acceptance of this behaviour. However, the findings also draw attention to the socialisation process of nursing students, as it would appear many of the challenging experiences they shared were early on in their programme and suggests as they

become more knowledgeable and confident, their ability to adapt and fit into new placement areas increases.

5.5.2 Mentoring Highs and Lows of Being a Mentor.

This subtheme derived from the mentors' experiences of supporting pre-registration nursing students in practice. Here mentors experienced contrasting emotions; in particular, these negative experiences appeared to have a profound impact on them and their willingness to support future students.

Accountability and Responsibility

When reviewing the mentors' narratives, this category emerged from the different sources of stress that mentors highlighted. There was an acknowledgement from mentors with regard to the accountability and responsibility of their role, yet this appeared to be an additional source of stress at times, especially when dealing with challenging situations or students who were failing a placement learning experience.

One mentor spoke of the emotional turmoil and guilt they felt when a student had failed their placement, and whilst they felt assured in their decision making, the emotional fallout stayed with them.

'It was horrible, because you don't want to be that person....maybe someone is down to their last placement have passed their exams and all the rest of it and you are sitting there going, I have serious concerns about your practice.

It's not a nice situation in a way I feel responsible that they didn't pass and are now working as a nursing assistant and not the staff nurse they wanted to be.

That still reflects, and although it was a good few years ago when I still see the person, I feel bad'

(Tricia, mentor).

When exploring this, Tricia discussed the effect this experience had on her confidence as a mentor, as she temporarily questioned her ability to fulfil the role. There were three other mentors who also discussed challenging situations that had arisen; similarly, this left them feeling somewhat apprehensive moving forwards.

'I find that really hard and it sometimes makes you feel like, you know, I don't want to be a sign-off mentor because the responsibility is too big. It's huge, I do feel the responsibility of that and I did say to sister after that, I don't know if I want to be a mentor anymore'

(Ellen, Mentor)

The difficulties of supporting students who were underperforming were also echoed by the practice education facilitators.

'I think that's where our role comes in, it can be so hard for the mentors when they are failing a student, that's where it's important that we are there to support them, you know, make sure that an action plan has been written up and that so if that student doesn't pass we know we've done everything possible to support them, but it can be so hard cause as the end of the day you are dealing with a person'

(Maria, PEF)

From those challenging experiences, threaded through the narratives was the importance of the assessment process and affirmation in their decision making; furthermore, despite the emotional turmoil encountered, they all spoke of the support they received, in particular, from the practice education facilitators and managers.

'We had a situation where the student wasn't happy with their grade, you know I had taken lots of time with her assessment, written lots of feedback. Both me and the co-mentor had spoken about it and were happy, it was still a really good grade but the student felt she should have got higher. Anyway, she really wasn't happy and went to the sister. Don't get me wrong sister was great and supported us but still...but still the whole situation it just made me feel awful'.

(Karen, mentor)

Lack of Time to Mentor

Time or lack thereof, also appeared to impact negatively on practice learning experiences, and be a frequent source of stress mentors encountered. Balancing the day-to-day workload with student support was recognised as being problematic.

'I think time, time is a big factor, you have to give it time which working in a department where you are really busy you really don't have, you've got like a minute and a half, or something at the end of day (Laughs) I think you have to give time'

(Ellen, mentor)

'and time as well, to be able to spend and that's probably been the biggest restriction because you are constantly on and I sometimes feel that there needs to be a period so that you are not just quickly going through the book'

(Tricia, Mentor)

A lack of mentors and sign-off mentors to support the students' journey also emerged as an additional source of stress, for some, this resulted in an increased workload as there were fewer mentors to share the load.

'...at the moment in our area there are only two sign-off mentors me and one of the other girls so I am actually mentoring mentors and mentoring students, so my role is quite big just now'

(Tricia, mentor)

The increased workload of mentors was also recognised by students; they recalled how this impacted on mentors' attitudes towards having a student.

'I know they are short on mentors, and see as students we want these really good placements but see if at the end of the day if you get someone that's had a student constantly for two years, they maybe just don't want to do it anymore, and I get that'.

(Jenna, student)

The shortage of registered mentors was also broached by both of the practice education facilitators that participated in the study. Furthermore, the lack of mentors is also reflected in table 11, where inconsistent mentor numbers across the practice learning environments can be seen. Various reasons appeared to cause this, including staff movement and staff shortages, which have been previously highlighted elsewhere in the literature (Vinales, 2015); however, the data also draws attention to the limited access to the mentor preparation module and the consequences of this. Moreover, both PEFs described the impact this had on the current mentor workforce and the student placement availability as often areas were forced to reduce their service level agreement and the number of students they could support due to a lack of available mentors.

Paying it Forward

In contrast to the emotional challenges discussed, and in spite of the pressures faced, all the mentor participants in this study acknowledged the positive nature of mentoring. The category 'paying it forward' transpired as mentors recalled the professional and personal rewards of being a mentor. For some mentors supporting a student throughout their placement learning offered a sense of achievement that appeared to boost their self-confidence.

'I think it's, it's quite reassuring when you think all that hard work and effort has paid off, and I think you feel, like oh yeah, I am quite confident being a mentor, I really enjoy having a student, I embrace it I love having a student'

(Ailsa mentor)

Similarly, another mentor spoke about the satisfaction of 'passing it on' to the next generation of nurses.

'but for me, you do like to pass it on, like you are proud when you see somebody really coming on or they say they have really really enjoyed their experience or even better when they come back as staff nurses, its like god, I did something right'

(Tricia, mentor)

This was echoed by Carol's comments;

'I like to think that, erm, you're shaping and influencing... .. The future staff nurses. I've been doing this for over 30 years now and I like to think that I... I'm... I'm quite a perfectionist as my colleagues will confirm, and I like to think I'm cascading on and passing on good practice and ... passing on to the students that I... I want them to treat every patient as if it was their own family that was being treated, y'know... No cutting

corners, no "don't do that", this is why we're doing it and this is the reason why and ... I'm quite a perfectionist, but... Just to kind of shape the future... The future nurses that's gonnie be looking after me, I... Really want to teach them how to do it properly'.

(Carol, mentor).

The quotes above describe the fulfilment associated with supporting a student within the learning environment and seeing them thrive; furthermore, it highlights the mentor's role in setting standards and being an effective role model and how this positive attitude to supporting student learning can cultivate a sense of belonging for students.

In terms of the mentor's professional development, the students were also viewed as being a good learning resource that could enhance their professional practice. There were examples provided where the student had brought new information to the area and how supporting students encouraged the mentors to review their own practice.

' there was one occasion, this was a few years ago now when they were taught blood pressure, they are taught now to put the cuff on the other way which to me looked upside down, wee things like, when the student comes and says to you oh this is what we have been taught, and you think I wonder why that is, and you look into it, its things like that that keeps you up to date'.

(Moir, mentor)

'Things we take for granted that you don't actually consider why, then a student says why are you doing it like that and then you go through the process you think aww right. You go into automatic pilot to do things just because you do it so regularly, so it is really good when we have students as it makes you think about the why'.

(Kat, mentor)

To conclude, this subtheme highlighted some of the emotions mentors' experienced when supporting a student in practice. Whilst the additional workload demands on mentor time have been highlighted previously in the literature (Veeremah, 2012), the data reviewed in this study expands on this notion further. Moreover, the findings suggest that the potential stress experienced and lack of available mentors, if not managed consistently, may contribute to mentor fatigue and burnout, affecting staff morale. Nevertheless, in spite of the challenges mentors faced, there appeared to be an enthusiasm for supporting students on their professional journey of becoming a nurse.

5.5.3 Emotional Highs and Lows of Being a Student Nurse.

This subtheme evolved from the range of emotions the student participants had encountered related to practice learning experiences. The students described polarising accounts.

Feeling Overwhelmed

Overwhelmed was a word that was commonly used within the narrative recollections. There appeared to be two distinct reasons contributing to this: the learning environment, and external factors.

Half of the mentors described how students could often feel overwhelmed whilst on placement due to the fast-paced nature of the clinical environment and the stark realities they faced when caring for people.

'I mean you can read a million articles on nursing and it's all very good but then you have to find yourself standing in a department and everyone is needing help and you feel you are not working quick enough or hard enough, it can be really hard for them at times'.

(Ellen, mentor)

'I think what doesn't work well at times is the business of the ward, the speed and pace of the ward in particular of a morning, it can be really hard for them'

(Moir, Mentor)

'I think sometimes, because we are so fast paced and if they can't keep up there is that danger that they get left behind.

I mean it's all very well sitting in a class learning about dementia and stuff like that, but the reality of having to look after people like that in a 30 bedded acute ward, they don't know how to approach it and stand back'

(Tricia, mentor)

The pressures of students' academic work were also highlighted by all participant groups as causing stress and feelings of being overwhelmed for students while on placement.

'The students sometimes feel very overwhelmed in terms of their workload, the second years in particular were very stressed, they were working on their break studying physiology and anatomy I was like, don't, please just come for a break, you are working hard you need a break. I think you could just feel the tension the week before the exam, it was their last week here so I thought it was a bit unfair for them really'

(Ailsa, mentor)

'I actually found it quite hard on my last placement you know, it was in high care, I had never been anywhere like that before and trying to concentrate on that and my Uni assignment was really hard I was shattered'.

(Eva, student)

'I remember one student, in particular, she was on her last placement in an acute area, and she was struggling as she had her final assignment due in at the same time, she was like a different student once she had handed it in, as though she could fully concentrate on her placement and give it her best shot'.

(Christine, liaison lecturer)

There was recognition that, whilst on placement, the students were often under pressure from their academic workload; here, allowances were made within the clinical environment to help support this. Nevertheless, the findings suggest at times, the intensive academic workload can impact on the student's ability to fully engage with the learning opportunities in practice. All of the students discussed the competing demands placed upon them whilst they were working within the learning environment that could impact on their levels of stress. Alongside the academic pressures discussed above, there was also recognition that personal and professional demands could impact upon their learning experiences. This was also recognised by the mentors in terms of the additional pressures on the students' time when they were on placement. In particular more than half of the mentors discussed students outside commitments as a contributing factor impacting on practice learning experiences. Several examples were provided by the mentors, managers and PEFs with regard to the flexibility

afforded to the students in recognition of their family circumstances and other employment commitments; however, there was a suggestion that at times the lack of flexibility from some students could cause professional issues.

'...that can be a problem with students that their outside life can dictate what they do in their training. The majority of them have outside jobs that they have to try and fit in which can work with the 12-hour shifts but unfortunately, not here as we are predominantly 9 to 5, but we do try and work with them'

(Moir, mentor)

'Again, sometimes you do get students who do have various commitments or that and can't work closely with you and then that can be a kinda issue when they are like wanting to choose their shifts'

(Kat, mentor)

'I feel that at times they kinda, pick and choose their shifts, it's not all students, the majority of students are fantastic, but there is that odd number that will cause those professional issues, they forget sometimes that it's not just as easy as saying I don't want to work such and such a day, we maybe have extra staff on that day because they are starting'.

(Matty, PEF).

Being Assessed

From the students' perspective, there was a general agreement that being assessed in practice could cause them some level of stress. The student participants within this study appeared motivated to do well but were cognisant that their grade relied on how they were assessed by their mentor; as such, their assessment of clinical practice appeared to be a constant pressure. In particular, one student spoke about how nervous they felt before each assessment. Even though they had received no feedback to indicate things were not going well, there was always a level of anxiety and apprehension before their final assessment.

'I hate when your mentor is filling out your book, even if I have had good feedback all the way through it's still really nerving, I think every assessment you are always just wanting to...I mean you just want to do well and hear how they think you've done. I am like please, just tell me I am no gonna greet, I'm no gonna, please like please tell me how I've done'. (Gaynor, student)

Through the exploration of the assessment process, there were discussions relating to the level of feedback received following the assessment, where students compared feedback. Their discussion appeared to suggest they desired more constructive feedback to help them learn and grow, which at times was lacking, resulting in feelings of frustration.

'I don't think I have had enough constructive criticism in 3rd year, and I don't know if its they don't feel confident enough to do it or they just want to try and be nice as I think I would maybe do that a bit, I've got this mentor just now and she's like you're fine you're fine but I feel as though no one is ever going to be just fine'

(Jenna, student)

In contrast, one student was given constructive feedback that helped her develop; moreover, there was recognition and appreciation of how this feedback was delivered in a positive way.

'I know what you mean but in my last placement, they picked up yeah I was good at everything else but that you maybe need to work on X and Y and that's why you've not got an A1, and I was like ok, I was fine with that. I felt quite happy with that, I felt happy with my mark, so its good to get that feedback back as well, so now I know what I need to work on'

(Sarah, student).

Feeling Powerless

Unfortunately, when encountering challenging experiences, the students spoke about how they often felt powerless. There was a general agreement that despite the negative experiences, they were reluctant to raise any concerns and appeared almost resigned to the prospect that 'nothing gets done anyway'. The students also appeared to feel isolated when problems arose and did not know who to talk to. This was articulated by the quote below.

'I had a terrible experience in that ward, but I mean you couldn't tell anyone about it on the ward cause, there was nobody to tell, I mean I wouldn't even know who to tell' because they all seem to already be, like, this kinda meshed group so if I report one of them they're all gonna gang up on you. And just kinda, leave you out so what's the point'

(Sarah, student).

The reluctance of the students in this to raise concerns highlights their vulnerability within the practice learning environment. For students to speak up, they require safety, security, and the belief that their concerns will be listened to (Brown, 2022). In contrast, the findings suggest that in raising concerns, the students in this study feared retribution.

Interestingly this finding differed within the other staff groups that were interviewed. They discussed how there were clear channels of communication to provide support if required and demonstrates the trusting relationship that had formed between those providing support.

‘What’s great is the support from the PEFs , we can contact them for anything even something silly and she is able to help. If I think oh my gosh I just have to ask this and it makes me look like an idiot but we find it out and it’s a big help knowing that they are there and available especially if we have any concerns with a student’

(Moir, mentor)

Positive Emotions

Despite some of the challenges that students faced, overwhelmingly, all of the students discussed how much they enjoyed the practical component of the curriculum. Whilst there was a general agreement that there were some areas for improvement, the students spoke passionately about how much they valued their time on placement. The following terms were just some of the words used to describe how a positive experience made them feel; valued, supported, more confident, reassured, fulfilled, and inspired.

The passion students’ felt towards the practice learning environment appeared to be rooted within the interaction with others. The quote below exemplifies how one student positively viewed their learning experience, preferring this part of the programme.

'I'm not gonna lie, I always get so nervous when I first go to a new area, especially if you've heard stories about it, but see for me, it's the placements that have made this course, that's what I have enjoyed the most. I know we need the theory bit but for me it's all about the practical. See knowing that I have helped someone, that's what it is all about'.

(Abby, student)

For some students, there was a sense that within these final placement experiences, they were able to consolidate their knowledge and were thriving in their role as a student nurse.

'I just love my placements, that last ward was so good there was so much to learn, physically it was tough as it never stopped, but I left every shift buzzing. The ward team were so good at involving me and including me I had wee tear in my eye when I left, it's one of the best wards I have been on. Yes, it was busy but it was organised everyone just chipped in'.

(Cerys, student)

To conclude, working within any clinical learning environment, students will inevitably be faced with different situations and sources of stress, be it interactions, academic workload, or external pressures. Consequently, they will experience a range of emotions; as such, it is important that students feel prepared to be able to manage these emotions.

This study set out to explore practice learning experiences from the perspective of pre-registration nursing students and those that support their learning, including mentors, liaison lecturers, practice education facilitators and a manager. The findings support the view that the practice learning environment is a complex social entity both in terms of how students

negotiate their experiences within this authentic learning environment and how the other participant groups strive to support them. It is clearly a defining moment in their nursing career. Therefore, the overarching concept, emerging from the findings is based on the social dynamics of the practice learning environment, termed within this thesis as the social practice of learning (see diagram 6).

(Diagram 6 – The Social Practice of Learning).

5.6 Chapter Conclusion

This chapter presented the findings from this study; firstly, it outlined the participant information detailing the number of interviews and focus groups that were undertaken. The remainder of this chapter focused on the two themes and seven subthemes that were

identified following the data analysis process. This chapter highlighted how teamwork was at the core of positive practice learning experiences that extended beyond the student-mentor relationship. Moreover, the findings explored the emotional milieu experienced and the intensity of these experiences. Throughout, careful consideration was given to the quotes that were used to ensure they were representative of the themes identified and allowed the participants' voices to be heard. This next chapter presents the discussion.

Chapter 6 Discussion

6.1 Introduction to the Chapter

This chapter offers a discussion of the research findings. As described in Chapter 5, the findings identified two distinct yet interrelated themes along with seven subthemes. This chapter will provide a critical discussion of these themes, drawing upon the existing literature to explore, interpret and contextualise the findings. Following on, the conclusion is centred around the current position of pre-registration nurse education and practice learning experiences within the United Kingdom, where an exploration of the NMC (2018a) future nurse standards is provided in relation to the findings.

As described in chapter two, the review of literature was an iterative process that evolved throughout this research journey. At the outset of this chapter, another literature search was carried out. The aim of this search was to critically interrogate each of the themes in an attempt to interpret, contextualise and offer an understanding of the findings in relation to the existing evidence. Appendix 13 lists the additional literature identified.

6.2 Discussion Teamwork Makes the Dream Work.

Healthcare brings together diverse members of the multidisciplinary team, where the aim is to provide safe, effective patient care (Epstein, 2014). However, simply bringing staff together does not necessarily constitute an effective team. Although team members have different roles and responsibilities, effective teamwork is built on the premise of collaborative working towards a shared common goal (Ryan, 2017). The findings of this research study resonate with this and draw upon the notion that successful practice learning experiences are a collaborative

event where everyone has a part to play, including the student, to enrich practice learning experiences. Consequently, the findings from this study are in keeping with previous research findings that draw attention to the critical aspect of social interaction within this multi-professional highly complex learning environment (Walsh, 2015).

The concept of collaboration and effective teamworking also draws resonance with Wenger's writings in relation to communities of practice. Wenger asserts that cohesive communities of practice are bounded by three interconnected dimensions, mutual engagement, joint enterprise and a shared repertoire (Wenger, 1998). Mutual engagement refers to the interaction and active participation of the members leading to a shared meaning (Li *et al.*, 2009, Roberts, 2006). Joint enterprise relates to the common purpose or shared goals that bring members together, the collective interest towards a shared goal (Smith, Hayes and Shea, 2017). Finally, shared repertoire encompasses the tools or resources created to negotiate meaning and facilitate learning (Li *et al.*, 2009). There were several examples throughout this theme linked to these dimensions.

Mentoring Relationships

Through this exploration of practice learning experiences, emerging from the data, was the acknowledgement that the student-mentor relationship was multifaceted, where the participants' narrative accounts uncovered the complexity of this relationship and the perceived impact on learning.

All participants articulated the importance of the student-mentor relationship; in particular, the students perceived the success of this relationship was connected to the access they were given to the learning opportunities. Moreover, they perceived their learning could be compromised if the mentoring relationship was unsuccessful. This next section explores the

existing literature around mentoring and mentoring relationships, in order to understand why this relationship carries such significance.

Alston and Hansman (2020) describe mentoring as a broad term that encompasses a wide range of supportive learning relationships. Within the wider literature, mentoring relationships have been described as a process whereby a more experienced other guides, supports and shares knowledge with someone less experienced (Lin *et al.*, 2018). In addition, Miles (2011) argues, this understanding of the mentoring relationship is compatible with supplementary roles, including supervision and assessment, thus aligning with the NMC's use of the term mentorship within their publication of the Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008). Here they define the term mentor as a registered nurse or midwife that 'facilitates learning and supervises and assesses students in a practice setting' (NMC, 2008, p53).

However, the findings of this study suggest that the foundation of the mentoring relationship is built on more than just support; as discussed previously, there was a definite sense of the relationship being reciprocal and mutually beneficial. Similarly, Hale and Phillips' theoretical framework of mentorship depicts the mentoring relationship as being intense, dynamic, and profound (Hale and Phillips, 2018). Their grounded theory research identified three core dimensions threaded throughout a successful mentoring relationship: earnest intentions, filial bond, and trustworthiness. Although their study focused on nurse-to-nurse mentoring during the transition of newly qualified practitioners, many of the conclusions within their research were mirrored within the findings of this study and provide some insight into the development and importance of mentoring relationships.

In this research study, the mentors' dedication to their role was evident. They took great care to plan relevant learning activities, involve the students in care delivery and ensure support

was continually provided. Moreover, their disappointment was palpable when this same commitment did not appear to be reciprocated by the student. According to Hale and Phillips (2018), this is an example of earnest intentions where the mentors are committed to their role in assisting the development of the student's confidence and professional expertise. To establish effective mentoring relationships, mentors are invested in the student's personal and professional growth; however, for the relationship to thrive, these earnest intentions must be reciprocated and reflected in the student's commitment and willingness to engage, develop and grow as an individual (Hilli *et al.*, 2014; Hale, 2015). The findings from this study suggest that when this commitment was not shared, the relationship faltered and could not flourish. Indeed, this was emphasised within the students' perspectives; they identified how being supported by someone who did not want to mentor them could be detrimental to their learning. Nevertheless, the students were cognisant of the constraint mentors faced; they recognised how increased pressures from work and management roles combined with a general lack of mentors in some areas potentially contributed to a lack of enthusiasm for the mentoring role. This finding has been highlighted previously where, despite the professional responsibility to support students learning, mentors were often left frustrated as they struggled to balance the demands of their workload with student support (Bowen, Kables and Keatringe, 2019).

The clinical workload of mentors has been recognised previously as a barrier to effective mentoring (Foster *et al.*, 2015; Veeremah, 2012; Teatheredge, 2010). Within this study, the mentors and manager acknowledged that the role could be challenging and, at times, overwhelming; however, for the most part, they did not perceive this as a barrier. Alternatively, as one mentor suggested, the complexity of patient care provided enhanced learning opportunities for students to participate in and learn from. Only one mentor described

how her leadership role as a senior member of the team impeded her ability at times to provide support. What is clear is how the mentors and students in this study had different perceptions of the impact workload had on mentoring. This difference could present a challenge; whilst the mentors did not perceive their busy workload as an obstacle to effectively support students, in contrast, the students appeared very aware. They were cognisant of their mentor's workload and did not want to disturb or interrupt them. This suggests that although they may have been physically in the same area, their mentor was not always accessible. The importance of accessibility resonates with the work of Eller, Lev and Feurer (2014); through their exploration of effective mentoring relationships, they described accessibility as a key component. In particular, mentees valued the interactions with mentors who made time for them, even when busy. They suggest that a lack of confidence and feelings of abandonment could occur if mentors were not accessible.

There were also instances within this study of the nurturing relationship that was cultivated where mentors appeared to genuinely care for students' wellbeing. This seemed more intensified when students required additional support to achieve their placement learning outcomes. This familial affection draws parallels with a maternal relationship and is an example of the filial bond developed between the mentor and mentee (Hale and Phillips, 2018). Here the relationship is based upon open, honest, and transparent communication that encourages accountability between both parties. Similarly, Hilli *et al.* (2014) explain how the origins of a successful mentoring relationship begin with a caring learning environment that is epitomised by permissiveness and honesty.

The need for openness, honesty, and transparency also highlights the vulnerability within the mentoring relationship. In this study, the students frequently spoke of their apprehension and

anxiety regarding their placement; they appeared to look towards their mentor for emotional support if they were feeling overwhelmed or experiencing periods of self-doubt. Consequently, when they had a supportive mentoring relationship, these feelings were somewhat alleviated. The vulnerability was also evident when the students disclosed their weaknesses or areas for further development; where there was a meaningful relationship, the mentors were able to provide reassurance and guidance that fostered a sense of safety and security, all elements of the profound nature of the mentoring relationship. As mentioned above, this links to the importance of a permissive learning environment that allows students the freedom and flexibility to develop at their own pace (Hilli *et al.*, 2014). This type of supportive learning environment values students' individuality and allows them to learn and make mistakes without fear of retribution.

The literature also suggests that mutual disclosure and trust underpin meaningful mentoring relationships (Sheehan *et al.*, 2021). Likewise, Hale and Phillips (2018) describe trust as the most important element of a successful mentoring relationship that intensifies as the relationship evolves. Trusting behaviours include being honest, accepting feedback and taking mentor guidance. In contrast, for mentors, this trust is often associated with non-judgemental behaviours. The concept of trust also appeared to be an essential element within the findings of this research and could be linked to constructive feedback. Here the students longed to seek meaningful, honest feedback; they perceived this feedback as an important measure of how they were doing but also as an opportunity to improve. At times they expressed their frustration when this feedback was lacking. Constructive feedback can facilitate both the student and mentor to develop future learning outcomes that can be linked to the learning opportunities available, thus creating pedagogical coherence (Mikkonen *et al.*, 2020). However, feedback that is perceived as criticism can be detrimental to the learning experience

(Eller, Lev and Feurer 2014). Therefore, mentors must find a balance in order to empower students to learn and grow. For example, it is critical that mentors emphasise the student's value and ability to change their behaviour, rather than simply pointing out what they have done wrong.

Trustworthiness cannot be taken for granted; alternatively, Hale and Phillips (2018) argue that trust develops and intensifies as the relationship grows. Consequently, for meaningful mentoring relationships to develop and thrive, time is required, yet student-mentor relationships are often time-limited, where the focus is on assessment and less on the development of effective interpersonal relationships (Hale, 2015). Within this study, the length of placement appeared to be a factor impacting on practice learning experiences, both in terms of developing meaningful relationships and seeking acceptance and belonging within the practice learning area. Lee *et al.* (2018) and Warne *et al.* (2010) established that student satisfaction with placement was increased during longer placement experiences where extended time in an area helped students develop interpersonal working relationships. Similarly, Levett-Jones and Lathlean (2009a) suggest that feeling comfortable within a placement can take up to four weeks. Therefore, placements greater than four weeks help engender belongingness as students can develop beyond the initial phase of settling in. However, within the wider literature, there was limited available evidence exploring the impact of shorter placement experiences.

Moreover, the concept of more extended placements presents practical challenges for both Higher Education and their practice partners due to an incremental increase in pre-registration nursing student numbers over the past ten years (Howarth, 2021). They are required to try and balance professional requirements, programme learning outcomes and placement capacity concerns. Yet, the literature would suggest regardless of the length of time on placement, if

environments are not welcoming or supportive, learning is not optimised (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2009a). As such, a longer placement does not necessarily guarantee the development of a positive student-mentor relationship. Alternatively, the evidence from this research study suggests that a positive relationship is symbiotic and strongly influenced by interpersonal dynamics.

Despite the students articulating their need for a strong student-mentor relationship, there appeared to be some contradictions expressed in their narrative recollections regarding their requirements. On the one hand, students discussed the need for constant direction, feedback, and organisation of learning opportunities akin to a dependent relationship on their mentor. Contrastingly, they also described striving for independence and longing for more autonomy when at times, they felt their learning was suffocated by overprotective mentors. This ambivalence is congruent with previous research (Thomson, Docherty and Duffy, 2017; Manninen, 2016; Ford *et al.*, 2016). The uncertainty the students were experiencing in this study could potentially be attributed to the transitioning role as they were in the final stages of their programme, where they were soon going to be registered practitioners. Manninen *et al.* (2016) identified how these feelings of uncertainty often manifest as self-centredness, where the students are focused solely on their own learning needs and what they believe they need to know as a registered nurse. Kram's 1983 seminal research exploring mentor relationships in the workplace describes this phase as separation where the mentee, in this case, the student, becomes more independent, striving for autonomy, outgrowing the current relationship. However, they caution that if separation is instigated too early, it can cause feelings of abandonment. This idea of abandonment perhaps helps to provide some insight into why ambiguity was experienced. The ambiguity students experienced also highlights the

importance of communication between the student and mentor to ensure all goals and learning outcomes are aligned. Therefore, those supporting students' learning needs to remain cognisant of the individual student learning needs, as these will inevitably differ depending on the students' previous practice learning experiences and development of knowledge and skills. In contrast, Saunders *et al.* (2016) interpretation suggests these feelings of abandonment are attributed to attachment behaviours. Shaped during early childhood, Bowlby's theory purports that attachment behaviours form the basis of relationships throughout an individual's life (Saunders *et al.*, 2016). In the context of practice learning, understanding that an attachment figure, in this case, the mentor, is accessible creates a sense of security for students. Hence if they perceive this support is lacking, feelings of abandonment can prevail. Whilst abandonment has been previously associated with more junior students on placement (Harrison – White, 2020), in this study, it appeared to resonate with final placement students and linked to their confidence as they progressed towards registration.

Previous literature exploring mentoring relationships identified that mentors often experience role confusion where the role of assessor was not perceived by mentors as a central component (Bray and Nettleton, 2007). Alternatively, the authors argued that mentors prioritised the pastoral, nurturing aspects of the mentoring relationship. This perspective was contrary to the findings of this study; whilst the pastoral role remained a dominant element, as discussed previously, the mentors appeared very aware of their professional responsibility in assessing the student's clinical practice. Assessment also appeared to be at the forefront of the student's relationship with their mentor. At times they described how they were somewhat reserved asking questions; they were cognisant that their mentor would be assessing them and did not want to appear unknowledgeable. By virtue of the mentor's role in

assessing the student's performance, these mentoring relationships can never be neutral, as ultimately, mentors will make the decision if a student can progress. Hilli *et al.* (2014) describe this as relationship asymmetry. Therefore, when exploring and understanding mentoring relationships, there must be consideration of the power dynamics. In particular, mentors need to be aware of the perceived hierarchy that comes with their role (Ewertsson *et al.*, 2017). For example, within this study, the power dynamics within the mentoring relationship would appear to be rooted within the process of assessment. Similarly, Harrison-White and Owens (2018) established how this imbalance creates a degree of vulnerability as mentors appear to have a dominant position. Therefore, mentors need to be cognisant of the perceived power and promote practices, such as self-reflection, in order to navigate any power differentials.

This study set out to explore practice learning experiences in order to interpret and understand the factors impacting on these experiences. It established that the student-mentor relationship was a crucial part of these experiences, but the findings also raised the question, who is responsible for nurturing this mentoring relationship? Mentors have previously been identified as being responsible for fostering effective mentorship relationships (Hale and Phillips, 2018). However, the findings from this study indicate that students also have a responsibility to invest in the relationship. As such, students need to be open and receptive to learning and also be invested in and willing to develop this complex interpersonal relationship. Several aspects of the student-mentor relationship resonate with the Wegner theory of communities of practice, for example mutual engagement refers to the active participation and interaction between members of a community of practice (Li *et al.*, 2009). Within the findings of this study, there were examples of this occurring when both the student and the mentor were actively and willingly collaborating in learning activities, discussions, and sharing

knowledge. The student's confidence and willingness to engage appeared to increase when their mentor had a genuine interest in the student and their learning needs. Moreover, it was through this process of mutual engagement that trusting relationships formed. Contrastingly, without this mutual engagement, barriers to participation appeared to emerge.

To summarise, from the findings, it was clear that the interpersonal relationship that developed between the student and mentor was central to practice learning experiences. The students in this study identified certain personal mentor characteristics that appeared to help develop meaningful relationships; qualities included being patient, kind and approachable. Indeed, mentor characteristics and qualities of an effective mentor have had prominence within the literature (Koontz *et al.*, 2010; Gidmen *et al.*, 2011; Vinales, 2015). However, not all relationships were perceived positively, and where there was a breakdown of the relationship, this could be detrimental. The findings provided some insight and understanding of how the mentoring relationship can evolve, in particular, the importance of the reciprocity that is required. However, it is also worth noting the available mentoring literature remains focused on the voluntary symbiotic relationship of a well-respected, more experienced individual guiding the professional development of a less experienced other (Moores, 2018). Yet, within pre-registration nurse education, neither the student nor mentor take up this role on a voluntary basis. Alternatively, they tend to be allocated to each other and have to quickly forge a relationship in order to support the students learning and assessment. Moreover, as Straus *et al.* (2013) argues, if mentoring goals are not aligned, or there are personality differences, these relationships may not always be fruitful, possibly explaining why within this study, these relationships were not always successful.

The Role of Others

Whilst the student-mentor relationship was acknowledged by all participants as being crucial in supporting students learning, there was an emerging consensus within the findings that other team members also made a significant contribution to practice learning experiences.

The findings recognised the contribution of medical staff; there were some specific examples provided by both the students and mentors of the inclusive approach to education, by medical staff, in terms of explaining procedures and practices to student nurses. Specifically, students shared their experiences of working with medical consultants who were particularly inclusive and appeared cognisant of the student's learning needs. They described examples where they took the time to provide explanations and sought the students out to include them in ward and teaching activities. According to Hood *et al.* (2014), interprofessional learning is an important aspect of preparing nurses to perform in an increasingly complicated work environment, where successful interprofessional teamwork is required to ensure safe and effective patient care. For the students in this study, it appeared to not only enhance their knowledge but provide them with a greater understanding of the different roles within the clinical environment. Moreover, this could be perceived as an example of joint enterprise where individuals within a community of practice have a shared common goal or purpose (Wenger, 1998). The findings of this study demonstrated the shared commitment of the community to support the students learning and the encouragement of person-centred care through multidisciplinary team working.

Whilst there were good examples of a multidisciplinary approach to student learning, the students in this study seemed to place a significant value on those interactions with consultant medical staff in comparison to all other staff. Here the students' perceptions appeared to demonstrate how they positioned their role in relation to the hierarchy within the ward area.

Whilst this finding should not devalue the collaborative approach to student learning, and the positive contribution medical staff can offer, anecdotally, it was interesting to note that the stereotypical preconceptions of healthcare hierarchy still exist. Whilst this finding has been noted elsewhere, Thurston (2017) warns that as student nurses develop their professional identity, the inherent stereotype casting, as was seen within this study, can impede future leadership roles if they perceive they have a subordinate position.

When exploring the contribution of healthcare support workers, the notion of professional hierarchy and positionality was also apparent. There were examples where the students were working alongside the healthcare support workers for extended periods of time, to the detriment of their learning. In addition, some students described tensions between themselves and the healthcare support workers, which appeared to be attributed to a misunderstanding of the students' role when on placement. These findings are not unique; within the practice learning environment, student nurses are often situated in the lowest hierarchical position (Lee *et al.*, 2018). As a result, negotiating learning opportunities can be challenging. Moreover, although students may be participating in the delivery of care alongside healthcare support workers, if they perceive learning opportunities are being compromised, they can feel marginalised (Harrison-White, 2020).

Despite some challenges encountered, this finding emphasises the collective, participative nature of practice learning, resonating with Wenger's perspective that communities of practice are collaborative social endeavours (Wenger, 1998). It was clear from the findings that students thrived within inclusive learning environments where all staff were invested in, and supported student learning.

The Student's Role

In terms of the student's role, within this study, participation appeared particularly important for the students as they strived to contribute and augment their position within the learning environment by actively contributing to the delivery of care and the ward routines. This finding is consistent with previous research (Connor, 2019) and is an example of legitimate peripheral participation. As discussed in chapter one, legitimate peripheral participation was first described in the literature by Lave and Wenger in 1991 in the development of their theory of situated learning. Their initial works defined situated learning as a process that evolves as a result of legitimate peripheral participation within communities of practice (Lave and Wenger, 1991). Here, they position learning within an authentic environment rooted in everyday culture, context and activity (O'Brien and Battisata, 2020; Connor, 2019). Moreover, Lave and Wenger (1991) described learning as a social process that is often unintentional, where learners' participation in the community incrementally increases. Central to this concept is the development of relationships and interactions between newcomers (students) and more knowledgeable others (old-timers) (Lave and Wenger, 1991). As students develop their knowledge and skills, their participation is gradually increased; it is through this trajectory that students move from participating within the periphery to becoming a central member of the community of practice (Connor, 2019).

As Molesworth (2017) illustrates, learning in the periphery can and should be perceived as a positive aspect of situated learning. It is here where student nurses are given access to the community, developing their knowledge and understanding through increasing involvement and participation and is a customary practice of group integration (Walsh, 2015).

However, within this study, there was a sense that the students were, at times, frustrated at being held within the periphery and wanted to contribute more as they appeared to aspire

towards a more central role. This finding is not surprising as the student participants in this study were at the end of their programme, and it highlights how they perceived they had moved from being newcomers to becoming a more experienced other. However, as mentioned earlier, within situated learning, participation is essential as it is through this process that identity and practices are enhanced and developed. As a result, if students are restricted from fully participating, this can be disempowering (Molesworth, 2017). A degree of non-participation is common at the outset of joining a new placement area, however, the level of participation is often dependant on a multitude of factors, including levels of engagement, access to opportunities and interpersonal dynamics (Thyrsoe *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, Wenger identified that there may be a number of barriers present that inhibit participation (Wenger, 1998). Nevertheless, they argue learning within a community of practice involves both participation and reification, where the interplay between these complimentary processes plays a significant role in shaping learning. As such, Morley (2016) proposes simple strategies aligned to reification that may counteract barriers. These include encouraging students to reflect on placement learning outcomes and their own personal development in order to strengthen participation and make learning more meaningful.

Manninen (2014) found that whilst final-year students wanted to become independent, they also wanted to be safe and continued to look to their supervisor for instruction. They attributed this uncertainty to the transition process whereby students became increasingly aware of the complexity of being a registered practitioner and the acknowledgement that they, too, will soon experience this reality. This suggests that there is a fine balance between working towards an independent role and being supported to do so. Therefore, those supporting learning need to be cognisant of this and ensure that the opportunities available address the student's individual development needs.

In terms of the student's role, the other participant groups highlighted the importance of the students' being self-directed and taking ownership of their own learning. Despite this, they recalled incidents when students appeared to be disengaged and lacked interest on placement. However, Kalyani, (2019) argues that the apparent lack of interest may, in fact, be a lack of confidence, suggesting that nursing students are uniquely vulnerable as they attempt to socialise within the profession and often have fears and anxiety related to their competence. Moreover, as the findings indicated, some students were exposed to explicit, negative bullying behaviours. Therefore, it is reasonable to suggest that these previous encounters may influence future interactions and again highlights students' vulnerable position within the practice learning environment.

The Role of Peers

The findings also draw attention to the importance and influence of peers; for the students, this was framed around the social interaction and collaboration with their fellow student nurses. Within the data, there was evidence of the strong bonds and friendships that formed between the student peers. There appeared to be a mutual appreciation that only fellow students could truly understand how they were feeling and what they were going through. This emerged even more so when faced with challenging or stressful situations and was cemented in the notion that their peers also faced similar scenarios. As mentioned previously, belongingness and acceptance have been identified as a prerequisite for a successful practice learning experience (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008). However, it is also acknowledged that practice learning experiences can be isolating as students struggle to navigate new placement areas and gain acceptance (Carey *et al.*, 2018). The findings suggest, that for students, interactions with their peers not only supported their emotional well-being but also helped

facilitate their transition into new areas. Moreover, from the student narratives, there was a clear element of trust and security that evolved from these relationships. For example, they identified their fellow students as being approachable and able to provide reassurance and guidance when they confided in them. Roberts (2008) explains that the relationships that students form are essential for emotional survival within the diverse realm of clinical practice. The findings from this study suggest that the cohesion and relationships that formed throughout their practice learning experiences are examples of the communities that formed between the students. As discussed previously describes, Wenger asserts that there are three domains (mutual engagement, joint enterprise and shared repertoire) that forge an effective community of practice (Wenger, 1998). In this study, there were clear examples of each.

- Mutual engagement – where students were interacting together, supporting each other professionally and emotionally on placement.
- Joint enterprise – students working collaboratively to provide patient care whilst on placement.
- Shared repertoire - helping new students settle into the area by sharing aspects of the ward routine and sharing 'how the ward runs'.

These examples emphasise the social participative nature of the practice learning environment where the students were learning together with their peers and supporting each other's understanding.

The peer communities of practice formed are not unusual, Carey's systematic review of peer learning within pre-registration nursing highlighted how student nurses often formed their own communities on placement as they developed relationships through mutual engagement and support (Carey, 2018), something that was mirrored within this study.

Interestingly, however, when the student participants discussed learning and working with their peers, the notion of comparison also emerged. Specifically, the students appeared to reflect on their placement allocations and experiences throughout the programme and compare this to other students. There was also an awareness and undercurrent of slight resentment of clinical skills acquisition and opportunities that had been provided to other students, especially if they had not been afforded that experience. This was particularly relevant in areas that had several students on placement simultaneously; whilst the students acknowledged having the emotional support of peers was beneficial, concurrently, they also recognised if there were too many students, this could be detrimental as learning opportunities could be viewed competitively. Walsh (2015) describes how student nurses frequently measure their own progress in comparison to their peers. They argue that this comparison can provide reassurance or motivation to further their efforts. Similarly, Stenberg and Carlson (2015) explain that competition can be positively linked with opportunities to enhance students' performance on placement as they use the comparison of fellow students as a trigger for their own individual improvement. The students in this study appeared to use their lack of comparative learning opportunities as a driver, identifying their eagerness to their mentors to ensure future involvement if the skills and opportunities arose.

The interactions with their peers also had additional advantages. The student participants identified how supporting more junior students with teaching and learning activities could be beneficial. Here their narrative recollections captured the increased confidence they experienced when sharing their knowledge. Although the students reported being initially nervous, through teaching and information sharing with their peers, they were able to consolidate their own learning and reflect on their personal growth, which resulted in increased self-esteem. This also emphasises the importance of reification, where the students

were able to take their own knowledge and experiences within the practice learning environment and make it explicit for others. This process of articulating and explaining clearly helped them consolidate their own learning and understanding. According to Wenger, reification is possible by 'projecting meanings' into the world and supports the learner to see that meaning has its own reality' (Wenger, 1998 p. 58). Moreover, as mentioned previously, reification works in duality with practice in order to negotiate meaning.

This personal growth and development discussed above is also congruent with Christenson and Bell's (2010) peer learning partnership initiative that piloted a model of peer learning and support for pre-registration nursing students. The findings of their qualitative study highlight the reciprocal benefits inherent within peer teaching, which for the senior students, could enhance their self-esteem in preparation for the completion of their programme of study. In this study, whilst the peer teaching and learning experiences were opportunistic and not formalised, the students still expressed personal gains in terms of enhancing their own understanding and confidence from these interactions. It is also another example of legitimate peripheral participation, where in this instance, the students took on the role of 'more experienced other' that guided learning through the sharing of their knowledge. This not only increased their self-confidence but appeared to cement their place and acceptance within the community. A more formalised approach to peer teaching and learning on placement can alleviate some of the challenges associated with new learners in practice, including anxiety and social isolation (Christiansen and Bell, 2010). Moreover, the reciprocal benefits for more senior students include personal growth, increased self-esteem and preparedness for the transition as a newly qualified nurse.

Communities of practice are often considered informal structures that evolve and include peer support and learning (Li *et al.*, 2009). Within this study, it was evident that the pre-registration

nursing students formed their own communities of practice whilst on placement, acknowledging how working collaboratively could be mutually beneficial. However, as can be seen from table 11, not all placement areas supported all years of nursing students. Therefore, opportunities to teach, learn and support other students are not consistent across all learning environments, somewhat limiting student opportunities to engage and interact with their peers.

The positive acknowledgement of peers in relation to practice learning experiences was also recognised by the mentor participants. The emotional support from their peers was valued, especially when students were failing their placement experience. There was a sense from the data that the mentors, on the whole, valued the advice and guidance of their peers, as exemplified by the case of Ailsa; as a new mentor, she appreciated the opportunity to discuss and debate learning opportunities with more experienced mentors and was not afraid to ask them for guidance.

Interestingly, Devlin and Duggan (2020), in their review of mentors' experiences, found that barriers to successful practice learning experiences included a lack of support from managers and peers. This, they identified, was to some extent related to a lack of equity as not all registered nurses supported student learning. However, they also attributed this to the lack of recognition in the role of mentor as there was no salary incentive or additional time afforded to undertake the mentor role. Similarly, Gray and Brown (2016) described how some nurse colleagues and managers failed to recognise the responsibility and effort required to support student learning in practice. These findings are in contrast with the present study; although the placement information (table 11) did acknowledge the potential for burnout due to a lack of mentors in some areas, the mentor participants in this study appeared to bear no resentment toward their other colleagues as they were cognisant of the staff turnover or

absences that attributed to the mentor shortage. Furthermore, there was an acknowledgement that their peers, even if they were not named mentors, still supported student learning, in turn supporting the mentor. This was particularly true of Tricia, who was a deputy charge nurse; having a more senior management role meant that she relied on her peers to jointly support the student's learning experiences. Moreover, throughout the interviews, the participants discussed the variety of collaborative mentorship models that were utilised to support student learning and counteract the rigid nature of mentorship provision as outlined by the NMC Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008). Previous research has evaluated the formal support available for mentors; this support has included liaison lecturers, practice education facilitators, and ward education coordinators (Clarke and Casey, 2016). Whilst this study did acknowledge the additional formal support available for mentors, it also highlighted that their fellow peers were well placed to provide guidance, especially when they were faced with making judgements and difficult decisions on a student's assessment. This is perhaps not surprising as mentors will interact with their fellow peers on a daily basis and inevitably turn to them for immediate support, yet within the literature, there appears to be a lack of research exploring this.

Within this study, the mentors, as a peer group, also formed their own community of practice; for example, their narrative accounts reflected on the conversations, advice and support they received from each other. Within a community of practice, this social interaction and collaboration between members to generate new knowledge and solve problems has been identified as an essential characteristic (Terry *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, communities of practice can often emerge organically (Wenger *et al.*, 2002), as was the case within this study, where they demonstrated a shared interest in the mentorship role and supporting student learning and development.

6.3 The Emotional Journey

The student participants all expressed a positive outlook towards their practice learning experiences; despite the challenges that were often encountered, they all recognised the value of experiential learning within the nursing curricula. In particular, students reflected on their placements and described their encounters as an intense emotional event where they experienced emotional ambivalence; for example, they described positive emotions related to the rewards of caring for patients and the development of effective working relationships; however, they also recalled contrasting emotions rooted within challenging interpersonal relationships and feelings of being overwhelmed.

Belongingness

Whilst the data illuminated a range of emotions expressed by the students, the findings of this study resonate with the findings within the literature review, where possessing a sense of belonging was a dominant finding. Belongingness is defined as the human emotional need to feel secure, accepted and valued within a social group that promotes a sense of connectedness (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008; Gilbert and Brown, 2015). Maslow's theory of human motivation suggests that individuals are driven by five basic needs: physiological, safety, love and belongingness, esteem, and self-actualisation (Hopper, 2021). He proposed a hierarchy of these needs, where lower needs must be achieved before an individual can progress to the next stage. Thus, purporting self-actualisation cannot be fully achieved if the proceeding needs, including belongingness, are not met (Bulut, Hisar and Demir, 2010).

In the context of pre-registration nursing education, belongingness has been explored in depth. Levett-Jones and Lathlean (2008) and Liljedahl *et al.* (2016) propose that the need to belong within the practice learning environment is a prerequisite for student success. Consequently, they suggest if a student is included and accepted, they can progress to the next

level and eventually reach the point of self-actualisation, or more specifically, professional actualisation, where they are able to successfully fulfil their role as a student nurse. Moreover, having a sense of belonging can be perceived as a precursor for a positive learning experience as students are more able to forge effective personal relationships (Houghton *et al.*, 2013). To some extent, this acceptance and its impact echo the findings from this study. When students felt they belonged, they demonstrated increased levels of confidence and self-esteem within their student role, as such, appeared to flourish and thrive within the practice learning environment.

In contrast, when students did not feel they fit in, the findings identified how negative emotions were elicited as students described feelings of uneasiness and anxiety. More worryingly, in some situations, the students were demoralised and appeared to disengage from the learning experiences. This finding aligns with previous research that suggests if belonging needs are not met, this can lead to feelings of stress, anxiety and diminished confidence, negatively impacting on the student's motivation to learn (Grobecer, 2016). Moreover, if acceptance does not exist, learning is not optimised as students remain preoccupied with developing interpersonal relationships (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008).

Conformity has been previously linked with the desired need to belong; it has been suggested that students often conform to poor practice in a quest to fit in. In particular, previous research identified that the students who were ignored were more likely to conform and not question poor care in an attempt to seek approval (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2009b).

Whilst conformity to this degree was not found within this study, for some students, the need for acceptance within the group could still come at a cost, where learning opportunities were missed as students opted to stay and help out in the busy ward environment. For example, Jenna described how she declined the opportunity to watch an autopsy as the ward area was

busy; alternatively, she opted to stay and help her mentor despite really wanting to go and participate. She reflected on the detrimental effect this had on the learning opportunities as she prioritised helping her mentor.

Whilst this could be perceived as altruistic, it demonstrates that, at times, the quest to earn acceptance and to be accepted can supersede the student's individual learning needs.

This study also recognised that despite all the student participants expressing a pervasive desire to belong, not having this acceptance did not mean that learning did not occur. In fact, students spoke of their learning and development in spite of this. Moreover, the negative attitudes and incivility experienced within this study could be viewed as beneficial with regards to the student's future development as they were quick to condemn these behaviours and express their desire not to emulate this. This is congruent with the findings from Felstead and Sringett (2016), who determined that poor experiences can also be influential as they can serve as a benchmark for learners identifying what not to do or how not to behave. Furthermore, when faced with challenging and excluding behaviours, the students in this study spoke of the strategies they used to overcome these, reinforcing the value of personal resilience and self-efficacy. In the context of Wenger's community of practice theory, the strategies the students used to overcome the challenging behaviours could also be considered examples of imagination and alignment. Within the findings of this study, it was clear that the students did not align with these professional behaviours and values and used the concept of imagination to determine how they would act differently when they became registered nurse.

As mentioned previously, Maslow's theory postulates that higher-order needs cannot be achieved if belongingness is not met (Maslow and Lewis, 1987). However, as pointed out by King-Hill, (2015), whilst humans inevitably have needs, a predefined hierarchy does not account for individualisation or recognition of cultural or societal variations. The findings within

this study, nevertheless, demonstrate how the students who were readily accepted, and included, appeared to thrive and reach their student potential; however, how belongingness was experienced differed throughout the student recollections. Despite this, all of the student participants were still able to achieve their placement learning outcomes and learn from their experiences, albeit at times within the periphery of the learning community.

The importance of creating that sense of belonging was also acknowledged by the manager and mentors as they described the inclusive approaches, they employed in order to make students feel welcomed. Arguably though, the findings highlight how their invitation and acceptance within the practice learning environment was conditional; for example, although the staff appeared inclusive and welcoming, they describe how they expected that the students came with a positive attitude, were motivated, and were prepared to learn. Moreover, this resonates with the work of Wenger, who emphasises the need for mutual engagement, where participants connect meaningfully in order for communities of practice to be successful (Wenger, 1998). Therefore, this supports the notion that students also have a role to play in the process of engendering acceptance within the practice learning environment.

The findings from this study do not dispute the importance of belonging; nevertheless, there would appear to be a disproportionate volume of literature describing belongingness where those within the practice learning community are viewed as gatekeepers, choosing whether or not to welcome newcomers, into the area and support their learning (King *et al.*, 2017). Alternatively, belongingness within the practice learning environment can and should be viewed as a reciprocal process between the environment and the individual where the relationship is interdependent (Liljedahl, 2016; Billett, 2004; 2016). Arguably, Billett (2004) suggests that students need to want to belong, and as such, belongingness should be regarded

as a mutual relationship. For example, how a student nurse chooses to engage within the learning environment is equally as important as how the environment chooses to welcome them.

Although this was not a longitudinal study, the participants were given the opportunity to reflect on a range of experiences (bound within the case) that included early career practice learning experiences. From the findings, it is interesting to note that it was in these early learning experiences that students highlighted a lack of acceptance and lack of belonging. One possible explanation is that the placement area did not align with their values, and the students chose not to belong in order that their personal values and beliefs were not compromised. This appeared particularly true of students who had no previous experience in health care as they seemed to initially struggle with the realities they encountered on placement. Students' perceptions and preconceived ideals of the nursing profession can, at times, present a dichotomy if their ideals do not align with the reality experienced (Maginnis 2018). However, through the process of professional socialisation, their understanding of the values, culture and behavioural norms of the profession evolve as they are exposed to a variety of placements. The findings from this study echo this perspective to some degree and would indicate as the student nurses progressed in their journey and formed their own professional identity, they began to understand or became more accepting of the knowledge, behaviours and norms of the nursing profession. This could explain why in their latter practice learning experiences, concerns regarding a lack of belongingness did not appear to be as prominent as the students were able to more readily adapt and fit in. Wegner (1998) explains that it is through this alignment that engagement is enhanced. Alignment specifically refers to the shared understanding and coherence within a community regarding the goals, values and practices (Smith, Hayes and Shea, 2017). Within the context of this study, student learning on placement

appeared to be augmented when the students were able to understand and align their practice to local and national policies and guidelines as they progressed in their programme of study. It also demonstrates the students' increased understanding of the hidden curriculum. Previous studies have suggested that the hidden curriculum contributes to students' learning of the social behaviours within the nursing profession that are not formally taught but are instrumental in the development of their own professional identity (Kelly, 2020).

The findings from this study also emphasised the unique culture within each placement area. The students recognised that each area had their own social construct, and as such, belongingness was not transferable; alternatively, when they moved placement area, the students had to start the process again of trying to fit in. This was also identified by Kern *et al.* (2014), who recognised the challenges faced by student nurses as each new placement was perceived as a new beginning where students had to begin the cycle of positioning themselves in order to gain acceptance. In this study, these challenges appeared to be exacerbated due to the number of short placement experiences, as all but one placement was less than seven weeks, where they felt they were just becoming embedded within a unit when it was time to move on.

In summary, the student participants all expressed a clear desire to belong and be accepted by the team, and this echoes earlier research (Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2008; Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016). Although challenges were encountered, particularly within early career placements, on the whole, the students' demonstrated resilience in establishing effective interpersonal relationships. Manager and mentor participants, whilst also recognising the importance of belonging, were clear to highlight the student's role within this, supporting the idea of belongingness being a reciprocal process.

Mentoring Matters.

This study sought to explore practice learning experiences from multiple perspectives; as such, the theme, the emotional journey, also featured within the mentors' accounts characterising their experiences.

There was an overwhelming sense that the process of mentorship and supporting students learning and development was viewed positively by the mentors. However, as with the student participants, mentors within this study experienced a range of emotions when exploring their involvement. The finding suggests that the mentors were motivated in their role and wanted to do a good job supporting student learning; nevertheless, at times, mentorship appeared to present additional emotional demands. As Schaffer (2013) explains, positive mentoring experiences can act as a buffer enhancing mentors' resilience, in contrast, as the findings from this study depict, the negative emotions experienced can result in feelings of guilt, anxiety and distress.

In particular, supporting students who were failing or required additional support appeared to elicit strong feelings of anxiety and distress. When presented with challenging situations, mentors spoke at length about the additional emotional burden. This was epitomised by one mentor's recollection as she spoke of the guilt she felt, which appeared to stay with her years later as the student never progressed to registration. These emotions seemed to emerge as mentors considered the consequences of their actions despite their moral integrity as they recognised failing the student was the correct course of action. Here the mentors appear to be describing the delicate balance between the accountability of their role and the nurturing pastoral role of supporting learners to develop.

The findings from the mentor participants resonate with previous studies regarding the challenges associated with supporting students in practice (Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy, 2017; Duffy, 2003). Arguably Duffy's (2003) seminal research exploring mentors' and liaison lecturers' experiences of failing to fail provides some understanding of the affective responses mentors experienced when making judgements to award a fail grade to students. They cited terms including 'horrendous, traumatic and draining' (pp., 38), indicating the increased distress associated with giving a fail grade. Moreover, mentors within their study appeared to associate these feelings with a personal failing as they were not able to support the student to reach their learner goals, highlighting the complexity of such situations in which the mentors would appear to be ill-prepared to deal with (Duffy 2003). The findings within this research study resonate with Duffy's conclusions. Whilst here, the mentors did not overtly state they felt emotionally unprepared; the language they used suggests otherwise. From the discussions, it emerged that the challenging situations experienced had a lasting emotional effect. Worryingly this would suggest that 20 years after Duffy's original research, when making difficult judgements on a student's performance, those involved, are not always equipped to deal with the emotional fallout of these decisions.

The concept of mentor fatigue also permeated the mentor discussions; in particular, this was associated with student allocations and mentor numbers and was also highlighted by the PEFs and ward manager. Supporting students' teaching, learning and assessment in practice inevitably comes with an increased workload (Rylance *et al.*, 2017). Yet not all nursing staff within placement areas are mentors and support this additional role, alluding to a potential imbalance in workload. The placement information in relation to mentor and sign-off mentor numbers (table 11) also supports this, demonstrating how, at the time of this study, there were inconsistencies in mentor numbers to support student learners within the identified practice

learning environments. This finding suggests that those who were able to support student nurse teaching, learning and assessment were relied upon more frequently, as not all registered nurses within the area supported student learning. Similar findings have been described by Devlin and Duggan (2020), who argue a fairer distribution is required in order to prevent mentor burnout and fatigue.

Although the mentors in this study described the challenges they encountered, they all embraced the positive aspects of supporting students and appeared to thrive in this role.

The intrinsic rewards associated with mentoring have been previously recognised (Macey, Green and Jardin, 2021), where the personal satisfaction and self-fulfilment of helping and nurturing a mentee's growth and development were identified as a reward of the mentoring role. Likewise, in this study, the mentors articulated a variety of personal benefits aligned with their role and spoke of the emotional rewards of supporting another's learning. Here 'paying it forward' and passing their knowledge on to the future generation of nurses appeared to be important as the mentors wanted to ensure high standards of care were set and maintained.

The mentors in this study also described how the students often came with a fresh outlook and helped them keep up to date with the latest evidenced based practice. As Bowen, Kables and Keatringe (2019) describe, supporting learners can enhance mentors' own practice as students can bring new ideas related to contemporary practice, thus emphasising the dynamic nature of knowledge. Indeed, Wenger (1998) argues within a community of practice, this interaction between old-timers and newcomers is pivotal in order to generate new knowledge. This was exemplified within the findings of this study as the students shared ideas and questioned current practices, further demonstrating the reciprocity and mutually beneficial elements of this relationship.

Emotional Highs and Lows of Being a Student Nurse.

As mentioned in section 6.1 above, the student participants' descriptions of their practice learning experiences were emotionally evocative. Beyond the emotional need to belong, several other emotions were identified within the findings; in particular, the students spoke about feeling anxious, overwhelmed, frustrated and stressed whilst in practice. This demonstrates how the practice learning environment can elicit a range of emotions. However, it would appear this finding is not unique, as the practical curriculum has been consistently recognised as a source of intense emotions (Kalyani *et al.*, 2020). Understanding how to regulate these emotions is a key part of the professional socialisation of nursing students. Without this, they can feel unwanted, overwhelmed, become stressed and lacking in confidence, in turn, this can lead to disengagement and inhibit learning (McCloughen *et al.*, 2020).

There is also some suggestion that specific student groups entering the profession are particularly vulnerable to the emotional demands of the role; for example, Stephens (2013) highlights that school leavers are less likely to be able to manage their emotions due to their lack of life experience dealing with stress and conflict. They suggest that these students may not be prepared for the emotional demands of the nursing curriculum, which includes caring for patients as well as coping with the potentially challenging dynamic within staff interaction. Within this study, it was also found that there were differences in student resilience, partly due to emotional intelligence and their ability to regulate their emotions. However, on the whole, when faced with difficult emotional situations, the students demonstrated resilient qualities and were able to acknowledge that learning could, and did, still occur.

Resilience can be defined as the ability to adapt when presented with challenging situations or when faced with adversity (Delgado *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, by virtue, this suggests strengthening student nurses' ability to develop resilience will help reduce negative stress, burnout and compassion fatigue. Reyes *et al.* (2015) echo this describing how resilience is a crucial element in how student nurses successfully adapt to burdensome experiences on an ongoing basis. Over time, through the accumulation of placement experiences, nursing students' resilience can be enhanced as they learn how to adapt and regulate their emotions (Lopez *et al.*, 2018). As they develop their ability to draw upon their individual protective factors, this equips them to deal with future adverse or emotionally demanding events (Stephens, 2013). Consequently, the cumulative accomplishment of dealing with these experiences through the passage of time results in increased resilience (Thomas and Revell, 2016). However, not all student nurses develop positive coping strategies; there were examples within the literature where maladaptive coping behaviours were adopted, such as increased alcohol consumption, in order to cope with the stress faced during clinical placement (Galvin *et al.*, 2015).

Within this research study, there were no examples discussed of any maladaptive behaviours. Alternatively, resilience and the emotional impact of practice learning experiences emerged as a key finding. For instance, student participants were nearing the end of their training programme and had inevitably encountered and dealt with a variety of emotions whilst on placement. Within their recollections, they described how, throughout the duration of their placement experiences, they drew upon both individual and sociocultural protective factors. The stage of their nurse education and previous placement experiences possibly explain why they demonstrated strong, resilient characteristics.

Lopez *et al.* (2018) reported that student nurses who experience unsupportive learning environments build resilience by using two key coping strategies: positive reframing and seeking support from their peers. Indeed, these findings were mirrored within this study. The concept of positive reframing can be understood in terms of how a person reflects positively on a challenging experience (Lopez *et al.*, 2018). Similarly, O'Mara *et al.* (2014) reported that student nurses responded to confronting situations by retrospectively reframing and tapping into their resilience. This positive adaptation and reframing can foster a student nurse's growth and development (Amsrud, Lyberg and Severinsson, 2019). Delgado *et al.* (2017) echo this, describing how, when faced with burdensome experiences, through the process of reflection, student nurses can adapt and learn; therefore, reframing can be perceived as a protective factor. This also draws parallels with Wenger's community of practice theory resonating with the concept of imagination (Wenger, 1998). Here the students were able to consider different possibilities and reflect on how this could influence their future practice. Likewise, Grealish and Ranse (2009) also established how student nurses used imagination to create alternative responses when faced with challenging situations.

Within this study, the notion of positive reframing and imagination was seen throughout the student responses as a coping mechanism as the students demonstrated growth and personal development when faced with adversity. There were examples where students were making complex interpretations of their challenging experiences. For example, they tried to reflect on why someone had acted in a particular way taking cognisance of external factors that could have influenced this. Through this reflection, they were able to successfully manage their emotions and were able to adapt and negotiate similar experiences. This aligns with Reyes's (2015) constructivist grounded theory of resilience and enactment; their research suggests that resilience is a process as opposed to a personal trait and describes resilience as a dynamic,

iterative process where transformation and growth can occur. Likewise, Stephens (2013) perceived resilience as a learned action; therefore, this would suggest that nursing students can be taught how to effectively use existing protective factors, or develop others, in order to enhance their ability to cope.

In this study, seeking support from peers complimented positive reframing. Indeed, effective social support has been recognised as a prerequisite for enhanced student resilience, where peers, friends, family and educational staff can help to manage emotional situations (Thomas and Revell 2016). In particular, peers can be considered an invaluable resource as they provide an opportunity for sharing and discussion (Lopez *et al.*, 2018). This resonates with the findings from this study, where peer support was a mechanism that students used as a coping strategy. Here the use of dialogue allowed students to engage in meaningful interactions with their peers as they tried to make sense of challenging or confronting situations in order to learn from and build on their experiences. Through this process, their peers were able to provide reassurance and affirmation. Lopez *et al.* (2018) describe this as emotional, social support, where students attempt to resolve negative feelings through problem-solving and reflection with others. In doing so, they assert, this helps to enhance their ability to cope. Consequently, in this study, the students perceived that their peers were able to fully understand the emotions encountered within the practice learning environment as they attempted to construct their resilience through this informal debriefing strategy.

Support from educational staff has also been recognised as a crucial element in enhancing resilience, in particular, when students are faced with adversity (Reyes *et al.*, 2015). However, this is in contrast with Stephens (2013), who reported that faculty members were not considered by students to be an effective source of support, as their supportive presence and engagement were lacking. This perspective echoes the current findings, where students

acknowledged a lack of clarity regarding the liaison lecturer's role and appeared confused as to who they could turn to when challenging situations arose. This incongruence and inconsistency do not appear limited to the current study. In MacIntosh's (2015) research, they described how some students found speaking with their liaison lecturer to be cathartic, particularly when feeling anxious, yet an inconsistent approach to this supportive measure meant that most students were self-reliant and found other ways to cope.

Although the students within this study described the coping strategies they used when faced with emotionally demanding situations, these appeared to be impromptu with limited theoretical underpinning or a consistent, purposeful approach.

Interestingly, all student participants identified the value of the focus group in this research study as it gave them an opportunity to critically reflect on their experiences with their peers, which they argued was not routinely offered to them. This suggests that the level of critical reflection and formal debriefing was missing within their undergraduate programme. Debriefing has been widely used within experiential learning and is most commonly associated with simulated practice (McCloughen *et al.*, 2020; Fisher and Oudshoorn, 2019). However, it can be a useful tool to support student nurses' practice learning experiences as it enables them to work through and master anxiety-provoking situations as they develop strategies to enhance their ability to manage future challenging encounters (McCloughen *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, the guided exploration of students' emotional management can help increase their understanding of these experiences.

To conclude, the students in this study demonstrated aspects of reification, alignment and imagination aligned to Wenger's community of practice theory in response to the barriers associated with non-participation and a lack of belongingness. Moreover, the data from this study and previous research would suggest that, at times, all nursing students are susceptible

to perceived periods of stress and adversity (Stephens, 2013); therefore, it is essential that resilience is fostered.

6.4 The Future Nurse Standards

At the outset of this research, there was an awareness that the NMC were reviewing the 2008 Standards to support learning and assessment in practice. However, although there had been indications that the current provision of mentorship may change, practice learning would remain a central component of pre-registration nurse education. After discussions with the supervisory team, it was agreed that the research project should continue as planned for the following reasons. Firstly, the aim of this study was always to explore practice learning experiences and not mentorship per se. As such, even with the introduction of the new standards, student nurses would still be undertaking practice learning experiences and requiring support and assessment on placement. Therefore, how these experiences were perceived and understood could still inform future practice. Secondly, the publication of this study could be a timely addition to the ongoing discourse surrounding pre-registration nurse education and, as such, support or refute the proposed changes to mentorship provision by providing a rich insight into practice learning from multiple perspectives.

In 2018 the future nurse standards for pre-registration nurse education were published; part two, student supervision and assessment, outlines the changes to how pre-registration nursing students are supported within clinical practice (NMC, 2018a). It has long been recognised that mentors play a crucial role in supporting students learning and development in practice (Rylance *et al.*, 2017); however, the previous Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008) were widely criticised and often described as being overly restrictive and

prescriptive in terms of how this mentorship provision was implemented (Leigh and Roberts, 2018). For example, mentors were expected to spend 40% of a placement experience with the student engaged in teaching, learning and assessment activities and had to complete an approved HEI mentorship programme prior to undertaking this role (NMC, 2008). In contrast, the new standards for student supervision and assessment adjust the focus of student teaching, learning and assessment where it is no longer solely the responsibility of the mentor. Alternatively, three new roles have been introduced, practice supervisor, practice assessor and academic assessor (NMC, 2018a) driving a more collaborative approach to pre-registration supervision and assessment in practice. These new roles are briefly discussed below and presented in the context of the findings from this study.

Practice Supervisor.

Where previously only a registered mentor was able to support student learning and assessment, the new standards recognise that all registered nurses are able to fulfil the role of practice supervisor (Duffy and Gillies, 2018). Moreover, the new standards appear to strengthen and recognise the contribution of the wider health team as they state 'students may be supervised by other registered health and social care professionals' (NMC, 2018a pp. 6), therefore affording the students the opportunity to learn from a variety of roles and participating within interprofessional learning. This new model, where the contribution from the wider team is encouraged, resonates with the findings from this study, where students valued working with diverse members of the multidisciplinary team and other registered nursing staff, providing a wider network of support to enhance their learning. Furthermore, as alluded to within the placement area information (table 11), having more staff willing and able to support student learning, rather than only the mentor as was previously, may alleviate the

pressure on the existing mentor population, thus mitigating the notion of mentor fatigue and burnout.

Practice Assessor

One of the key changes within the new NMC standards is the development of clear boundaries between the roles of supervision and assessment, where those supporting student learning cannot simultaneously assess the student's practice (Leigh and Roberts, 2018). This creates a clear distinction between the role of assessor and supervisor; however, integral to the effectiveness of this approach is good communication channels between the practice supervisor and practice assessor to ensure they can make an informed, evidence-based, robust assessment of the student's performance. The decoupling of the two roles would appear to align with the findings of this study. From the students' perspective, they were continually aware that their mentor would be assessing them and, at times, did not want to ask questions related to their learning for fear of appearing unknowledgeable.

Moreover, the students often looked to their mentor as the person solely responsible for their learning. However, this new approach would appear to encourage the students to take ownership of their learning through working with a variety of individuals.

Academic assessor

The academic assessor is required to work in partnership with the practice assessor in order to assess and make judgments on the student's progression (NMC, 2018a). This new role appears to strengthen and formalise the collaboration between the practice areas and the HEIs. Here academic assessors will make decisions on students' progression by reviewing evidence from a variety of sources that may include practice assessment documentation, coursework and communications with the practice assessor (Drayton and Edmonds, 2020). A perceived benefit of this role is the shared decision and support this offers, especially when making judgments

on students who are underperforming (Drayton and Edmunds, 2020). There was evidence of the lasting emotional impact mentors faced when confronted with challenging situations, such as students failing their placement. Therefore, this joint approach may offer some reassurance and be less isolating for those staff making these decisions.

It is interesting to note that the findings from this research would appear to suggest that collaboration between HEIs and practice already exists and functions well for those supporting learning. However, students, when in practice, were not always aware of this and who they could turn to for support. Moreover, the new standards do not appear to address this.

To summarise, the introduction of these new standards heralds a cultural shift in relation to student teaching, learning and assessment in practice as practice learning environments and higher education institutions develop new ways of working. The standards encourage a degree of flexibility, innovation and creativity as to how they are implemented and appear to be a welcomed approach that supports practice learning within increasingly complex healthcare settings (Pearson and Wallymahmed, 2020). However, whilst many of the changes resonate with the findings of this study, as with any significant change to policy or practice, ongoing evaluation and research is required to ensure practice learning experiences remain positive and the future nursing workforce are adequately supported to develop the knowledge and skills required.

6. Chapter Conclusion

This chapter presented a discussion of the research findings. The two themes and seven subthemes were critically explored, drawing upon the existing literature in order to explore, interpret and contextualise the findings. The chapter concluded with an exploration of the

current NMC Future Nurse Standards (NMC, 2018a) and how these relate to the findings of this study.

Chapter 7 Moving Forward.

7.1 Introduction to Chapter

This chapter concludes the thesis. Firstly, it explores how the study has addressed the research aim and objectives. Secondly, it presents reflections on the research process, including the strengths and limitations. Implications of the research findings on practice and policy are then discussed, including the recommendations. Finally, this chapter concludes with a personal reflection on this research journey.

7.2 How This Study Answered the Aim and Objectives.

The aim of this study is to explore pre-registration nursing student practice learning experiences in order to identify and interpret what contributes to, or inhibits, practice learning experiences.

The following objectives helped frame and guide the study:

- to develop an understanding of what influences pre-registration student nurses' practice learning experiences.
- To explore the perspectives of mentors, managers, practice education facilitators and liaison lecturers about practice learning experiences.
- To interpret the contextual factors related to pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences.

As discussed previously, there is an extensive amount of existing literature exploring practice learning experiences from the student perspective, less so exploring mentors' perspectives. However, this research offers a degree of originality, as it has moved beyond mentors and students and explored the topic from multiple perspectives. As described in chapter 4, the inclusiveness of involving a range of participants (pre-registration nursing students, mentors, practice education facilitators, liaison lecturers and a ward manager) facilitated the collection of rich data from the practice learning environment. Importantly, it enabled interaction and engagement with all the participant groups and allowed their voices to be heard.

Within the context of the practice learning environment, several key aspects were identified as impacting upon practice learning experiences. Undoubtedly, the relationship that developed between the mentor and student was one of the most crucial elements recognised by all participant groups; as such, the development of this interpersonal relationship generated the most discussion within the narrative recollections. Students valued mentors that were supportive of their learning needs, were good role models and were inclusive in their approach to teaching and learning where they encouraged the student's involvement. However, what this study adds to the understanding of practice learning experiences, is the reciprocity that is required for the relationship to flourish. Mentors expected students to be motivated, proactive, interested, enthusiastic and take responsibility for their learning, highlighting the mutual accountability required for successful practice learning experiences.

In addition, the workplace experiential learning that student nurses participated in offered them an opportunity to engage with and learn from a variety of different people, including other healthcare professionals and their peers. In particular, students appeared to thrive when they felt included and were able to actively participate within the teams.

This study also highlighted the lack of consistency within mentorship provision and the impact that this had on mentors' willingness and enthusiasm to support ongoing student learning. In some areas, the lack of qualified mentors appeared to place additional pressure on those fulfilling the role. This was substantiated within the placement information that outlined this lack of consistency across practice learning environments.

The findings from this study brought to the forefront a range of emotions that were experienced in practice. For both students and those supporting learning, the emotional highs and lows of these experiences appeared to have a lingering effect. Whilst within their recollections, students, described strategies that helped develop their resilience, formalised support, or approaches to this appeared to be lacking. This was also mirrored within the mentors' recollections, especially when dealing with students who required extensive additional support or failed their placement experience. The emotional fallout appeared to last long after the situation had passed, suggesting that existing strategies to offer support and reflection may have been lacking.

Finally, belongingness and the emotional impact of these feelings was a dominant finding within this study. As discussed previously within the literature, belongingness would appear to be a prerequisite for successful/fruitful practice learning experiences (Liljedahl *et al.*, 2016). However, it was clear that although strategies could be implemented to engender belongingness, students had to want to belong; this appeared particularly relevant in relation to early practice learning experiences where pre-conceived ideals of the profession were not aligned with the reality they experienced.

7.3 Reflections on the Strengths and Limitations of the Research Process.

7.3.1 Strengths

This research was a small-scale study carried out in a local hospital; as such, the findings cannot be generalised; however, the findings may be transferable across other practice learning contexts. Whilst the uniqueness of the context of this study should be acknowledged, the findings are consistent with similar studies (Thomson, Docherty and Duffy, 2017; Cassidy, Coffey and Murphy, 2017; Walsh, 2015). Furthermore, as defined by Yin (2018), this case study was a common case that offered a rich, thick description of the context, allowing the reader to make judgements as to how the findings can be applied or transferred to other areas of similarity (Bryman, 2012).

This dissertation provided an in-depth exploration of practice learning experiences and adds to the existing body of knowledge around the complexity of these experiences and how they are understood. As mentioned above, a strength of this research and its unique contribution is offered through the study population sample. The use of multiple participants allowed the area of study to be explored holistically, presenting a range of perspectives. Moreover, bound within the context of the study, the participants were ideally placed to offer their insights; for example, the students had experienced a range of placements, whilst the other participant groups all had experience supporting students learning in practice.

The use of multiple varied data collection methods could also be considered a strength of this study. Multiple data sources allowed an in-depth exploration that was able to contextualise the findings and offer triangulation of the data. In this study, placement information, focus groups and interviews were converged to corroborate the findings.

Another strength of this study could be considered the timing. With the introduction of the new standards to support student supervision and assessment (NMC, 2018a), the timeous

nature of the findings and recommendations offers an insight that adds to the discourse as these new standards become embedded within practice.

7.3.2 Limitations

As a lecturer, liaison lecturer, mentorship site lead and former employee of the NHS board, the researcher was known to most of the participants; as such, this relationship could have potentially introduced bias. As Fleming (2018) describes, what participants disclose may well be influenced by how the researcher is perceived. This was mitigated throughout the research process, where assurances of confidentiality and anonymity were provided. Moreover, to address any potential power imbalances, all students were informed that participation would have no bearing on any future grades or assignments. Nevertheless, it must be recognised that the relationship with the participants may have influenced how they responded. However, Fleming (2018) also argues that familiarity can be beneficial to the research as participants feel comfortable to share and explore their feelings, thus generating a rich source of data. This was particularly true of the focus groups, where they appeared to value the cathartic nature of discussing their practice learning experiences in a safe, non-judgmental space, acknowledging this within the focus group interviews.

The year three lecturers who initially introduced the study were also known to the student participants. The lecturers were given specific information to share and encouraged to direct any questions to myself as the researcher. Students were again assured that any participation was voluntary. However, despite these measures, it must be acknowledged that there was a risk that the students might have felt coerced into participating.

By virtue of their interest in participating in the study, it could be assumed that the mentors were already proactively interested in supporting student learning; thus, their positive outlook on the mentorship process may be reflected in their discussions.

In terms of recruitment, despite several ward managers expressing an interest in the study, only one manager responded to the invitation to attend; therefore, this could be considered a limitation of the study.

The findings have highlighted the holistic nature of practice learning where other registered nurses (who were not mentors), medical staff and health care support workers all impacted on practice learning experiences yet were not included within the study participant groups. As such, it should be acknowledged that including these groups may have offered a wider understanding of how practice learning experiences were perceived.

Only third-year students were invited to participate, the rationale for this being that the researcher did not teach or mark into year three. Therefore, only including this year group attempted to mitigate any coercion or power imbalance that may have been perceived. However, students from varying stages in their programme will attend these practice learning experiences. By only including third-year students, this might have limited the understanding as students will inevitably have different practice learning needs throughout their programme of study. Although the students in this study did reflect on all their experiences, their stage of the programme, as they moved towards being a registered practitioner, may well have influenced how they perceived these practice learning experiences.

Finally, the boundaries of the case study and the participants recruited could be considered a further limitation. As described in chapter 4, the boundaries of the case were in accordance with Yin's description of a typical case (Yin, 2018); here, a typical case study design is used to explore a common situation to provide an in-depth understanding. As such, the participants were recruited from one hospital and one university campus. Whilst rich data was retrieved, it should be acknowledged that practice learning experiences can and do take place within a variety of different health and social care settings. Although some of the findings may be transferrable due to the similarities, including a range of placement experiences out with secondary health care environments may have offered a different perspective. In addition, widening the scope of participants to involve other universities and/or other health board areas may have broadened the scope of perceptions offering alternative insights. Moreover, only adult pre-registration nursing students were included within the sample, which could also be perceived as a limitation; involving other disciplines might offer a different understanding.

7.4 Implications for Practice.

This research has made a positive contribution to the understanding of how practice learning experiences are perceived; the quotes throughout the dissertation provided evidence of the complexity of practice learning and demonstrated that these experiences were both emotionally evocative and influenced by many individuals. This supports the notion that practice learning should be viewed as a collaborative experience. Practice learning remains a central component of pre-registration nurse education; as such, the findings of this study have contributed to the ongoing debate as it highlighted examples of both positive and negative experiences. On the whole, practice learning experiences were perceived positively, where participants appeared to value a collegiate approach to supporting student learning. However, it also provided examples of experiences that were less than favourable, where the lasting

emotional impact was evident. In particular, those first practice learning experiences appeared to have a profound effect. For some students, their expectations did not match what they experienced. A number of findings highlighted how student nurses are supported and the preparation they require prior to their practice learning experiences. Therefore, valuable lessons can be taken from the findings to enhance and support future experiences.

This study methodology and the underpinning theoretical framework recognise that each individual participant will construct their own meaning and understanding of their experiences; however, the commonalities identified from the findings tentatively highlight implications that could be considered for future practice and are presented below.

7.4.1 Pre-registration Nursing Students

As mentioned above, this study acknowledged how practice learning experiences can be emotionally challenging for students for a variety of reasons. Therefore, students should be supported to develop and enhance their resilience and emotional wellbeing. This suggests that opportunities to develop coping strategies need to be more explicit and embedded within nursing programmes; this will not only enhance their ability to adapt and cope within practice but also equip them for the emotionally challenging demands they will inevitably face throughout their career.

7.4.2 The Ideal Context for Practice Learning.

Optimal practice learning environments were recognised as being inclusive and supportive. Such environments adopted a culture that embraced learning and valued students' contributions. 'Everybody's student' was the poignant phrase by one student participant that captured the positive learning culture that was exemplified by the whole team's interest in their learning journey. Therefore, practice learning environments need to consider how this

culture can be fostered in a more consistent manner. Moreover, practice areas need to be cognisant of students' emotional needs and promote simple welcoming behaviours that acknowledge the student as an individual. Simple things, such as being prepared for a student's arrival, having a plan for their learning and support and using their name (rather than referring to them as the student) can support the development of belongingness throughout their practice learning experiences.

7.4.3 Reciprocity

This notion of mutual responsibility was key within the findings of this study. As highlighted within the discussion, much of the discourse surrounding practice learning experiences has focused on those supporting learning being solely responsible for ensuring the learning relationship flourishes. In contrast, this study highlighted the mutually beneficial elements of this relationship and the reciprocity required to enable this relationship to flourish. For example, the importance of students taking ownership of their own learning; this autonomy should be at the forefront of placement experiences and be encouraged, in incremental stages, from the outset to promote self-directed behaviours. In practice, this can be achieved by seeking out relevant learning opportunities and learning from a variety of different team members, fostering a culture of multidisciplinary learning. Moreover, practice areas need to be aware of students' emotional needs and consistently promote welcoming behaviours.

7.5 Implications for Policy.

As mentioned previously, at the outset of this research, there was an awareness that the NMC were reviewing the 2008, Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice. Throughout this thesis, the term mentorship is continually used as, at the time of the data

collection, those supporting nursing students teaching, learning and assessment in practice were referred to as mentors (NMC, 2008). In 2018 the NMC launched the Standards for student supervision and assessment, which were implemented in 2019. Reflecting on the introduction of these new standards, the recommendations from this research study will be presented in the context of the latest roles using practice supervisor, practice assessor and academic assessor terminology.

7.6 Recommendations

7.6.1 Further Research Recommendations

This study was not longitudinal, albeit the students did reflect on a variety of practice learning experiences throughout their pre-registration nurse education. However, it would be useful to conduct a longitudinal study that looked to compare practice learning experiences across the programme to determine how these experiences evolve throughout the duration of the program of study.

In addition, as mentioned within the limitations, only third-year students were invited to participate and share their experiences. However, it may be useful to conduct further research exploring all year groups to determine if there are any differences in these experiences.

In light of the themes that arose, it was clear that a range of people within the practice learning environment impacted on these experiences; whilst most were represented within this study, the participant invitations did not include medical staff or health care support workers. It was evident from the findings that these staff members had a valuable contribution to student practice learning experiences. Therefore, it would be beneficial to explore their contribution within future research to understand their perceived role in supporting pre-registration nursing students' practice learning experiences.

Alternative research methods may have offered a different insight or enhanced understanding of practice learning experiences. Whilst this research never set out to produce generalisable findings, the findings offer some interesting insights into how practice learning experiences are perceived. However, a larger scale study using alternative methods such as a survey or psycho-social assessment tool may provide further evidence to enhance the understanding of experiences within the practice learning environment.

7.6.2 Recommendations for Future Practice

Through analysis and interpretation of the findings, some recommendations for future practice have arisen that should be considered. A key finding of this study was the lasting emotional impact practice learning experiences can have on individuals.

From a pre-registration nursing student perspective, in order to develop and enhance their emotional resilience, several strategies are recommended for consideration.

- Routine debriefing sessions are integrated within programmes of study where students are encouraged to critically reflect on the learning from these practice learning experiences.
- A structured approach to preparation for practice should be developed for students prior to commencing their practice learning experiences. Ideally, this should be supported by practice partners where there is an opportunity to discuss what to expect when on placement, including expectations of the student learners. Acknowledging the impact of the first placement experiences, these early placement experiences should be the initial focus of preparation for practice sessions. However, it should be recommended that preparation for practice is integrated consistently throughout the

various stages of the programme; this will enable learners to explore the different learning experiences and outcomes expected from practice learning depending on their stage of the programme.

- HEIs to develop a placement aide memoir or app to support students when out in practice. This should include clear instructions to clarify what is required and expected of students before, during and after practice learning experiences to support their learning. In addition, this should include details/links where to access support (University wellbeing, staff care etc.), how to raise concerns and whom to contact if additional support is required.

In the development of the strategies and interventions outlined above, it is further recommended that consideration is given to co-production. Brook *et al.*, (2020) explain how working collaboratively with key participants can result in the development of interventions that are more appropriate, pragmatic and relevant. Moreover, co-production can enhance the integrity of new developments as it values stakeholder expertise where they can draw on their previous experiences. In relation to the findings of this study and the resulting recommendations, through co-production, priorities may be identified which could strengthen the effectiveness of future interventions.

To support practice supervisors' and practice assessors' emotional well-being, peer support networks and facilitated reflective sessions should be encouraged. This could be supported within the practice education networks and HEIs. Moreover, examples of good practice and innovative approaches to supporting students learning in practice should be celebrated.

Clear communication links between those supporting students in practice (the practice supervisor and practice assessor) and the academic assessor need to be embedded as these new roles evolve. Here different methods of communication should be promoted to ensure decisions around students' progression are made in partnership, strengthening and formalising collaborative working relationships.

The other key finding of this study was centred around the aspect of teamwork, where everyone had an important role to play in supporting pre-registration student nurses learning. Given the contribution of the multidisciplinary team upon students' practice learning experiences, the following recommendations should be considered.

- How interprofessional learning could be enhanced within pre-registration nursing programmes should be explored, particularly within the practice component where placement areas can be supported to maximise the value of multidisciplinary learning opportunities.
- As the study highlighted, students will inevitably spend time with a variety of health care staff, not just their practice supervisor and practice assessor. To enhance student practice learning experiences and ensure they are supported to meet the learning outcomes these staff members need to have a good understanding of the student's programme. Therefore, wider dissemination of information on the nursing programmes and the role of the student nurse within the practice learning environment is required.

Finally, recognising the contribution and the positive impact that peers have on nursing students' practice learning experiences, strategies for enhancing peer learning and peer support should be considered. This could include collaborative learning in practice models (CLiP), where the focus is on peer learning and collaboration to deliver patient care under the

guidance of a coach (Hill, Woodward and Arthur, 2020). In addition, peer-assisted teaching and learning could also be embedded within the curriculum, where more experienced students can share their experience of practice with novice nursing students in their preparation for placement.

7.7 Personal Reflections on my Research Journey.

Prior to starting my professional doctorate, I remember hearing accounts of how challenging the process was, but I don't think anything could have prepared me for what lay ahead. I feel this journey has changed me in ways I could never have imagined; it has been both challenging and rewarding in equal measure.

Throughout this research process, I had to make several changes, some driven by external influences that I had no control over. Although this thesis is presented in a relatively traditional linear trajectory, as changes happened, there was a lot of movement back and forth, revisiting chapters to ensure there was alignment.

One of the biggest obstacles I faced during my research journey was choosing an appropriate methodology; at the outset, I knew what I wanted to explore, but I remember feeling frustrated at having to change my initial planned research approach. It was only as I intensively explored the concept of participatory action research and realised that it was not feasible for this study that I began to look at alternative methods that would still explore the topic and give the participant groups a voice but be achievable. I realise now that this was all part of my research journey. I have to give credit to my supervisors as they gave me the space and freedom to come to a conclusion on my own (despite suggesting this to me several meetings earlier). I believe this reflects my initial naivety of what was realistic or achievable and my lack of

understanding concerning the underpinning research philosophies that would be appropriate to use. My advice to future doctoral candidates would be - don't be restrictive in your thinking, be open to changes and exploring alternative ideas.

As an early career researcher, at times, I felt very overwhelmed. This was particularly true during the analysis stage. I felt exasperated as I had been looking forward to exploring the data; however, with so much, I struggled where to start and how to make sense of it all, and, more importantly, the time this would take. The notion of time was a recurrent theme throughout my journey, and the understanding that I needed to afford myself the time to plan and prepare. In recognition of this, I took myself away from my family to a cottage in the Scottish Highlands to get focused and get some clear headspace without distractions. However, like all good plans, I had to adapt and come home early due to the escalation of an evolving global pandemic. As the data collection took place prior to the pandemic, I have tried to keep CoVid 19 out of my story. However, looking back now, I wonder if my feelings of being overwhelmed were partly related to what was going on out with. Inevitably trying to write a thesis during two years of lockdowns presented challenges. Yet, it also served as a form of escapism where I could focus on my study rather than the unknown.

Academically, I feel I have grown throughout this process, particularly regarding my writing. I found writing particularly challenging at the beginning, where I lacked the confidence to even share my work. I have realised for me writing is a process where the value of drafting and re-drafting and reading cannot be underestimated. As a lecturer, I can now state with confidence that writing is a skill, and like any other, it can be practised, developed and refined over time. There were definitely some poignant moments on this journey. I felt very honoured and privileged to listen to the participants' stories. Hearing about the challenges that some students and mentors had experienced was heart-breaking. However, even more moving was

hearing about the positive experiences. The compassion shown to learners and how they were embraced in practice restored all faith in the value of practice learning. I remain grateful that undertaking this study allowed me to engage with the participants and hear these powerful recollections of their experiences.

7.8 Final Comments

At the outset, my motivation to undertake this study was driven by a desire to gain a better understanding of what really impacted on practice learning experiences. This study has uncovered some valuable insights that can be taken forward to enhance and strengthen practice learning. As a researcher, the stories uncovered throughout this process leave me in no doubt that practice learning offers pre-registration nursing students a unique learning experience; nevertheless, the complexity of these experiences cannot be underestimated. There were some clear areas identified where improvements could be made. However, I leave this thesis feeling optimistic and excited as to what the future holds for both practice learning and the future nursing workforce.

References

- Akpan, V., Igwe, U., Mpamah, I., Okoro, C., (2020) 'Social Constructivism: Implications on Teaching and Learning'. *British Journal of Education* Vol.8, Issue 8, pp.49-56. Social-Constructivism.pdf (eajournals.org) (accessed September 11, 2022).
- Aliakbari, F.F., Parvin, N.N., Heidari, M.M. and Haghani, F.F. (2015) 'Learning theories application in nursing education', *Journal of education and health promotion*, 4. doi: 10.4103/2277-9531.151867.
- Alston, G.D. and Hansman, C.A. (2020) 'Mentoring in adult and continuing education', *The Handbook of Adult and Continuing Education*, Jossey-Bass, San Francisco, California.
- Amsrud, K.E., Lyberg, A. and Severinsson, E. (2019) 'Development of resilience in nursing students: A systematic qualitative review and thematic synthesis', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 41, pp. 102621. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.102621>.
- Andrew, N., Tolson, D. and Ferguson, D. (2008) 'Building on Wenger: Communities of practice in nursing', *Nurse education today*, 28(2), pp. 246-252. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2007.05.002>.
- Andrews, M., Brewer, M., Buchan, T., Denne, A., Hammond, J., Hardy, G., Jacobs, L., McKenzie, L. and West, S. (2010) 'Implementation and sustainability of the nursing and midwifery standards for mentoring in the UK', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 10(5), pp. 251-255. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2009.11.014>.
- Andrews, M. and Wallis, M. (1999) 'Mentorship in nursing: a literature review', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 29(1), pp. 201-207. doi: [10.1046/j.1365-2648.1999.00884.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.1999.00884.x).
- Aston, L. and Hallam, P. (2011) *Successful mentoring in nursing*. SAGE. London.
- Attenborough, J., Abbott, S., Brook, J. and Knight, R. (2019) 'Everywhere and nowhere: Work-based learning in healthcare education', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 36, pp. 132-138. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2019.03.004>.
- Bada, Steve (2015). Constructivism Learning Theory: A Paradigm for Teaching and Learning. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 5 (6) pp 66-70. doi: 10.9790/7388-05616670
- Baraz, S.S., Memarian, R.R. and Vanaki, Z.Z. (2015) 'Learning challenges of nursing students in clinical environments: A qualitative study in Iran', *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 4. doi: [10.4103/2277-9531.162345](https://doi.org/10.4103/2277-9531.162345).
- Baxter, P. and Jack, S. (2008) 'Qualitative case study methodology: Study design and implementation for novice researchers', *The Qualitative Report*, 13(4), pp. 544-559. doi 10.46743/2160-3715/2008.1573

- Bennett, M. and McGowan, B. (2014) 'Assessment matters-mentors need support in their role', *British Journal of Nursing*, 23(9), pp. 454-458. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2014.23.9.454
- Billett, S. (2004) 'Workplace participatory practices: Conceptualising workplaces as learning environments', *Journal of workplace learning*, 16 (6), pp. 312-324. doi.org/10.1108/13665620410550295
- Billett, S. (2016) 'Learning through health care work: premises, contributions and practices', *Medical education*, 50(1), pp. 124-131. doi: [org/10.1111/medu.12848](https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.12848).
- Bisholt, B., Ohlsson, U., Engström, A.K., Johansson, A.S. and Gustafsson, M. (2014) *Nursing students' assessment of the learning environment in different clinical settings*. *Nurse Education in Practice*, 14(3), pp. 304-10. doi: [10.1016/j.nepr.2013.11.005](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2013.11.005)
- Bolton, G. and Delderfield, R. (2018) *Reflective practice: writing and professional development*. 5th Ed. London, England: SAGE Publications
- Bondy, N., K. (1983) 'Criterion-Referenced definitions for rating scales in Clinical Education', *Journal of Nursing Education*, 22(9) 376-382
- Borbasi, S. (2016) *Navigating the maze of research : enhancing nursing and midwifery practice*. 4th ed. edn. Chatswood, N.S.W.: Chatswood, Elsevier Australia, c2016.
- Bowen, L., Kable, A. and Keatinge, D. (2019) 'Registered nurses' experience of mentoring undergraduate nursing students in a rural context: a qualitative descriptive study', 55(1), pp. 1-14. doi: 10.1080/10376178.2018.1513808.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2013) *Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners*, *Successful Qualitative Research*, 1st ed. London. Sage publications.
- Bray, L. and Nettleton, P. (2007) 'Assessor or mentor? Role confusion in professional education.', *Nurse education today*, 27(8). doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2006.11.006](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2006.11.006)
- Broadbent, M., Moxham, L., Sander, T., Walker, S. and Dwyer, T. (2014) 'Supporting bachelor of nursing students within the clinical environment: Perspectives of preceptors', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 14(4), pp. 403-409. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2013.12.003.
- Brook, J., Aitken, L., MacLaren, DJ., Salmon, D. (2020) Co-production of an intervention to increase retention of early career nurses: Acceptability and feasibility. *Nurse Education in Practice*. 47:102861. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2020.102861.
- Brown, P. (2022) *Nursing students' raising concerns in clinical practice: A grounded theory study of the mentor-student dynamic*. PHD Thesis. Cardiff University. Available at: <https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/id/eprint/149865/2/Nursing%20Students'%20raising%20concerns.%20A%20grounded%20theory%20study%20of%20the%20mentor-student%20dynamic%20-%20Patricia%20Brown.pdf> (accessed 17/07/22).

Brown, L., Douglas, V., Garrity, J. and Kim Shepherd, C. (2012) 'What Influences Mentors to Pass or Fail Students', *Nursing Management - UK*, 19(5), pp. 16-21. doi: [10.7748/nm2012.09.19.5.16.c9260](https://doi.org/10.7748/nm2012.09.19.5.16.c9260)

Browne, C., Wall, P., Batt, S. and Bennett, R. (2018) 'Understanding perceptions of nursing professional identity in students entering an Australian undergraduate nursing degree', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 32, pp. 90-96. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2018.07.006>.

Brydon-Miller, M., Kral, M., Maguire, P., Noffke, S., Sabhlok, A., Denzin, N. and Lincoln, Y. (2011) 'Jazz and the banyan tree', *Handbook of qualitative research*, pp. 387-400. Edition: 4th Ed. Sage. London

Buccheri, R.K. and Sharifi, C. (2017) 'Critical Appraisal Tools and Reporting Guidelines for Evidence-Based Practice', *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(6), pp. 463-472. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/wvn.12258>.

Bulut, H., Hisar, F. and Demir, S.G. (2010) 'Evaluation of mentorship programme in nursing education: A pilot study in Turkey', *Nurse education today*, 30(8), pp. 756-762. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2010.01.019>.

Callaghan, I. and McLafferty, I. (1997) *An audit tool for assessing the learning environment for Project 2000*. Nurse Education Today. 1997 Aug;17(4):338-42. doi: 10.1016/s0260-6917(97)80066-4.

Carey, M.C., Kent, B. and Latour, J.M. (2018) 'Experiences of undergraduate nursing students in peer assisted learning in clinical practice: a qualitative systematic review', *JBI database of systematic reviews and implementation reports; JBI Database System Rev Implement Rep*, 16(5), pp. 1190-1219. doi: 10.11124/JBISRIR-2016-003295.

Carlisle, C., Calman, L. and Ibbotson, T. (2009) 'Practice-based learning: the role of practice education facilitators in supporting mentors.', *Nurse education today*, 29(7), pp. 715-721. doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2009.02.018](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2009.02.018)

Carter, N., Bryant-Lukosius, D., DiCenso, A., Blythe, J. and Neville, A.J. (2014) 'The Use of Triangulation in Qualitative Research', *Oncology nursing forum*, 41(5), pp. 545-547. doi: 10.1188/14.ONF.545-547.

Cassidy, S.N., Coffey, M.N. and Murphy, F.N. "Seeking authorization': a grounded theory exploration of mentors' experiences of assessing nursing students on the borderline of achievement of competence in clinical practice', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*. 73(9):2167-2178. doi: [10.1111/jan.13292](https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13292)

Christiansen, A. and Bell, A. (2010) Peer learning partnerships: exploring the experience of pre-registration nursing students. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 2010 Mar;19(5-6):803-10. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2702.2009.02981.x.

Clark, L. and Casey, D. (2016) 'Support for mentors—an exploration of the issues', *British Journal of Nursing*, 25(20), pp. 1095-1100. doi:10.12968/bjon.2016.25.20.1095

Conneely, A. and Hunter, D. (2012) 'Introducing first-year student placements in critical care', *Nursing Standard*, 26(23), pp. 35-40. doi: 10.7748/ns.26.23.35.s51.

Connor, K. (2019) 'Student perceptions of knowledge development and consolidation in a clinical community of practice', *Nurse education in practice; Nurse Education Practice*, 39, pp. 90-95. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2019.08.012.

Converse, M. (2012) 'Philosophy of phenomenology: How understanding aids research', *Nurse researcher*, 20(1). doi: [10.7748/nr2012.09.20.1.28.c9305](https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2012.09.20.1.28.c9305)

Courtney-Pratt, H., Pich, J., Levett-Jones, T. and Moxey, A. (2018) "I was yelled at, intimidated and treated unfairly": Nursing students' experiences of being bullied in clinical and academic settings', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 27(5-6), pp. e903-e912. doi: 10.1111/jocn.13983.

Creswell, J.W., Poth, J. (2018) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: Sage publications.

Cronin, C. (2014) 'Using case study research as a rigorous form of inquiry', *Nurse Researcher*, 21(5), pp. 19-27. doi: 10.7748/nr.21.5.19.e1240.

Crotty, M.J. (1998) *The foundations of social research: Meaning and perspective in the research process*, London. Sage publications.

Dames, S. THRIVEable work environments: A study of interplaying factors that enable novice nurses to thrive. *Journal of Nurse Management*. 2019; 27: 567– 574. doi: [org/10.1111/jonm.12712](https://doi.org/10.1111/jonm.12712)

Davidson, A.S. (2013) 'Phenomenological approaches in psychology and health sciences', *Qualitative research in psychology*, 10(3), pp. 318-339. doi: [10.1080/14780887.2011.608466](https://doi.org/10.1080/14780887.2011.608466)

Delgado, C., Upton, D., Ransie, K., Furness, T. and Foster, K. (2017) 'Nurses' resilience and the emotional labour of nursing work: An integrative review of empirical literature', *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 70, pp. 71-88. doi: [10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2017.02.008](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2017.02.008)

Devlin, N. and Duggan, S. (2020) 'An evaluation of nurses' experiences of mentoring pre-registration students', *British Journal of Nursing*, 29(5), pp. 308-313. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2020.29.5.308.

Dowling, M. (2007) 'From Husserl to van Manen. A review of different phenomenological approaches', *International journal of nursing studies*, 44(1), pp. 131-142. doi: [10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2005.11.026](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2005.11.026)

Drayton, L. and Edmonds, M. (2020) 'Understanding the role of the academic assessor', *Nursing standard*, 35(9), pp. 41-45. doi: 10.7748/ns.2020.e11463.

D'Souza, M.S., Karkada, S.N., Parahoo, K. and Venkatesaperumal, R. (2015) 'Perception of and satisfaction with the clinical learning environment among nursing students', *Nurse Education Today*, 35(6), pp. 833-840. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.02.005>.

Duffy, K. (2003) *Failing students: a qualitative study of factors that influence the decisions regarding assessment of students' competence in practice*, Glasgow Caledonian University. Caledonian Nursing and Midwifery Research Centre School of Nursing, Midwifery and Community Health

Duffy, K. and Gillies, A. (2018) 'Supervision and assessment: the new Nursing and Midwifery Council standards', *Nursing management*, 25(3), pp. 17-21. doi: 10.7748/nm.2018.e1765.

Earle, V. (2010) 'Phenomenology as research method or substantive metaphysics? An overview of phenomenology's uses in nursing', *Nursing Philosophy*, 11(4), pp. 286-296. doi: 10.1111/j.1466-769X.2010.00458.x.

Eddles-Hirsch, K. (2015) 'Phenomenology and educational research', *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(8). doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2013.07.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.07.020)

Eller, L.S., Lev, E.L. and Feurer, A. (2014) 'Key components of an effective mentoring relationship: A qualitative study', *Nurse education today*, 34(5), pp. 815-820. doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2013.07.020](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.07.020)

Epstein, N.E. (2014) 'Multidisciplinary in-hospital teams improve patient outcomes: A review', *Surgical neurology international*, 5(Suppl 7), pp. S295-303. doi: 10.4103/2152-7806.139612.

Ewertsson, M., Bagga-Gupta, S., Allvin, R. and Blomberg, K. (2017) 'Tensions in learning professional identities - nursing students' narratives and participation in practical skills during their clinical practice: an ethnographic study', *BMC nursing*, 16(1), pp. 48-48. doi: 10.1186/s12912-017-0238-y.

Felstead, I.S. and Springett, K. (2016) 'An exploration of role model influence on adult nursing students' professional development: A phenomenological research study', *Nurse Education Today*, 37, pp. 66-70. doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2015.11.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.11.014)

Fisher, M.,E. and Oudshoorn, A. (2019) ' Debriefing for Professional Practice Placements in Nursing: A Concept Analysis, Nursing Education Perspectives: ', *Education Perspectives*, 40(4), pp. 199-204. doi: [10.1097/01.NEP.0000000000000487](https://doi.org/10.1097/01.NEP.0000000000000487)

Fleming., J. (2018) 'Recognizing and resolving the challenges of being an insider researcher in work-integrated learning ', *International Journal of Work-Integrated Learning*, 19(3), pp. 311-320. Retrieved from <https://www.proquest.com/scholarly-journals/recognizing-resolving-challenges-being-insider/docview/2227915506/se-2>

Flood, A. (2010) 'Understanding phenomenology', *Nurse researcher*, 17(2). doi: [10.7748/nr2010.01.17.2.7.c7457](https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2010.01.17.2.7.c7457)

Ford, K., Courtney-Pratt, H., Marlow, A., Cooper, J., Williams, D. and Mason, R. (2016) 'Quality clinical placements: The perspectives of undergraduate nursing students and their supervising nurses', *Nurse education today*, 37, pp. 97-102. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2015.11.013.

Foster, H., Ooms, A. and Marks-Maran, D. (2015) Nursing students' expectations and experiences of mentorship. *Nurse Education*, 35(1):18-24. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2014.04.019.

Fulton, J. (2015) 'The archaeology and genealogy of mentorship in English nursing', *Nursing inquiry*, 22(1), pp. 39-49. doi: 10.1111/nin.12051.

Galbin, A., (2014) 'An introduction to social constructionism', *Social Research Reports*, 26, pp. 82-92. [Garada site.pmd \(researchreports.ro\)](http://garada.site.pmd(researchreports.ro)) (accessed June 11th, 2022)

Galvin, J., Suominen, E., Morgan, C., O'Connell, E.-. and Smith, A.P. (2015) 'Mental health nursing students' experiences of stress during training: a thematic analysis of qualitative interviews', *Journal of psychiatric and mental health nursing*, 22(10), pp. 773-783. doi: 10.1111/jpm.12273.

Gerrish, K., Lacey, A. and Cormack, D. (2010) *The research process in nursing*. 6th ed. / edited by Kate Gerrish and Anne Lacey. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell, 2010.

Gibbons, C., Dempster, M. and Moutray, M. (2011) 'Stress, coping and satisfaction in nursing students', *Journal of advanced nursing*, 67(3), pp. 621-632. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2648.2010.05495.x>.

Gidman, J., McIntosh, A., Melling, K. and Smith, D. (2011) Student perceptions of support in practice. *Nurse Education Practice*, 11(6):351-5. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2011.03.005.

Gilbert, J. and Brown, L. (2015) 'The clinical environment-do student nurses belong?: A review of Australian literature', *Australian Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 33(1), pp. 23-28. doi:10.3316/informit.444940851090289

Glen, S. (2009) 'Nursing education -- is it time to go back to the future?', *British Journal of Nursing*, 18(8), pp. 498-502. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2009.18.8.41814.

Grant, C. and Osanloo, A. (2015) 'Understanding, selecting, and integrating a theoretical framework in dissertation research', *Administrative Issues Journal*, 4(10), pp. 12-22.

Gray, O. and Brown, D. (2016) 'Evaluating a nurse mentor preparation programme', *British Journal of Nursing*, 25(4), pp. 212-217. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2016.25.4.212

Gray, M.A. and Smith, L.N. (2000) 'The qualities of an effective mentor from the student nurse's perspective: findings from a longitudinal qualitative study.', *Journal of advanced nursing*, 32(6), pp. 1542-1549. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-2648.2000.01606.x

- Grealish, L., Ranse, K., (2009) An exploratory study of first year nursing students' learning in the clinical workplace. *Contemporary Nurse*. 2009 Aug;33(1):80-92. doi: 10.5172/conu.33.1.80.
- Greenwood, J. (2000) 'Critique of the graduate nurse: an international perspective', *Nurse education today*, 20(1), pp. 17-23. doi: 10.1054/nedt.2000.0424
- Grix, J. (2018) *The foundations of research*. 3rd ed., United Kingdom, Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Grobecker, P.A. (2016) 'A sense of belonging and perceived stress among baccalaureate nursing students in clinical placements', *Nurse education today*, 36, pp. 178-183. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2015.09.015
- Hale, R.L. and Phillips, C.A. (2018) 'Mentoring up: A grounded theory of nurse-to-nurse mentoring', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 28(1-2), pp. 159-172. doi: [10.1111/jocn.14636](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.14636)
- Hale, R.L. (2015) *Mentoring Up: A Classical Grounded Theory Exploring the Proteges Perceptions of Nurse-to-Nurse Mentoring*. PHD Thesis. The University of Texas.
- Hammersley, M. and Atkinson, P. (2007) 'Ethnography: principles in practice' London. Routledge.
- Harrison, H., Birks, M., Franklin, R. and Mills, J. (2017) 'Case Study Research: Foundations and Methodological Orientations', *Forum: Qualitative Social Research*, 18(1). doi: 10.17169/fqs-18.1.2655.
- Harrison-White, K. (2020) An investigation of student nurses' experiences of learning within the Clinical Learning Environment. Thesis, Doctorate in Education (EdD): King's College, London. Available at: https://kclpure.kcl.ac.uk/portal/files/131963377/2020_Harrison_White_Karen_1256410_ethesis.pdf (Accessed on 24.2.22).
- Harrison-White, K. and Owens, J. (2018) 'Nurse link lecturers' perceptions of the challenges facing student nurses in clinical learning environments: A qualitative study', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 32, pp. 78-83. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2018.07.012>.
- Henderson, A., Twentyman, M., Eaton, E., Creedy, D., Stapleton, P. and Lloyd, B. (2010) 'Creating supportive clinical learning environments: an intervention study', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 19(1-2), pp. 177-182. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2702.2009.02841.x.
- Henderson, A. (2012) 'Nursing students' perceptions of learning in practice environments: A review', *Nurse education today*, 32(3), pp. 299. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2011.03.010
- Hilli, Y., Melender, H., Salmu, M. and Jonsén, E. (2014) 'Being a preceptor—A Nordic qualitative study', *Nurse education today*, 34(12), pp. 1420-1424. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2014.04.013

Hoe, J. and Hoare, Z. (2012) 'Understanding quantitative research', *Nursing Standard*, 27(15), pp. 52. doi: [10.7748/ns2012.12.27.15.52.c9485](https://doi.org/10.7748/ns2012.12.27.15.52.c9485)

Holm, A.L., Berland, A.K. and Severinsson, E. (2016) 'Older Patients' Involvement in Shared Decision-Making—A Systematic Review', *Open Journal of Nursing*, 6, pp. 170-185. doi: [10.4236/ojn.2016.63018](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojn.2016.63018)

Hood, K., Cant, R., Baulch, J., Gilbee, A., Leech, M., Anderson, A. and Davies, K. (2014) 'Prior experience of interprofessional learning enhances undergraduate nursing and healthcare students' professional identity and attitudes to teamwork', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 14(2), pp. 117-122. doi: [10.1016/j.nepr.2013.07.013](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2013.07.013)

Hopper, E. (2021). Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs Explained. Retrieved from <https://www.thoughtco.com/maslows-hierarchy-of-needs-4582571>

Houghton, C.E., Casey, D., Shaw, D. and Murphy, K. (2013) 'Students' experiences of implementing clinical skills in the real world of practice', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 22(13-14), pp. 1961-1969. doi: [10.1111/jocn.12014](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.12014).

Houghton, C., Murphy, K., Meehan, B., Thomas, J., Brooker, D. and Casey, D. (2017) 'From screening to synthesis: using nvivo to enhance transparency in qualitative evidence synthesis', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 26(5-6), pp. 873-881. doi: [10.1111/jocn.13443](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.13443).

Howarth, G. (2021) 'Funded places for student nurses in Scotland to increase for 10th year', *Nursing Times*, News Article. Available at [https://www.nursingtimes.net/news/education/funded-places-for-student-nurses-in-scotland-to-increase-for-10th-year-24-12-2021/#:~:text=The%20Scottish%20Government%20has%20said,and%204%2C206%20in%202020%2D21.\(Accessed on 1/09/22\)](https://www.nursingtimes.net/news/education/funded-places-for-student-nurses-in-scotland-to-increase-for-10th-year-24-12-2021/#:~:text=The%20Scottish%20Government%20has%20said,and%204%2C206%20in%202020%2D21.(Accessed on 1/09/22))

Huff, A.S. (2008) *Designing research for publication*. Sage. Thousand Oaks, CA.

Hunt, L.A., McGee, P., Gutteridge, R. and Hughes, M. (2016) Failing securely: The processes and support which underpin English nurse mentors' assessment decisions regarding under-performing students. *Nurse Education Today*, 39:79-86. doi: [10.1016/j.nedt.2016.01.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2016.01.011).

Hyde, A. and Brady, D. (2002) 'Staff nurses' perceptions of supernumerary status compared with rostered service for Diploma in Nursing students', *Journal of advanced nursing*, 38(6), pp. 624-632. doi: [10.1046/j.1365-2648.2002.02230.x](https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2648.2002.02230.x).

Jack, K., Hamshire, C., Harris, W.E., Langan, M., Barrett, N. and Wibberley, C. (2018) "My mentor didn't speak to me for the first four weeks": Perceived Unfairness experienced by nursing students in clinical practice settings', *Journal of Clinical Nursing; J Clin Nurs*, 27(5-6), pp. 929-938. doi: [10.1111/jocn.14015](https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.14015).

James, A. and Chapman, Y. (2010) 'Preceptors and patients—the power of two: Nursing student experiences on their first acute clinical placement', *Contemporary Nurse*, 34(1), pp. 34-47. doi: [10.5172/conu.2009.34.1.034](https://doi.org/10.5172/conu.2009.34.1.034)

Jokelainen, M., Jamookeeah, D., Tossavainen, K. and Turunen, H. (2013) 'Finnish and British mentors' conceptions of facilitating nursing students' placement learning and professional development', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 13(1), pp. 61-67. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2012.07.008.

Jones, J. and Smith, J. (2017) *Ethnography: challenges and opportunities* BMJ Publishing Group Ltd and RCN Publishing Company Ltd. London.

Jørgensen, W. and Hadders, H. (2015) 'The significance of communities of practice: Norwegian nursing students' experience of clinical placement in Bangladesh', *Nursing open*, 2(1), pp. 36-46. doi: 10.1002/nop2.15.

Joynes, V.C.T. (2017) 'Defining and understanding the relationship between professional identity and interprofessional responsibility: implications for educating health and social care students', *Advances in health sciences education: theory and practice; Adv Health Science Education Theory Practice*, 23(1), pp. 133-149. doi: 10.1007/s10459-017-9778-x.

Kaman, Z.K., and Othman, Z., (2016) Validity, Reliability and Triangulation in Case Study Method: An Experience. *Qualitative Research Conference (QRC)* , 24-26 May 2016, Penang, Malaysia. [ICAS 2015 Template \(qualitative-research-conference.com\)](http://www.icas2015.com) (accessed February 24th2022)

Kalyani, M., Jamshidi, N., Molazem, Z., Torabizadeh, C. and Sharif, F. (2019) 'How do nursing students experience the clinical learning environment and respond to their experiences? A qualitative study', *British Medical Journal Open*, 9(7), pp. e028052-2018-028052. doi: 10.1136/bmjopen-2018-028052

Kaiser K. Protecting Respondent Confidentiality in Qualitative Research. *Qualitative Health Research*. 2009;19(11):1632-1641. doi:10.1177/1049732309350879

Kelly, S.E., Bourgeault, I. and Dingwall, R. (2010) 'Qualitative interviewing techniques and styles', *The SAGE handbook of qualitative methods in health research*, pp. 307-326. Sage, London.

Kelly, S.H. (2020) 'The hidden curriculum: Undergraduate nursing students' perspectives of socialization and professionalism', *Nursing ethics*, 27(5), pp. 1250-1260. doi: [10.1177/0969733019881714](https://doi.org/10.1177/0969733019881714)

Kern, A., Montgomery, P., Mossey, S. and Bailey, P. (2014) 'Undergraduate nursing students' belongingness in clinical learning environments: Constructivist grounded theory', *Journal of Nursing Education and Practice*, 4(3), pp. 133. doi: 10.5430/jnep.v4n3p133

King, C., Russell, K. and Bulsara, C. (2017) 'Promoting student belongingness: 'WANTED'-the development, implementation and evaluation of a toolkit for nurses', *Australian Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 34(3), pp. 48-53. Available at; <https://www.ajan.com.au/archive/Vol34/Issue3/6King.pdf> (Accessed on 13/01/2022).

- King-Hill, S. (2015) 'Critical analysis of Maslow's hierarchy of need', *The STeP Journal (Student Teacher Perspectives)*, 2(4), pp. 54-57. <http://insight.cumbria.ac.uk/id/eprint/2942>
- Koontz, A., Mallory, J., Burns, J. and Chapman, S. (2010) Staff Nurses and Students: The Good, The Bad, and The Ugly. *Medsurg Nursing*. 2010 Jul-Aug;19(4):240-4, 246. PMID: 20860251.
- Krueger, R.A. (2014) *Focus groups: A practical guide for applied research*. Sage publications. Thousand Oaks. CA.
- Landers, M.G., Mairin O'Mahony and McCarthy, B. (2020) 'A Theoretical Framework to Underpin Clinical Learning for Undergraduate Nursing Students', *Nurse Science Quarterly*, 33(2), pp. 159-164. doi: 10.1177/0894318419898167.
- Lave, J., Wenger, E. (1991) *Situated learning: legitimate peripheral participation*. Cambridge: Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511815355
- Law, M., Stewart, D., Letts, L., Pollock, N., Bosch, J. and Westmorland, M. (1998) 'Guidelines for critical review of qualitative studies', *McMaster University occupational therapy evidence-based practice research Group*, pp. 1-9.
- Lee, J.J., Clarke, C.L. and Carson, M.N. (2018) 'Nursing students' learning dynamics and influencing factors in clinical contexts', *Nurse education in practice* 29, pp. 103-109. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2017.12.003.
- Leigh, J. and Roberts, D. (2018) 'Critical exploration of the new NMC standards of proficiency for registered nurses', *British journal of nursing (Mark Allen Publishing); British Journal of Nursing*, 27(18), pp. 1068-1072. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2018.27.18.1068.
- Letts, L., Wilkins, S., Law, M., Stewart, D., Bosch, J. and Westmorland, M. (2007) 'Critical review form-Qualitative studies (Version 2.0)', *McMaster University*.
- Levett-Jones, T. and Lathlean, J. (2008) Belongingness: a prerequisite for nursing students' clinical learning. *Nurse Education Practice*, 8 (2), pp.103-11. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2007.04.003.
- Levett-Jones T, Lathlean J. (2009a) 'The ascent to competence conceptual framework: an outcome of a study of belongingness'. *Journal of Clinical Nursing*. 18(20): pp. 2870-9. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2702.2008.02593.x.
- Levett-Jones, T, and Lathlean, J. (2009b) 'Don't rock the boat': Nursing students' experiences of conformity and compliance, *Nurse Education Today*,29(3),pp. 342-349. Doi:10.1016/j.nedt.2008.10.009.
- Li, L.C., Grimshaw, J.M., Nielsen, C., Judd, M., Coyte, P.C. and Graham, I.D. (2009) 'Evolution of Wenger's concept of community of practice', *Implementation science*, 4(1), pp. 1-9. doi: 10.1186/1748-5908-4-11.
- Liljedahl, M., Björck, E., Kalén, S., Ponzer, S. and Bolander Laksov, K. (2016) 'To belong or not to belong: nursing students' interactions with clinical learning environments - an

observational study', *BMC medical education*, 16(1), pp. 197-197. doi: 10.1186/s12909-016-0721-2.

Lin, J., Chew, Y.R., Toh, Y.P. and Krishna, L.K.R. (2018) 'Mentoring in nursing: an integrative review of commentaries, editorials, and perspectives papers', *Nurse Educator*, 43(1), pp. 1-5. Doi: 10.1097/NNE.0000000000000389

Lingard, L. (2019) 'Beyond the default colon: Effective use of quotes in qualitative research', *Perspectives on medical education*, 8(6), pp. 360-364. doi: 10.1007/s40037-019-00550-7.

LoBiondo-Wood, G. and Haber, J. (2014) *Nursing research: Methods and critical appraisal for evidence-based practice*. Elsevier. St Louis.

Longley, M., Shaw, C. and Dolan, G. (2007) *Nursing: Towards 2015 Alternative scenarios for Health care, Nursing and Nurse education..* United Kingdom: The Welsh Institute for Health and Social Care. Available at: <https://aape.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2015/02/Nursing-Toward-2015.pdf> (Accessed:15/09/2018).

Lopez, V., Yobas, P., Chow, Y.L. and Shorey, S. (2018) 'Does building resilience in undergraduate nursing students happen through clinical placements? A qualitative study', *Nurse Education Today*, 67, pp. 1-5. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2018.04.020>.

Lunaigh, P.O. (2015) 'Becoming a professional: What is the influence of registered nurses on nursing students' learning in the clinical environment?', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 15(6), pp. 450-456. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2015.04.005.

MacDonald, C. (2012) 'Understanding participatory action research: A qualitative research methodology option', *The Canadian Journal of Action Research*, 13(2), pp. 34-50. <https://doi.org/10.33524/cjar.v13i2.37>

Macey, A., Green, C. and Jarden, R.J. (2021) 'ICU nurse preceptors' perceptions of benefits, rewards, supports and commitment to the preceptor role: A mixed-methods study', *Nurse Education in Practice*, 51, pp. 102995. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nepr.2021.102995>.

MacIntosh, T. (2015) 'The link lecturer role; inconsistent and incongruent realities', *Nurse Education Today*, 35(3), pp. e8-e13. doi 10.1016/j.nedt.2015.01.004

Maginnis, C. (2018) 'A discussion of professional identity development in nursing students', *Journal of Perspectives in Applied Academic Practice*, 6(1). doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2015.03.014

Manninen, K., Welin Henriksson, E., Scheja, M. and Silén, C. (2013) 'Authenticity in learning - nursing students' experiences at a clinical education ward', *Health Education*, 113(2), pp. 132-143. doi: 10.1108/09654281311298812.

Manninen, K., Henriksson, E.W., Scheja, M. and Silén, C. (2014) 'Patients' approaches to students' learning at a clinical education ward--an ethnographic study', *BMC medical education*, 14(1), pp. 131. doi: 10.1186/1472-6920-14-131.

Manninen, K. (2016) 'Experiencing authenticity – the core of student learning in clinical practice'. *Perspectives in Medical Education*, 5, pp. 308-311. doi: 10.1007/s40037-016-0294-0

Maslow, A. and Lewis, K. (1987) 'Maslow's hierarchy of needs', *Salenger Incorporated*, 14(17), pp. 987-990.

McCloughen, A., Levy, D., Johnson, A., Nguyen, H. and McKenzie, H. (2020) 'Nursing students' socialisation to emotion management during early clinical placement experiences: A qualitative study', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 29(13-14), pp. 2508-2520. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jocn.15270>.

McGuinness, C., Scott, M.J.A., McKinlay, M.L. and Sturley, M.L. 'Learning in Practice: What are the Perceptions of Undergraduate Pre-Registration Nursing Students and Mentors?', NHS Education for Scotland (NES). Available at: <https://www.nes.scot.nhs.uk/media/021jnanu/project-report-practice-learning-31st-may-2019.pdf> (Accessed on 1/05/22).

McIntosh, A., Gidman, J. and Smith, D. (2014) 'Mentors' perceptions and experiences of supporting student nurses in practice: Student support: The role of mentors', *International Journal of Nursing Practice*, 20(4), pp. 360-365. doi: 10.1111/ijn.12163.

McNiff, J. (2013) *Action research: Principles and practice*. London. Routledge.

McNiff, J. and Whitehead, J. (2011) *All you need to know about action research*. Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage Publications.

Mcsharry, E. and Lathlean, J. (2017) 'Clinical teaching and learning within a preceptorship model in an acute care hospital in Ireland; a qualitative study', *Nurse Education Today*, 51, pp. 73-80. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2017.01.007

Mead, D., Hopkins, A. and Wilson, C. (2011) 'Views of Nurse Mentors about their Role', *Nursing Management - UK*, 18(6), pp. 18-23. doi: 10.7748/nm2011.10.18.6.18.c8716

Melincavage, S. M. (2008) *Anxiety in student nurses in the clinical setting. A phenomenological study*. Doctorate of Education. The Pennsylvania State University. Available at: <https://etda.libraries.psu.edu/catalog/8155> (Accessed on 24/2/22).

Melincavage, S.M. (2011) 'Student nurses' experiences of anxiety in the clinical setting', *Nurse education today*, 31(8), pp. 785-789. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2011.05.007>.

Merriam, S.B. (1998) *Qualitative Research and Case Study Applications in Education. Revised and Expanded from " Case Study Research in Education."*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass

Mikkonen, K., Tomietto, M., Cicolini, G., Kaucic, B.M., Filej, B., Riklikiene, O., Juskauskienė, E., Vizcaya-Moreno, F., Pérez-Cañaveras, R.M., De Raeve, P. and Kääriäinen, M. (2020) 'Development and testing of an evidence-based model of mentoring nursing students in clinical practice', *Nurse education today*, 85, pp. 104272. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2019.104272>.

Miles, M.B. and Huberman, A.M. (1994) *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications.

Miles, K. (2011) 'Using attachment theory in mentoring', *Nursing Times*, 107(38), pp. 23-25.

Minton, C. and Birks, M. (2019) "You can't escape it": Bullying experiences of New Zealand nursing students on clinical placement. *Nurse Education Today*, 77 (6), pp. 12-17. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2019.03.002

Molesworth, M. (2017) 'Nursing students' first placement: Peripherality and marginality within the community of practice', *Journal of Nursing Education*, 56(1), pp. 31-38. doi: 10.3928/01484834-20161219-07

Moore, L.K., Holley, A.B. and Collen, J.F. (2018) 'Working with a mentor: Effective strategies during fellowship and early career', *Chest*, 153(4), pp. 799-804. doi: [10.1016/j.chest.2018.02.016](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chest.2018.02.016)

Morley, D. (2016) 'Applying Wenger's communities of practice theory to placement learning', *Nurse Education Today*, 39, pp. 161-162. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2016.02.007>.

Moss, C., Grealish, L., Lake, S. (2010) 'Valuing the gap: A dialectic between theory and practice in graduate nursing education from a constructive educational approach', *Nurse Education Today*, 30 (4) pp 327-332. doi, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2009.09.001>.

Nagle, L. (2021) *An exploration of the factors impacting on Pre-Professional Identity formation during Legitimate Peripheral Participation within nursing clinical placement*. PhD thesis. University of Limerick Kemmy School of Business.

Newman, I., Benz, C.R. and Ridenour, C.S. (1998) *Qualitative-quantitative research methodology: Exploring the interactive continuum*. SIU Press.

Newton, J. (2009) 'Journeying through clinical placements - An examination of six student cases', *Nurse education today*, 29(6), pp. 630. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2009.01.009

NHS Education for Scotland (NES) (2013) *National Approach to Mentor Preparation for Nurses and Midwives: Core Curriculum Framework*, 2nd ed., Edinburgh: NES.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (2008) *Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice. NMC Standards for Mentors, Practice Teachers and Teachers*. NMC, London., 2nd ed., London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (2006) *Standards to Support Learning and Assessment in Practice. NMC Standards for Mentors, Practice Teachers and Teachers*. 1st ed., London: NMC.

Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) (2018a) *Realising professionalism: Standards for education and training. Part 2: Standards for student supervision and assessment*. Nursing and Midwifery Council. London.

Nursing and Midwifery Council NMC (2018b) *Future nurse: Standards of proficiency for registered nurses*. Nursing and Midwifery Council. London.

O'Driscoll, M.F., Allan, H.T. and Smith, P.A. (2010) 'Still looking for leadership – Who is responsible for student nurses' learning in practice?', *Nurse Education Today*, 30(3), pp. 212-217. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2009.12.012>.

O'Brien, B.,C. and Battista, A. (2020) 'Situated Learning Theory in Health Professions Education Research: A Scoping Review', *Advances in Health Sciences Education : theory and practice*, 25(2), pp. 483-509. doi: 10.1007/s10459-019-09900-w.

Olmos-Vega, F., Stalmeijer, R.E., Varpio, L. and Kahlke, R. (2022) 'A practical guide to reflexivity in qualitative research: AMEE Guide No. 149', *Medical Teacher*, pp. 1-11. doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2022.2057287.

O'Mara, L., McDonald, J., Gillespie, M., Brown, H. and Miles, L. (2014) Challenging clinical learning environments: Experiences of undergraduate nursing students. *Nurse Education Today*, 29(6), pp. 630-4. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2009.01.009.

Ousey, K. 'The changing face of student nurse education and training programmes' *Wounds UK*, 7(1), pp.70-75. Available at: https://www.woundsme.com/uploads/resources/content_9838.pdf (accessed on 29/3/21).

Panda, S., Dash, M., John, J., Rath, K., Debata, A., Swain, D., Mohanty, K. and Eustace-Cook, J. (2021) 'Challenges faced by student nurses and midwives in clinical learning environment – A systematic review and meta-synthesis', *Nurse education today*, 101, pp. 104875. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2021.104875>.

Papastavrou, E., Dimitriadou, M., Tsangari, H. and Andreou, C. (2016) 'Nursing students' satisfaction of the clinical learning environment: a research study', *BMC nursing*, 15(1), pp. 44-44. doi: 10.1186/s12912-016-0164-4.

Papathanasiou, I.V., Tsaras, K. and Sarafis, P. (2014) Views and perceptions of nursing students on their clinical learning environment: Teaching and learning. *Nurse Education Today*, 34(1) pp. 57-60. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2013.02.007.

Parahoo, K. (2014) *Nursing research: principles, process and issues*. London, Palgrave Macmillan.

Patel, C. (2017) *A MACAT ANALYSIS Situated Learning, legitimate peripheral participation*. 1st ed. New York: Routledge.

Patton, M.Q. (2014) *Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice*. Thousand Oaks, CA.Sage Publications.

Pearson, S., Wallymahmed, M., (2020) 'The new NMC standards: Changes to student supervision and assessment', *Journal of Diabetes Nursing Volume*, 24(3). Available at: <https://diabetesonthenet.com/journal-diabetes-nursing/new-nmc-standards-changes-student-supervision-and-assessment/> (accessed on 13.01.2021).

Polit, D.F. and Beck, C.T. (2010) 'Generalization in quantitative and qualitative research: Myths and strategies', *International Journal of Nursing Studies*, 47(11), pp. 1451-1458. doi: 10.1016/j.ijnurstu.2010.06.004

Ponterotto, J.G. (2005) 'Qualitative research in counseling psychology: A primer on research paradigms and philosophy of science.', *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 52(2), pp. 126. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0167.52.2.126>

Powell, I. (2013) 'Can you see me? Experiences of nurses working night shift in Australian regional hospitals: a qualitative case study', *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 69(10), pp. 2172-2184. doi: 10.1111/jan.12079.

Priya, A. (2014) 'Revisiting case study method of social research examining its cardinal attributes and its potential for generating authoritative knowledge', *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 9(11), pp. 44-49. doi:10.9790/0837-191174044

Pullon, S., Morgan, S., Macdonald, L., McKinlay, E. and Gray, B. (2016) 'Observation of interprofessional collaboration in primary care practice: a multiple case study', *Journal of Interprofessional Care*, 30(6), pp. 787-794. doi: 10.1080/13561820.2016.1220929

QSR International Pty Ltd. (2020) NVivo (released in March 2020), <https://www.qsrinternational.com/nvivo-qualitative-data-analysis-software/home>

Reyes, A.T., Andrusyszyn Mary-Anne, Carroll, I., Cheryl, F. and Babenko-Mould Yolanda (2015) 'Resilience in Nursing Education: An Integrative Review', *Journal of Nursing Education*, 54(8), pp. 438-444. doi: 10.3928/01484834-20150717-03.

Roberts, J. (2006). Limits to communities of practice. *Journal of Management Studies*, 43(3), 623-639. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-6486.2006.00618>

Roberts, S., (2018). *Exploring How Women on Corporate Boards Cope With Gender Bias*. PHD. Walden University. Available at: <https://scholarworks.waldenu.edu/dissertations/4885/> (Accessed 10/06/22)

Roberts, D. (2008) Learning in clinical practice: the importance of peers. *Nursing Standard*. 2;23(12):35-41. doi: 10.7748/ns2008.11.23.12.35.c6727

Roxburgh M, Conlon M and Banks D (2012) Evaluating Hub and Spoke models of practice learning in Scotland, UK: a multiple case study approach. *Nurse Education Today*, 32(7):782-9. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2012.05.004

Roxburgh, M. (2014) 'Undergraduate student nurses' perceptions of two practice learning models: A focus group study', *Nurse Education Today*, 34(1), pp. 40-46. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2013.02.017>.

Royal College of Nursing (2016) *RCN Mentorship Project 2015: From Today's Support in Practice to Tomorrow's Vision for Excellence. Rapid Evidence Review*. RCN. London.

Royal College of Nursing (1985) *The Education of Nurses: A New Dispensation. Commission on Nursing Education. Chairman, Dr. Harry Judge*. RCN, London London:

Ryan, S. (2017) 'Promoting effective teamwork in the healthcare setting', *Nursing standard*; 31(30), pp. 52-60. doi: 10.7748/ns.2017.e10726.

Rylance, R., Barrett, J., Sixsmith, P. and Ward, D. (2017) 'Student nurse mentoring: an evaluative study of the mentor's perspective', *British Journal of Nursing*, 26(7), pp. 405-409. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2017.26.7.405

Savin-Baden, M. and Howell-Major, C. (2013) 'Qualitative research: The essential guide to theory and practice', *Qualitative Research: The Essential Guide to Theory and Practice*. Routledge, Thousand Oaks. CA.

Schaffer, M. (2013) *The mentoring-burnout relationship and predictors of nurse mentoring behaviour*. PHD thesis. Clemson University. Available at: https://tigerprints.clemson.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2116&context=all_dissertations (accessed on 06/06/22)

Scotland, J. (2012) 'Exploring the philosophical underpinnings of research: Relating ontology and epistemology to the methodology and methods of the scientific, interpretive, and critical research paradigms.', *English language teaching*, 5(9), pp. 9-16. doi:10.5539/elt.v5n9p9

Sheehan, A., Elmir, R., Hammond, A., Schmied, V., Coulton, S., Sorensen, K., Arundell, F., Keedle, H., Dahlen, H. and Burns, E. (2021) 'The midwife-student mentor relationship: Creating the virtuous circle', *Women and Birth*, 35(5):e512-e520. doi: 10.1016/j.wombi.2021.10.007.

Scholz, R. W., Tietje, O. (2002). *Embedded case study methods – integrating quantitative and qualitative knowledge*. Thousand Oaks, California. Sage Publications, Inc.

Silverman, D. (2011) *Interpreting Qualitative Data*. Thousand Oaks, California. Sage Publications.

Simons, H. (2009) *Case study research in practice*. 1st Ed. London. Sage Publications.

Smedley, A. and Morey, P. (2010) 'Improving learning in the clinical nursing environment: perceptions of senior Australian bachelor of nursing students', *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 15(1), pp. 75-88. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/1744987108101756>.

Smith, P., (2018) 'Collecting Sufficient Evidence When Conducting a Case Study'. *The Qualitative Report*. 23 (5), pp. 1043-1048. doi. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2018.3188>

Smith, S. U., Hayes, S., and Shea, P (2017). A critical review of the use of Wenger's Community of Practice (CoP) theoretical framework in online and blended learning research, 2000- 2014, *Online Learning* 21(1), 209-237. doi: 10.24059/olj.v21i1.963

Stacey, G. (2014) *A case study exploring presentation and positioning of self in graduate entry nursing students*, Doctor of Philosophy in Nursing Studies. Nottingham University.

Stake, R.E. (2005) *Multiple case study analysis*. New York. The Guilford Press.

Stake, R.E. (1995) *The art of case study research*. London. sage.

Stenberg, M. and Carlson, E. (2015) 'Swedish student nurses' perception of peer learning as an educational model during clinical practice in a hospital setting—an evaluation study', *BMC nursing*, 14(1), pp. 1-7.

Stephens, T.M. (2013) 'Nursing Student Resilience: A Concept Clarification', *Nursing Forum*, 48(2), pp. 125-133. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/nuf.12015>.

Straus, S.E., Johnson, M.O., Marquez, C. and Feldman, M.D. (2013) 'Characteristics of successful and failed mentoring relationships: a qualitative study across two academic health centers', *Academic medicine*, 88(1), pp. 82-89. doi: 10.1097/ACM.0b013e31827647a0.

Sundler, A.J., Björk, M., Bisholt, B., Ohlsson, U., Engström, A.K. and Gustafsson, M. (2014) 'Student nurses' experiences of the clinical learning environment in relation to the organization of supervision: A questionnaire survey'. *Nurse Education Today*, 34(4):661-6 doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2013.06.023

Taylor, R. and Thomas-Gregory, A. (2015) 'Case study research', *Nursing Standard*, 29(41), pp. 36-40. doi: 10.7748/ns.29.41.36.e8856.

Teatheredge, J. (2010) 'Interviewing student and qualified nurses to find out what makes an effective mentor', *Nursing times*, 106(48), pp. 19-21.

Terry, D.R., Nguyen, H., Peck, B., Smith, A. and Phan, H. (2020) 'Communities of practice: A systematic review and meta-synthesis of what it means and how it really works among nursing students and novices', *Journal of Clinical Nursing*, 29(3-4), pp. 370-380. doi: 10.1111/jocn.15100.

Tsai, A., Kohrt, B., Matthews, T., Betancourt, T., Lee, J., Andrew V. Papachristos A., Weiser, S., Dworkin, S. (2016) 'Promises and pitfalls of data sharing in qualitative research', *Social*

Science & Medicine, 169, pp 191-198, ISSN 0277-9536,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2016.08.004>

Thanh, N.C. and Thanh, T. (2015) 'The interconnection between interpretivist paradigm and qualitative methods in education', *American Journal of Educational Science*, 1(2), pp. 24-27. doi:390/60.7585

Thomas, L.J. and Revell, S.H. (2016) 'Resilience in nursing students: An integrative review', *Nurse Education Today*, 36, pp. 457-462. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2015.10.016.

Thomas, J., Jinks, A. and Jack, B. (2015) 'Finessing incivility: The professional socialisation experiences of student nurses' first clinical placement, a grounded theory', *Nurse education today*, 35(12), pp. e4-e9. doi: org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.08.022.

Thomson, R., Docherty, A. and Duffy, R. (2017) 'Nursing students' experiences of mentorship in their final placement', *British Journal of Nursing*, 26(9), pp. 514-521. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2017.26.9.514

Thurston, M.M., Chesson, M.M., Harris, E.C. and Ryan, G.J. (2017) 'Professional Stereotypes of Interprofessional Education Naive Pharmacy and Nursing Students', *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education; Am J Pharm Educ*, 81(5), pp. 84-84. doi: 10.5688/ajpe81584.

Tuffour, I. (2017) ' (2017) *A critical overview of interpretative phenomenological analysis: a contemporary qualitative research approach*. Journal of Healthcare Communications, 2 (4). p. 52. ISSN 2472-1654', *Journal of Healthcare Communications*, 2(4), pp. 52. doi: 10.4172/2472-1654.100093

Tuli, F. (2010) 'The basis of distinction between qualitative and quantitative research in social science: Reflection on ontological, epistemological and methodological perspectives', *Ethiopian Journal of Education and Sciences*, 6(1). doi: 10.4314/ejesc.v6i1.65384

Turnbull (2014) *Exploration of the influences on developing and maintaining a successful mentorship process: An investigation of mentorship from multiple perspectives*. Health Education East of England Local Education and Training board.

Veeramah, V. (2012) 'What are the barriers to good mentoring?', *Nursing times*, 108(39), pp. 12-15.

Vinales, J.J. (2015) 'The mentor as a role model and the importance of belongingness', *British Journal of Nursing*, 24(10), pp. 532-535. doi: 10.12968/bjon.2015.24.10.532.

Vivekananda-Schmidt, P. and Sandars, J. (2018) 'Belongingness and its implications for undergraduate health professions education: a scoping review', *Education for Primary Care*, 29(5), pp. 268-275. doi: 10.1080/14739879.2018.1478677.

Von Colln-Applying, C. and Giuliano, D. (2017) 'A concept analysis of critical thinking: A guide for nurse educators', *Nurse Education Today*, 49, pp. 106-109. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2016.11.007>.

Walsh, R. (2003) 'The methods of reflexivity', *The Humanistic Psychologist*, 31(4), pp. 51-66. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08873267.2003.9986934>

Walsh, A. (2015) 'The effect of social interaction on mental health nurse student learning', *Nurse education in practice; Nurse Education in Practice*, 15(1), pp. 7-12. doi: 10.1016/j.nepr.2014.11.003.

Warne, T., Johansson, U., Papastavrou, E., Tichelaar, E., Tomietto, M., den Bossche, K., Moreno, M. and Saarikoski, M. (2010) 'An exploration of the clinical learning experience of nursing students in nine European countries', *Nurse education today*, 30(8), pp. 809-815. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2010.03.003.

Weaver, K. and Olson, J.K. (2006) 'Understanding paradigms used for nursing research', *Journal of advanced nursing*, 53(4), pp. 459-469. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2648.2006.03740.x.

Wenger, E., McDermott, R., Snyder, W. (2002) *Cultivating communities of practice: a guide to managing knowledge*. Boston: Boston: Harvard Business School Press.

Wenger, E. (1998) *Communities of practice: learning, meaning and identity*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press, 1998.

White, C. (2010) 'A socio-cultural approach to learning in the practice setting', *Nurse education today*, 30(8), pp. 794-797. doi: 10.1016/j.nedt.2010.02.002.

Whitmore, C., Baxter, P.E., Kaasalainen, S. and Ploeg, J. (2018) 'Protocol for a case study to explore the transition to practice of new graduate nurses in long-term care', *SAGE Open Nursing*, pp. 4, doi: 2377960818797251.

Williams, E. and Palmer, C. (2014) 'Student nurses in critical care: benefits and challenges of critical care as a learning environment for student nurses', *Nursing in critical care*, 19(6), pp. 310-315. doi:10.1111/nicc.12053.

Willis, L. *Raising the Bar Shape of Caring: A Review of the Future Education and Training of Registered Nurses and Care Assistants.*, London: Health Education England.

Woods, A., Cashin, A. and Stockhausen, L. (2016) 'Communities of practice and the construction of the professional identities of nurse educators: A review of the literature', *Nurse education today*, 37, pp. 164-169. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2015.12.004>.

Yazan, B. (2015) 'Three approaches to case study methods in education: Yin, Merriam, and Stake', *The qualitative report*, 20(2), pp. 134-152. doi:10.46743/2160-3715/2015.2102

Yilmaz, K. (2013) 'Comparison of quantitative and qualitative research traditions: Epistemological, theoretical, and methodological differences', *European journal of education*, 48(2), pp. 311-325 doi: doi.org/10.1111/ejed.12014

Yin, R.K. (2016) *Qualitative Research from Start to Finish*. 2nd ed. New York. The Guilford Press.

Yin, R.K. (2018) *Case study research: Design and methods*. 6th ed. Thousand Oaks, CA. Sage Publishing.

Appendix 1 NMC Domains

NMC Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (DOMAINS) (NMC, 2008).

1 Establishing effective working relationships

2 Facilitation of learning

3 Assessment and accountability

4 Evaluation of learning

5 Creating an environment for learning

6 Context of practice

7 Evidence-based practice

8 Leadership

Appendix 2 Qualitative Research Methodologies.

The qualitative research methodologies that were considered for this research and subsequently rejected are presented below.

Ethnography

Ethnography is described as a form of social research that studies people in their cultural context (Hammersley and Atkinson 2007). Within contemporary research, ethnography has gained popularity as a means to interpret and understand cultural factors within a specific community or group. Ethnographic research acknowledges that each person brings with them their own individual perspective that is influenced by multiple factors such as their knowledge, previous experiences and historical influences that impact upon the cultures of which they are a part of (Draper, 2012).

Although diverse research methods can be adopted, ethnographic data collection tends to be centred on observations and interviews where the researchers spend lengthy periods of time immersed within a community (Jones and Smith 2017). The observations predominantly focus on observing participants' values, behaviours, language and interactions in an attempt to interpret the meaning behind these, thus developing an understanding of complex situations within everyday practices (Hammersley and Atkinson 2007).

Although there is some evidence of ethnographic research within the practice learning environment (Ewertsson *et al.*, 2017 and Manninen *et al.*, 2014), a frequent criticism of this methodology is the observer effect, where the presence of the researcher can influence the behaviour of participants (Jones and Smith, 2017). As a result, in the context of this research design, bias could be introduced as both students and mentors may well interact differently in the presence of the researcher and lecturer at the local university. Furthermore, the process

of immersion can be labour intensive, in order to be fully immersed within a culture and overcome the observer effect can take months or even years (Draper 2012). Therefore, this approach was not feasible due to the time constraints of part-time doctoral studies.

Phenomenology

Depending on the context, the term phenomenology can hold radically different, albeit related, meanings as it is used to describe both a philosophical perspective and a research method (Earle, 2010; Flood, 2010; Davidsen, 2013). Philosophically, phenomenology is associated with the writings of Husserl, a mathematician in the early twentieth century who became disillusioned with the objective scientific methods being used as a means to understand the social world (Earle, 2010). To understand human consciousness and experience, Husserl's goal was the rigorous study of 'things as they appear' (Dowling, 2007, pp. 132). A critical component of Husserlian phenomenology is eidetic reduction, referring to the bracketing of any pre-conceived perceptions of a phenomenon to experience its essence (Converse, 2012). Over time, other philosophers, including Heidegger, Gadamer, Sartre and Merleau-Ponty have re-theorised this approach in the study of human experience. The aforementioned philosophies are frequently used to underpin contemporary phenomenological research that can be descriptively or interpretively orientated (Dowling, 2007).

As a methodology, phenomenological research attempts to understand the essence of a phenomenon from the perspective of participants who have experienced it (Eddles-Hirsch 2015) and is characterised by the use of semi-structured or unstructured interviews and intensive thematic analysis. Phenomenology has been used previously to successfully investigate the practice learning environment; for example, James and Chapman (2010) explored nursing students lived experience of their clinical placement. However,

phenomenological research is often criticised as it focuses on understanding the meaning of these experiences and not necessarily why they have happened (Tuffour, 2017), suggesting that the wider context and the conditions that led to or triggered these experiences may not be addressed. The aim of this research study is not only to understand practice learning experiences; rather, it is to explore these experiences and the wider contextual factors that may have an impact upon these experiences, as such phenomenology did not align sufficiently with the aim and objectives of this study and was subsequently rejected.

Grounded theory

Whilst the application of grounded theory has evolved over the years, classic grounded theory originated from the work of Glaser and Straus in the mid-1960s, where their focus was the generation of theory from empirical data through the inductive analysis and constant comparison of data (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013). Here the intent of grounded theory moves beyond the description of the situation by generating contextually situating theories to help explain the phenomenon being studied (Creswell and Poth, 2018; Braun and Clarke, 2013; Savin Badin Major, 2013).

Classic grounded theory suggests in-depth knowledge of the literature desensitises the researcher as they can rely on previously identified ideas and concepts (Savin-Baden and Major, 2013; Braun and Clarke, 2013). Alternatively, it is suggested that the literature should be reviewed concurrently throughout the data collection and analysis. This concept of desensitisation was considered a deciding factor when choosing a methodology. An in-depth literature review had already been undertaken as part of the doctoral research process, where the literature and theories related to practice learning had been explored. Furthermore, as this study's research aim and objectives were centred around exploration as opposed to

explanation and did not include the generation of new theory, grounded theory was deemed unsuitable.

Participatory Action Research

Participatory action research (PAR) was also given consideration. Brydon-Miller *et al.*, (2011) define PAR as an interpretative form of inquiry that uses qualitative research methods in an attempt to break free from traditional social science methodologies. The focus and purpose of this collaborative method are to empower participants to take action (McDonald, 2012). For example, researchers work collaboratively with participants through a cyclical process of gathering data, critically reflecting and planning change, to investigate a social problem. Although used frequently within educational research (McNiff, 2010), no PAR studies within the practice learning environment were identified. Whilst the collaborative nature of PAR initially seemed appealing, it was recognised that time constraints of part-time doctoral studies would potentially limit the PAR cycle, as difficulties in implementing and testing any changes may have been encountered. Furthermore, the prescriptive nature of the current NMC Standards to support learning and assessment in practice (NMC, 2008) may have inhibited the implementation of any recommendations identified by the practice learning community being studied and, as such, restrict the effectiveness of PAR, therefore, participatory action research was also rejected.

Appendix 3 Copy Confirmation of Ethical Approval.

From: [REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
Subject: Ethics Application Approved

The source of this email is EXTERNAL to UWS

Dear Claire Bryson,

Your application [REDACTED] Study exploring practice learning experiences, submission [REDACTED] been **approved, with conditions**, by the Health Nursing and Midwifery SEC. The conditions can be found in the attached approval letter.

Dr W MacKay

31/05/2019 (Gordon Mackay, co-chair, ethics)

Dear ClaireBryson,

Your application [REDACTED] A study exploring practice learning experiences, submission [REDACTED] has been approved, with conditions, by the Health Nursing and Midwifery SEC. **You may proceed with your study provided you meet the conditions outlined below;**

Title

Details of the Amendment(s):

Change request: "Demographic information will be collected, as above confidentiality and anonymity will be maintained in accordance with all other sensitive information as outlined in the original application."

Please ensure that the necessary approvals are in place (in writing) to gather and use these data.

Please ensure that you have written permission from the relevant module coordinators to gather and use this information.

If you wish to make any significant changes to your study, you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr W MacKay

Participant information sheet.

A research study exploring what contributes to or inhibits practice learning experiences .

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part.

Who is conducting the study?

What will taking part involve?

The study is looking to understand what contributes to or inhibits practice learning experiences. Using a case study approach different data collection methods will be used. These include:

Focus groups/interviews with pre-registration nursing students.

Focus groups/interviews with those that support learning in practice (Mentors, PEFs, Liaison lecturers and ward managers).

If you agree to take part in this study you will be invited to participate in a focus group or interview to discuss your previous practice learning experiences.

I would ask you to read this information in full and if you have any other questions to get in touch with me.

The focus group will last approximately one hour, where semi structured questions will be asked to promote discussions about your practice learning experiences. Field notes will be taken throughout the focus groups they will also be audio recorded, this will allow the tapes to be transcribed and themes to be established.

Do you have to take part?

You don't have to take part in the study and can at any point during the study withdraw. If you do not wish to take part you need do nothing else and I thank you reading the information.

What are the benefits of taking part?

By participating in the study you will be providing valuable information that can help review the practice learning environment. The information may also be used within peer journal publications and presented within my professional doctorate thesis.

Will taking part be confidential?

You will not be referred to personally in any documentation or publications therefore your confidentiality will be maintained at all times.

How will the information you provide be recorded, stored and protected?

All signed consent forms and audio recordings will be held at the university and be encrypted and stored securely until after my degree has been conferred.

When the study has been completed all information will be destroyed. Under freedom of information legalisation, you are entitled to access the information you have provided at any time.

If you have any further questions or require any more information please get in touch.

Thank you

Claire

Claire Bryson

Consent Form: A Case Study research study exploring practice learning experiences.

I confirm that I have been informed of and understand the purposes of the study and have been given the opportunity to ask questions.

Signature
Date

I understand that I can withdraw from the study at any time.

Signature
Date

I understand that the focus groups/interviews/workshops will be audio recorded and field notes taken. The researcher and supervisory team will have access to this information however any information which may potentially identify me will not be used in any material.

Signature
Date

I understand that the findings from this study will be presented within the researcher's thesis and may appear within publications however any information which may potentially identify me will not be used in any material.

Signature
Date

I agree to participate in the study outlined to me.

Participant signature:

Print name:

Principle research signature:

Date:

One copy retained by researcher, one copy retained by participant.

Appendix 6 Email Invitation to Participate
(Copy of email invitation to participate)

Dear mentor,

As part of my doctoral research, I am carrying out a study looking at students' practice learning experiences.

I am undertaking interviews with students and staff that support their learning in practice, and as an experienced mentor, would like to invite you to participate. The interview should last no longer than an hour of your time. I have enclosed an information sheet and would be grateful if you would consider participating.

If you would like to participate, please forward your expression of interest to the email address will be in touch with potential interview dates and times.

Please do not hesitate to get in touch if you have any other questions.

Thank you for your consideration.

Best wishes

Claire Bryson
Lecturer – Adult Nursing (Part 2 Lead)
School of Health and Life Sciences.

Appendix 7 Copy of Follow up Email (mentors)
(Copy of follow-up email sent to mentor participants)

Thank you for expressing an interest in taking part in this research study exploring student nurses' practice learning [redacted]

[redacted] on the 26th and 27th of June to carry out interviews. The interviews should last no longer than an hour. I would be grateful if you could respond below with the best date and time; however, if these dates do not suit you, I am happy to rearrange.

Preferred Date	Availability
Wednesday 26 th AM	
Wednesday 26 th PM	
Thursday the 27 th AM	
Thursday 27 th PM	

I have enclosed the information sheet and consent forms and would be happy to answer any questions you may have.

Many thanks for your consideration.

Best wishes

Claire Bryson
Lecturer – Adult Nursing (Part 2 Lead)
School of Health and Life Sciences.

Appendix 8 Copy of Follow up Email (students)
(Copy of follow-up email sent to students)

Thank you for expressing an interest in taking part in this research exploring nursing students' practice learning experiences.

I have managed to organise a focus group date on the 20th of June [redacted] at 10am where students will be asked to reflect on their previous learning experiences. The focus group should last no longer than 90 minutes.

If you could let me know if you can attend.

Many thanks in advance for your consideration.

Best wishes

Claire Bryson
Lecturer – Adult Nursing (Part 2 Lead)
School of Health and Life Sciences.

Guide for interviews

Housekeeping and introductions.

Introductions (Check consent forms signed)

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this research as part of my doctoral study. As you know, I am looking to explore practice learning experiences from the perspective of pre-reg student nurses and those that support their learning. I am going to start with some general questions on your mentorship background before focusing on your experiences as a mentor.

General questions.

How long have you been a mentor?

How long were you qualified before becoming a mentor?

Did you complete any training prior to becoming a mentor/if so what?

Focused questions (and prompts)

Can you tell me about supporting student nurses in your area?

- *What does a typical student experience look like in your area?*
- *What sort of students do you get/how frequently?*
- *Do you use a specific/different mentorship model?*
- *Do all staff support student learners?*
- *Do you get any feedback from students about their experiences?*

How do you feel when supporting student nurses in practice?

- *Why do you think this is?*

What do you enjoy about supporting students' practice learning experiences and why?

- *Can you give some examples?*

Are there any challenges supporting students' practice learning experiences?

- *How did this make you feel?*
- *Did you have support when facing these challenges?*
- *Is there anything that could be improved to support you in your role?*

Can you think of anything that could help improve practice learning experiences?

Anything else you would like to add?

Guide Focus Group

Housekeeping and introductions.

Introductions (Check consent forms signed)

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this research as part of my doctoral study. As you know, I am looking to explore practice learning experiences from the perspective of pre-reg student nurses and those that support their learning.

Reminders – Confidentiality of the conversation. Listen and allow others to speak.

I'm going to start with some general questions on your practice learning experiences.

General questions.

Tell me about your practice learning experiences in [REDACTED]

What have you enjoyed about practice and why?

What have you not enjoyed as much?

Focused questions (and prompts)

Can you tell me about being a student nurse in [REDACTED]

- *What does a typical student experience look like?*
- *What makes a good practice learning experience?*
- *Have you experienced different mentorship models, if so what does this look like?*
- *Other than your mentor did you get support from anyone else on placement?*
- *How do you give feedback to the areas about your experience?*

Have you experienced any challenges on placement?

- *How did this make you feel?*
- *Did you have support when facing these challenges?*
- *Is there anything that could be improved to support you in your role?*

Can you think of anything that could help improve practice learning experiences?

Anything else you would like to add?

Probe questions for any interesting points

- *Can you tell me a bit more about that?*
- *How did that make you feel?*
- *Why do you think that happened?*

Appendix 10 Excerpt Reflective Diary (Data collection)

1/6/19.

Carried out my first mentor interviews today. Both mentors that I interviewed had loads of experience supporting students so had plenty to talk about. I was lucky enough to get a room in the education centre at the hospital so it was really handy for the mentors. I used the Dictaphone and had my ipad and spare batteries for backup just in case. The sound was really good so should be easy enough to transcribe. I was feeling really nervous before my first interview, not sure why as I was excited to get the data collection started. It has felt such a long time to get to this stage. My first interview was a bit short and only lasted 25 minutes, I thought it would have lasted longer but felt I rushed the questions and could have been a bit more patient. At the end of the first interview, the mentor and I had a really good conversation about mentorship in general, I wish I had kept the recording going. I managed to take some notes but will keep that in mind for future interviews. Still got some really good information though and pleased to have started collecting the data.

4/6/19

Carried out another 3 mentor interviews today. I felt much more relaxed and comfortable doing them. There were a good range of experiences explored and some challenging topics. It is really interesting to hear the different perspectives. I still haven't confirmed a manager to take part in the study, so planning to send another email out tomorrow. Have sent an email to my supervisors today updating them on how the interviews have been going.

20/6/19.

Had my first focus group today, and all I can say is what a great group of students. I was a bit apprehensive that they wouldn't all attend but it was great to see a full house. I had the wee room at the top of the corridor which was a great size, not too big. The students seemed to

really enjoy the focus group and were really articulate in describing their experiences. There was such maturity in their answers, I wonder if this was because they were year 3 students and almost qualifying. I am sure the focus group would easily have lasted another hour as they were really keen to share their experiences. I had to keep pulling one student back though to the purpose of the focus groups as she kept veering off track and speaking about all things university. I also found it really hard to stay neutral and not contribute as I would normally have chipped in and offered my thoughts. I have one more focus group next week.

25/6/19

Today was the second focus group, it was interesting that the group had a very different feel to it. I wouldn't say it was negative but there was definitely a different vibe. Maybe a bit more reserved. The conversation started off very negatively, especially when speaking about their first experiences and there were some shared stories that were interesting where students in the group had been on placement together and had very different learning experiences. A lot to think about I've made some notes to help my analysis as not starting transcribing until after the summer.

Appendix 11 Worked Example of Data Analysis.

After transcribing and collating all the data, the first reading was focused on line-by-line coding. Using NVivo I looked for key phrases or words within the data and assigned them to a level 1 NVivo node. The aim was to fragment the data (disassembling), at this stage, the codes appeared very descriptive, however I tried to intuitively assign codes to the text without overthinking.

There was an overwhelming number of initial level one nodes (more than 400) however it quickly became clear that many of them were similar or shared a similar meaning, these were then grouped together.

I was initially struck by how powerful some of the words that participants had used. I began to notice how emotional practice learning could be for the participants and became very aware of the emotional language presented in the text.

I then started to look for emotional content across the data within the different participant groups to establish if there was a pattern within the data. This involved me pouring back over the data to look for any theoretical concepts. Initial codes were realigned to more focused codes (level 2 code).

I uncovered polarising emotions that were experienced and became interested in what had led to these differences in experiences and was prompted to review the transcripts again. I also used the NVivo mind-map function to play about with and make sense of the data (see appendix X). It was at this point the tentative ideas and categories emerged.

I then tried to look for relationships between the categories, although I uncovered polarising emotions related to practice learning experiences this did not fully explain how or why this occurred and what impact these emotions had on experiences. As I considered this the patterns became more explicit. For example, how having a sense of belongingness positively influenced students learning experiences. This psychosocial process was underpinned by human connections where interactions and inclusion empowered students. However, this 'ideal' was not always experienced by all students and the negative fallout of this was evident within the data. Therefore, the theme emotional rollercoaster emerged.

Example of how themes emerged.

Original text	Initial Nvivo Node	Level 2 code	Higher level Categories (subthemes)	Final theme
I am not kidding she was brilliant, she taught me the things I didn't feel confident in, cause I was going onto my management placement –	Increased confidence Empowering Nurturing Relationships	Flourishing	Mentoring relationship	Teamwork makes the dream work.

having a good mentor is paramount				
.....I mean I went home crying everyday, the staff, the nursing assistants were horrible to you they spoke to horrible, it was just horrific I hated it, I hated every minute of it	Distress Traumatic Relationships	Incivility	Belongingness	The emotional rollercoaster (Journey)
Both [redacted] I were there and if it wasn't for [redacted] I don't know... I wouldn't have got through it, seriously I would not have made it past the 4 weeks, I would have turned round and quit it was awful.	Support from another student Friendship Relationships	Moral support	Influence of Peers	Teamwork makes the dream work
she could see that I wasn't confident with drips and things and she was like 'right come on' and these are the things you learn from, she took me under her wing, and we got on great,	Interested in student needs. Individualised teaching Interpersonal relationship	Flourishing	Mentoring relationships	
it was horrible and it was such a good learning ward that we could have learned hundreds...but we didn't because they didn't take the time or want to share things with students, and if you're resented being there, you just feel like I don't want to be here. I was left on my own with no direction or support it was awful.	No time Not sharing Excluded Resented Lack of support or guidance	Barriers Alienation Floundering	Belongingness	The emotional rollercoaster (Journey)

Appendix 12 Example Initial Visual Chart Coding NVIVO

Appendix 13 Additional Literature Identified.

Theme	Additional literature identified.
Mentoring relationships	Bowen, Kables and Keatringe, 2019; Hilli <i>et al.</i> 2014; Hale, 2015; Hale and Phillips, 2018; Lin <i>et al.</i> 2018; Miles, 2011; Alston and Hansman, 2020; Eller, Lev and Feurer, 2014; Sheehan <i>et al.</i> 2021; Mikkonen <i>et al.</i> 2020; Lee <i>et al.</i> 2018; Howarth, 2021; Ford <i>et al.</i> 2016; Saunders <i>et al.</i> 2016; Harrison – White, 2020; Bray and Nettleton, 2007; Ewertsson <i>et al.</i> 2017; Harrison-White and Owens 2018; Moores <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Straus et al, 2013.
The student’s role	Connor, 2019; O’Brien and Battisata, 2020; Walsh, 2015; Kalyani <i>et al.</i> 2019
The role of others	Hood <i>et al.</i> , 2014; Thurston, 2017; Lee <i>et al.</i> 2018; Harrison-White, 2020
The role of Peers	Carey <i>et al.</i> 2018; Roberts, 2008; Stenberg and Carlson, 2015; Li et al. 2009; Devlin and Duggan, 2020; Gray and Brown, 2016; Clarke and Casey, 2016; Terry <i>et al.</i> 2019
Belongingness	Gilbert and Brown, 2015; Hopper, 2021; Bulut, Hisar and Demir, 2010; Houghton <i>et al.</i> 2013; Grobecer, 2016; Levett-Jones and Lathlean, 2009a, b.; Felstead and Sringett, 2016; Maslow and Lewis, 1987; King-Hill, 2015; Billett, 2004; 2016; King <i>et al.</i> 2017; Maginnis, 2018; Kelly, 2020; Kern <i>et al.</i> 2014;
The highs and lows of mentoring	Schaffer, 2013; Duffy, 2009; Devlin and Duggan, 2020; Macey, Green and Jardin 2021; Bowen, Kables and Keatringe, 2019;
The students’ emotions	Kalyani <i>et al.</i> , 2020; McCloughen <i>et al.</i> 2020; Stephens, 2013; Delgado <i>et al.</i> 2017; Reyes <i>et al.</i> 2015; Lopez <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Thomas and Revell, 2016; Galvin <i>et al.</i> 2015; Amsrud, Lyberg and Severinsson, 2019; Reyes, 2015; MacIntosh, 2015; Fisher and Oudshoorn, 2019;

